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**Optimization of the method for Loop-mediated isothermal
amplification (LAMP) of nucleic acids for field detection of food- and
waterborne pathogens**

-PhD dissertation-

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Abstract in Englishlanguage:	The UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that by 2050 there will be close to 10 billion people on Earth. The major global challenge is how to provide enough food for everyone, that is safe, ample and produced in a sustainable way. In regard to food safety, large-scale epidemics of foodborne diseases are a persistent threat to public health, as the number of food- and waterborne diseases significantly increases year by year, resulting in the on-going global public health issue. Food- and waterborne microbiological pathogens can be found in a variety of foodstuffs, and their early detection is extremely important to increase overall food safety, and to prevent enormous economic losses. The problems with health-unsafe food in the last 20 years, and a related rise in food poisoning cases internationally, have led to a growing and urgent demand for safe food products that will not pose a danger to consumers. On the other hand, it is equally important to ensure the absence of

microbiological pathogens in the whole process of food production e.g. during crop cultivation where it is very important to perform early detection of pathogens to prevent their further spread and avoid the negative effects on yield and quality of crops or during food processing and storage. Classical microbiological cultivation methods are still considered the "gold standard" in detection of different types of pathogens (bacteria, viruses, pathogenic fungi) during quality analysis, due to their sensitivity, relative low cost and ability to generate qualitative and quantitative information regarding the number and nature of microorganisms of a different origin. However, what is considered perhaps the biggest drawback of these methods is the fact that they require at least 3-4 days to get the first results, and even up to 7 days for confirmatory results. In addition, there are pathogens that cannot be cultivated i.e., so-called *viable but non-culturable* - VBNC pathogens that do not have the ability to form visible colonies, which further hinders the ability to use classical microbiological cultivation methods for their detection. Application of polymerase chain reaction, i.e. PCR, changed the way microbiological analyses are performed in the direction of detecting specific microbial DNA as a target. PCR-based methods that detect pathogen-derived nucleic acids are faster (last up to several hours), very reliable and allow the analysis of VBNC pathogens. However, these techniques depend on precise instruments, clean working conditions and hence, cannot be used in the field. In addition, PCR can give false-positive or false-negative results due to the use of nonspecific primers or to the lack of differentiation between nucleic acids of the living (active) and dead (inactive) cells. To address these challenges, the primary focus of this doctoral dissertation is on development and optimization of innovative nucleic acid based methods for rapid detection of pathogens in food and water. More specifically, the research focus of the dissertation is the application of the isothermal loop-mediated amplification (LAMP) method, which allows for fast, simple, and reliable field detection. This approach for detection of pathogens in food of animal and plant origin and in the environment corresponds to the "One health" paradigm, recommended by the FAO, that is encompassing methods of optimizing the health and well-being of people, animals, plants and environment. In line with this, the **primary objectives (O)** of this doctoral dissertation have been formulated as follows: **O1**) To perform advanced development of the LAMP method for research and potential practical purposes in order to detect pathogens in different complex matrices comprising foodstuffs (meat and vegetable), water, and soil-like matrix; **O2**) to determine applicability of the LAMP method for river water quality assessment as advised by the One health paradigm; **O3**) to improve and optimize procedures for nucleic acid (NA) isolation in order to enable rapid extraction in the field conditions and **O4**) comparison of the efficiency of the developed LAMP protocols versus both the conventional cultivation methods and the PCR method as the "gold standard" for NA amplification-based analyses. **O1** formulated in the above described way comprises **O1.1**) establishing clearly defined protocols for LAMP detection of bacterial pathogens in various food matrices using *Klebsiella aerogenes* species as a model system; The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers,

and **O1.2**) developing LAMP protocol for early detection of pathogenic fungi *Trichoderma* spp. in soil-like matrix. The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers. Final protocol includes implementation of colorimetric detection of the LAMP products using gold nanoparticles, thereby increasing the technology readiness level (TRL) for real-life application of the developed protocol. **O2** focuses on evaluating the potential application of the LAMP method in detecting fecal indicator bacteria (FIB), such as *E. coli*, for river water quality assessment. **O3** deals with enhancing extraction protocols for rapid DNA isolation **O3.1.1**) from the foodstuffs and **O3.1.2**) from soil-like real-life samples (Chelex 100 method) and **O3.2**) from highly contaminated river water samples (a syringe-based DNA isolation method) and provides evaluation of developed protocols for application in the field conditions. **O4** aims to provide conclusions on the applicability of developed LAMP protocols for use in early detection of pathogens of bacterial and fungal origin, in field conditions. The key conclusions derived from the research conducted in this dissertation are that the LAMP method has been successfully optimized for the specific detection of *K. aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp. in various types of real-life samples. Additionally, the LAMP protocol development included design of novel LAMP primers for both *K. aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp. as the primer sequences for these pathogens were not found in the literature. The developed LAMP procedures using novel primers are characterized by high sensitivity and low detection limits for all tested samples, as well as with better efficiency compared to the PCR method. These aspects confirm the significant potential of the LAMP method as a diagnostic tool for pathogen detection. Additionally, the field application of the LAMP method combined with the Chelex 100 method for DNA isolation enables practical use of the developed LAMP protocols under various conditions. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that the LAMP method can also be used for detecting *E. coli* in complex samples such as highly contaminated water, positioning the LAMP method as a very good tool for application following the One Health approach. Notably, the protocols for both LAMP and DNA extraction procedures developed within this thesis still require further increase in TRL before commercial field applications. Taking all of the above into account, this dissertation represents a significant contribution to the research on molecular detection methods and development of innovative diagnostic tools for enhancing food and water safety, that can be of significant importance in addressing the global challenge of ensuring safe food and sustainable environment for the growing population. Further research and application of these methods may greatly contribute to food poisoning prevention, public health and environmental management, as defined in the “One health” agenda.

Accepted by the Scientific Board on:	
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Thesis Defense Board: (title, first name, last name, position, institution)	<p>President: Željko D. Popović, PhD, Associate professor, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad;</p> <p>Member: Ljiljana Šašić Zorić, PhD, Senior Research Associate, BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad;</p> <p>Member: Jasmina Vidić, PhD, Ingénieur de recherche hors classe (equivalent to the title principal research fellow), National Institute for Agricultural, Food and Environmental Research (INRAE), Paris, France;</p> <p>Member (advisor): Ivana Gađanski, PhD, Senior Research Associate, BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad;</p> <p>Member (advisor): Marija Lesjak, PhD, Full professor, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad</p>
Note:	

¹ The author of the doctoral dissertation has signed the following Statements:

56 – Statement on the authorship,

5B – Statement that the printed and e-version of the doctoral dissertation are identical and about personal data,

5r – Statement on copyright licenses.

The paper and e-versions of the Statements are held at the faculty and are not included into the printed thesis.

КЉУЧНА ДОКУМЕНТАЦИЈСКА ИНФОРМАЦИЈА²

Врста рада:	Докторска дисертација
Име и презиме аутора:	MSc Мила Ђисалов
Ментор (титула, име, презиме, звање, институција)	др Ивана Гађански, виши научни сарадник, Институт БиоСенс, Универзитет у Новом Саду проф. др Марија Лесјак, редовни професор, Природно-математички факултет, Универзитет у Новом Саду
Наслов рада:	Оптимизација петљом-посредоване методе изотермалног умножавања нуклеинских киселина (<i>LAMP</i>) за примену у теренској детекцији патогена из хране и воде
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Резиме на српском језику:	Према проценама светске Организације за храну и пољопривреду (ФАО – од <i>енгл.</i> Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), до 2050. године ће на планети Земљи бити близу 10 милијарди људи. Велики глобални изазов је како обезбедити довољно хране за све, која је безбедна, доступна у довољним количинама и произведена на одржив начин. Што се тиче безбедности хране, епидемије великих размера које могу бити узроковане преносом патогена путем хране представљају сталну претњу јавном здрављу, јер се број болести узрокованих овом врстом патогена значајно повећава из године у годину, што доводи до сталног глобалног проблема у области јавног здравља. Микробиолошки патогени који се преносе путем хране и воде могу се наћи у различитим врстама намирница, а њихово рано откривање је изузетно важно за свеукупно повећање безбедности хране, као и за спречавање великих економских губитака. Проблеми са здравствено

небезбедном храном у последњих 20 година, као и пораст примера тровања храном на међународном нивоу, довели су до све веће потражње за безбеднијим производима које неће представљати опасност за потрошаче. С друге стране, подједнако је важно осигурати одсуство микробиолошких патогена и у свим фазама производње хране, укључујући узгајање усева, где је рано откривање патогена кључно за спречавање њиховог ширења и избегавање негативних утицаја на принос и квалитет усева, као и у току прераде и складиштења хране. Класичне микробиолошке методе култивације се још увек сматрају „златним стандардом” у детекцији различитих врста патогена (бактерија, вируса и патогених гљива) приликом анализе квалитета, захваљујући њиховој осетљивости, релативно ниској цени и могућности генерисања квалитативних и квантитативних информација о броју и природи микроорганизама добијених из узорака различитог порекла. Међутим, оно што се сматра можда највећом маном ових метода јесте чињеница да захтевају најмање 3–4 дана да би се добили претпостављени резултати, а чак и до 7 дана за потврдне резултате. Такође, неки патогени могу бити вијабилни, али се не могу култивисати (*енгл.* viable but non culturable – VBNC), односно немају могућност формирања видљивих колонија, што даље омета могућност коришћења класичних микробиолошких метода култивације за њихово откривање. Примена ланчане реакције полимеразе, тј. PCR-а, променила је начин извођења микробиолошких анализа у правцу детекције специфичне микробне ДНК као таргета. Методе засноване на PCR-у које откривају нуклеинску киселину која потиче од патогена, су брже (трају до неколико сати), веома поуздане и омогућују анализу VBNC патогена. Међутим, ове технике зависе од прецизних инструмената, чистоће радних услова и не могу се користити на лицу места тј. на терену. Осим тога, PCR може дати лажно позитивне или лажно негативне резултате услед неспецифичног умножавања, најчешће због примене неспецифичних почетница, или због немогућности разликовања нуклеинских киселина пореклом из живих (активних) и мртвих (инактивних) ћелија патогена. У циљу решавања ових изазова, примарни фокус ове докторске дисертације је на развоју и оптимизацији иновативних метода заснованих на нуклеинским киселинама за брзо и ефикасно откривање патогена у храни и води. Тачније, у жижи истраживања дисертације је примена петљом-посредоване изотермалне методе умножавања нуклеинских киселина тј. LAMP-а (од *енгл.* Loop-mediated isothermal amplification) која омогућава брзу, једноставну и поуздану детекцију на терену. Овакав приступ откривања патогена у храни животињског и биљног порекла и у животној средини одговара парадигми „Једно здравље“ (*енгл.* “One health”), коју препоручује ФАО, а која обухвата методе оптимизације здравља и добробити људи, животиња, биљака и животне средине. У складу са овим, примарни циљеви ове докторске дисертације су формулисани на следећи начин: **1)** спровођење напредног развоја LAMP методе за истраживачке и потенцијално практичне сврхе у циљу откривања патогена у различитим комплексним матрицама као што су намирнице (месо и поврће), вода и матрикс налик земљишту; **2)**

утврђивање применљивости LAMP методе за процену kvaliteta речне воде у складу са парадигмом „Једно здравље“; **3)** побољшање и оптимизација процедуре за изолацију нуклеинских киселина, како би се омогућила брза изолација нуклеинских киселина у теренским условима и **4)** поређење ефикасности развијених LAMP протокола са конвенционалним методама култивације и PCR методом као „златног стандарда“ за анализе засноване на умножавању нуклеинских киселина. Циљ **1)** формулисан на горе описани начин обухвата **1.1)** успостављање јасно дефинисаних протокола за LAMP детекцију бактеријских патогена у различитим матрицама хране користећи врсту *Klebsiella aerogenes* као модел систем; **1.2)** развој LAMP протокола за рано откривање патогених гљива *Trichoderma* spp. у матрицама налик земљишту. Финални протокол обухвата имплементацију колориметријске детекције LAMP производа коришћењем наночестица злата, чиме се повећава ниво технолошке спремности (ТРЛ – од енгл. technology readiness level) за реалну примену развијеног протокола; циљ **2)** се фокусира на процену потенцијалне примене LAMP методе у откривању фекалних индикаторских бактерија (ФИБ), као што је *E. coli*, за процену квалитета речне воде; и циљ **3)** се бави унапређењем протокола екстракције за брзу изолацију ДНК **3.1.1)** из намирница и **3.1.2)** из реалних узорака налик земљишту (Chelex 100 метода) и **3.2)** из високозагађених узорака речне воде (методе екстракције ДНК на бази шприца) и обезбеђује евалуацију развијених протокола за примену у теренским условима. Циљ **4)** тежи да пружи закључке о применљивости развијених LAMP протокола за примену у раном откривању патогена бактеријског и гљивичног порекла у теренским условима. Најзначајнији закључци који произилазе из истраживања спроведеног у оквиру ове докторске дисертације су да је LAMP метода успешно оптимизирана за специфичну детекцију *K. aerogenes* и *Trichoderma* spp. у различитим врстама реалних узорака. Додатно, развој LAMP протокола подразумевао је и дизајн потпуно нових, до сада непостојећих LAMP почетница за *K. aerogenes* и *Trichoderma* spp., јер секвенце почетница за ове патогене нису биле доступне у литератури. Развијени LAMP протоколи који користе нове почетнице карактеришу се високом осетљивошћу и ниским границама детекције за све тестиране узорке, као и бољом ефикасношћу у поређењу са PCR методом. Ови аспекти потврђују значајан потенцијал LAMP методе као дијагностичког алата за откривање патогена. Поред тога, теренска примена LAMP методе у комбинацији са Chelex 100 методом за изолацију ДНК омогућава практичну употребу развијених LAMP протокола под различитим условима. Штавише, резултати су показали да се LAMP метода може користити и за детекцију *E. coli* у сложеним узорцима као што је високозагађена вода, позиционирајући LAMP методу као изузетно користан алат за примену у складу са приступом „Једно здравље“. Треба нагласити да протоколи за извођење LAMP-а и изолације ДНК развијени у оквиру ове докторске дисертације захтевају даље повећање ТРЛ-а пре комерцијалне примене на терену. Узимајући све наведено у обзир, ова дисертација представља значајан допринос истраживању метода молекуларне детекције и развоју иновативних

	дијагностичких алата за унапређење безбедности хране и воде, који могу бити од великог значаја у решавању глобалног изазова – постојање безбедне хране и животне средине за растућу популацију. Даља истраживања и примена ових метода могу у великој мери допринети превенцији тровања храном, управљању јавним здрављем и животном средином, као што је дефинисано у агенди „Једно здравље“.
Датум прихватања теме од стране надлежног већа:	
Датум одбране: (Попуњава одговарајућа служба)	
Чланови комисије: (титула, име, презиме, звање, институција)	Председник: др Жељко Д. Поповић, ванредни професор, Природно-математички факултет, Универзитет у Новом Саду; Члан: др Љиљана Шашић Зорић, виши научни сарадник, Институт БиоСенс, Универзитет у Новом Саду; Члан: др Јасмина Видић, Ingénieur de recherche hors classe (еквивалент звању научни саветник), Национални институт за пољопривредна, прехранбена и еколошка истраживања (ИНРАЕ), Париз, Француска; Члан (ментор): др Ивана Гађански, виши научни сарадник, Институт БиоСенс, Универзитет у Новом Саду; Члан (ментор): др Марија Лесјак, редовни професор, Природно-математички факултет, Универзитет у Новом Саду
Напомена:	

² Аутор докторске дисертације потписао је и приложио следеће Обрасце:

5б – Изјава о ауторству;

5в – Изјава о истоветности штампане и електронске верзије и о личним подацима;

5г – Изјава о коришћењу.

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List of abbreviation

A

ANOVA – analysis of variance

AuNPs – gold nanoparticles

B

BIP – backward inner primer

BLAST – Basic Local Alignment Search Tool

bp – base pairs

B3 – backward outer primer

C

CCA – chromogenic coliform agar

CDC – United States Centers for Disease Control

CFU – colony forming units

CO₂ – carbon dioxide

Ct – cycle threshold

D

DNA – deoxyribonucleic acid

dNTPs – deoxyribonucleoside triphosphates

dsDNA – double-stranded DNA

ΔG – Gibbs free energy

E

ECDC – European Center for Disease Prevention and Control

eDNA – environmental DNA

EL1α – elongation factor 1 alpha

F

FAO – Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

F3 – forward outer primer

FIB – fecal indicator bacteria

FIP – forward inner primer

H

HDC – histidine decarboxylase coding gene

HPB – histamine-producing bacteria

HRM – high resolution melting

K

KCl – potassium chloride

L

LAMP – Loop-mediated isothermal amplification

LB – loop backward

LF – loop forward

LFA – lateral flow immunoassay

LOD – limit of detection

M

MA – malt agar

McF – McFarland standard

Mg²⁺ – magnesium ions

MgCl₂ – magnesium chloride

Mg₂P₂O₇ – magnesium pyrophosphate

MgSO₄ – magnesium sulfate

Mn²⁺ – manganese ions

MnCl₂ – manganese (II) chloride

N

NaCl – sodium chloride

NAs – nucleic acids

NTC – no template control

O

O₂ – oxygen

P

PBS – phosphate-buffered saline

PC – primer candidate

PCR – polymerase chain reaction

PEG – polyethylene glycol

pH – potential of hydrogen

PPi⁻ – pyrophosphate ions

PoN – point of need

POC – point of care

R

RBA – rose bengal agar

R&D – research and development

RNA – ribonucleic acid

S

ssDNA – single-stranded DNA

T

TBE – tris-borate-EDTA

TE – tris-EDTA

tef1 – transcription elongation factor 1
alpha coding gene

Tm – melting temperature

TSA – tryptone soya agar

TSB – tryptone soya broth

Tt – time to threshold value

V

VBNC – viable but non-culturable

W

WHO – World Health Organization

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Abstract

The UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that by 2050 there will be close to 10 billion people on Earth. The major global challenge is how to provide enough food for everyone, that is safe, ample and produced in a sustainable way. In regard to food safety, large-scale epidemics of foodborne diseases are a persistent threat to public health, as the number of food- and waterborne diseases significantly increases year by year, resulting in the on-going global public health issue. Food- and waterborne microbiological pathogens can be found in a variety of foodstuffs, and their early detection is extremely important to increase overall food safety, and to prevent enormous economic losses. The problems with health-unsafe food in the last 20 years, and a related rise in food poisoning cases internationally, have led to a growing and urgent demand for safe food products that will not pose a danger to consumers. On the other hand, it is equally important to ensure the absence of microbiological pathogens in the whole process of food production e.g. during crop cultivation where it is very important to perform early detection of pathogens to prevent their further spread and avoid the negative effects on yield and quality of crops or during food processing and storage. Classical microbiological cultivation methods are still considered the "gold standard" in detection of different types of pathogens (bacteria, viruses, pathogenic fungi) during quality analysis, due to their sensitivity, relative low cost and ability to generate qualitative and quantitative information regarding the number and nature of microorganisms of a different origin. However, what is considered perhaps the biggest drawback of these methods is the fact that they require at least 3-4 days to get the first results, and even up to 7 days for confirmatory results. In addition, there are pathogens that cannot be cultivated i.e., so-called *viable but non-culturable* - *VBNC* pathogens that do not have the ability to form visible colonies, which further hinders the ability to use classical microbiological cultivation methods for their detection. Application of polymerase chain reaction, i.e. PCR, changed the way microbiological analyses are performed in the direction of detecting specific microbial DNA as a target. PCR-based methods that detect pathogen-derived nucleic acids are faster (last up to several hours), very reliable and allow the analysis of *VBNC* pathogens. However, these techniques depend on precise instruments, clean working conditions and hence, cannot be used in the field. In addition, PCR can give false-positive or false-negative results due to the use of nonspecific primers or to the lack of differentiation between nucleic acids of the living (active) and dead (inactive) cells. To address these challenges, the primary focus of

this doctoral dissertation is on development and optimization of innovative nucleic acid based methods for rapid detection of pathogens in food and water. More specifically, the research focus of the dissertation is the application of the isothermal loop-mediated amplification (LAMP) method, which allows for fast, simple, and reliable field detection. This approach for detection of pathogens in food of animal and plant origin and in the environment corresponds to the “One health” paradigm, recommended by the FAO, that is encompassing methods of optimizing the health and well-being of people, animals, plants and environment. In line with this, the **primary objectives (O)** of this doctoral dissertation have been formulated as follows: **O1)** To perform advanced development of the LAMP method for research and potential practical purposes in order to detect pathogens in different complex matrices comprising foodstuffs (meat and vegetable), water, and soil-like matrix; **O2)** to determine applicability of the LAMP method for river water quality assessment as advised by the One health paradigm; **O3)** to improve and optimize procedures for nucleic acid (NA) isolation in order to enable rapid extraction in the field conditions and **O4)** comparison of the efficiency of the developed LAMP protocols versus both the conventional cultivation methods and the PCR method as the “gold standard” for NA amplification-based analyses. **O1** formulated in the above described way comprises **O1.1)** establishing clearly defined protocols for LAMP detection of bacterial pathogens in various food matrices using *Klebsiella aerogenes* species as a model system; The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers, and **O1.2)** developing LAMP protocol for early detection of pathogenic fungi *Trichoderma* spp. in soil-like matrix. The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers. Final protocol includes implementation of colorimetric detection of the LAMP products using gold nanoparticles, thereby increasing the technology readiness level (TRL) for real-life application of the developed protocol. **O2** focuses on evaluating the potential application of the LAMP method in detecting fecal indicator bacteria (FIB), such as *E. coli*, for river water quality assessment. **O3** deals with enhancing extraction protocols for rapid DNA isolation **O3.1.1)** from the foodstuffs and **O3.1.2)** from soil-like real-life samples (Chelex 100 method) and **O3.2)** from highly contaminated river water samples (a syringe-based DNA isolation method) and provides evaluation of developed protocols for application in the field conditions. **O4** aims to provide conclusions on the applicability of developed LAMP protocols for use in early detection of pathogens of bacterial and fungal origin, in field conditions. The key conclusions derived from the research conducted in this dissertation are that the LAMP method has been successfully optimized for the specific detection of *K. aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp. in

various types of real-life samples. Additionally, the LAMP protocol development included design of novel LAMP primers for both *K. aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp. as the primer sequences for these pathogens were not found in the literature. The developed LAMP procedures using novel primers are characterized by high sensitivity and low detection limits for all tested samples, as well as with better efficiency compared to the PCR method. These aspects confirm the significant potential of the LAMP method as a diagnostic tool for pathogen detection. Additionally, the field application of the LAMP method combined with the Chelex 100 method for DNA isolation enables practical use of the developed LAMP protocols under various conditions. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that the LAMP method can also be used for detecting *E. coli* in complex samples such as highly contaminated water, positioning the LAMP method as a very good tool for application following the One Health approach. Notably, the protocols for both LAMP and DNA extraction procedures developed within this thesis still require further increase in TRL before commercial field applications. Taking all of the above into account, this dissertation represents a significant contribution to the research on molecular detection methods and development of innovative diagnostic tools for enhancing food and water safety, that can be of significant importance in addressing the global challenge of ensuring safe food and sustainable environment for the growing population. Further research and application of these methods may greatly contribute to food poisoning prevention, public health and environmental management, as defined in the “One health” agenda.

Key words: LAMP; isothermal method; nucleic acids; detection of pathogenic microorganisms; food safety; food security; field detection

Резиме

Према проценама светске Организације за храну и пољопривреду (ФАО – од *енгл.* Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), до 2050. године ће на планети Земљи бити близу 10 милијарди људи. Велики глобални изазов је како обезбедити довољно хране за све, која је безбедна, доступна у довољним количинама и произведена на одржив начин. Што се тиче безбедности хране, епидемије великих размера које могу бити узроковане преносом патогена путем хране представљају сталну претњу јавном здрављу, јер се број болести узрокованих овом врстом патогена значајно повећава из године у годину, што доводи до сталног глобалног проблема у области јавног здравља. Микробиолошки патогени који се преносе путем хране и воде могу се наћи у различитим врстама намирница, а њихово рано откривање је изузетно важно за свеукупно повећање безбедности хране, као и за спречавање великих економских губитака. Проблеми са здравствено небезбедном храном у последњих 20 година, као и пораст примера тровања храном на међународном нивоу, довели су до све веће потражње за безбеднијим производима које неће представљати опасност за потрошаче. С друге стране, подједнако је важно осигурати одсуство микробиолошких патогена и у свим фазама производње хране, укључујући узгајање усева, где је рано откривање патогена кључно за спречавање њиховог ширења и избегавање негативних утицаја на принос и квалитет усева, као и у току прераде и складиштења хране. Класичне микробиолошке методе култивације се још увек сматрају „златним стандардом” у детекцији различитих врста патогена (бактерија, вируса и патогених гљива) приликом анализе квалитета, захваљујући њиховој осетљивости, релативно ниској цени и могућности генерисања квалитативних и квантитативних информација о броју и природи микроорганизама добијених из узорака различитог порекла. Међутим, оно што се сматра можда највећом маном ових метода јесте чињеница да захтевају најмање 3–4 дана да би се добили претпостављени резултати, а чак и до 7 дана за потврдне резултате. Такође, неки патогени могу бити вијабилни, али се не могу култивисати (*енгл.* viable but non culturable – VBNC), односно немају могућност формирања видљивих колонија, што даље омета могућност коришћења класичних микробиолошких метода култивације за њихово откривање. Примена ланчане реакције полимеразе, тј. PCR-а, променила је начин извођења микробиолошких анализа у правцу детекције специфичне микробне ДНК као таргета. Методе засноване на PCR-у које

откривају нуклеинску киселину која потиче од патогена, су брже (трају до неколико сати), веома поуздане и омогућују анализу VBNC патогена. Међутим, ове технике зависе од прецизних инструмената, чистоће радних услова и не могу се користити на лицу места тј. на терену. Осим тога, PCR може дати лажно позитивне или лажно негативне резултате услед неспецифичног умножавања, најчешће због примене неспецифичних почетница, или због немогућности разликовања нуклеинских киселина пореклом из живих (активних) и мртвих (инактивних) ћелија патогена. У циљу решавања ових изазова, примарни фокус ове докторске дисертације је на развоју и оптимизацији иновативних метода заснованих на нуклеинским киселинама за брзо и ефикасно откривање патогена у храни и води. Тачније, у жижи истраживања дисертације је примена петљом-посредоване изотермалне методе умножавања нуклеинских киселина тј. LAMP-а (од *енгл.* Loop-mediated isothermal amplification) која омогућава брзу, једноставну и поуздану детекцију на терену. Овакав приступ откривања патогена у храни животињског и биљног порекла и у животној средини одговара парадигми „Једно здравље“ (*енгл.* “One health”), коју препоручује ФАО, а која обухвата методе оптимизације здравља и добробити људи, животиња, биљака и животне средине. У складу са овим, примарни циљеви ове докторске дисертације су формулисани на следећи начин: **1)** спровођење напредног развоја LAMP методе за истраживачке и потенцијално практичне сврхе у циљу откривања патогена у различитим комплексним матрицама као што су намирнице (месо и поврће), вода и матрикс налик земљишту; **2)** утврђивање применљивости LAMP методе за процену квалитета речне воде у складу са парадигмом „Једно здравље“; **3)** побољшање и оптимизација процедуре за изолацију нуклеинских киселина, како би се омогућила брза изолација нуклеинских киселина у теренским условима и **4)** поређење ефикасности развијених LAMP протокола са конвенционалним методама култивације и PCR методом као „златног стандарда“ за анализе засноване на умножавању нуклеинских киселина. Циљ **1)** формулисан на горе описани начин обухвата **1.1)** успостављање јасно дефинисаних протокола за LAMP детекцију бактеријских патогена у различитим матрицама хране користећи врсту *Klebsiella aerogenes* као модел систем; **1.2)** развој LAMP протокола за рано откривање патогених гљива у матриксу налик земљишту коришћењем *Trichoderma* spp. као модел за патогене гљиве и супstrate који се користе за гајење печурака као матрице налик земљишту. Финални протокол обухвата имплементацију колориметријске детекције LAMP производа коришћењем наночестица злата, чиме се повећава ниво технолошке спремности (ТРЛ – од *енгл.*

technology readiness level) за реалну примену развијеног протокола; циљ 2) се фокусира на процену потенцијалне примене LAMP методе у откривању фекалних индикаторских бактерија (ФИБ), као што је *E. coli*, за процену квалитета речне воде; и циљ 3) се бави унапређењем протокола екстракције за брзу изолацију ДНК 3.1.1) из намирница и 3.1.2) из реалних узорака налик земљишту (Chelex 100 метода) и 3.2) из високозагађених узорака речне воде (методе екстракције ДНК на бази шприца) и обезбеђује евалуацију развијених протокола за примену у теренским условима. Циљ 4) тежи да пружи закључке о применљивости развијених LAMP протокола за примену у раном откривању патогена бактеријског и гљивичног порекла у теренским условима. Најзначајнији закључци који произилазе из истраживања спроведеног у оквиру ове докторске дисертације су да је LAMP метода успешно оптимизирана за специфичну детекцију *K. aerogenes* и *Trichoderma* spp. у различитим врстама реалних узорака. Додатно, развој LAMP протокола подразумевао је и дизајн потпуно нових, до сада непостојећих LAMP почетница за *K. aerogenes* и *Trichoderma* spp., јер секвенце почетница за ове патогене нису биле доступне у литератури. Развијени LAMP протоколи који користе нове почетнице карактеришу се високом осетљивошћу и ниским границама детекције за све тестиране узорке, као и бољом ефикасношћу у поређењу са PCR методом. Ови аспекти потврђују значајан потенцијал LAMP методе као дијагностичког алата за откривање патогена. Поред тога, теренска примена LAMP методе у комбинацији са Chelex 100 методом за изолацију ДНК омогућава практичну употребу развијених LAMP протокола под различитим условима. Штавише, резултати су показали да се LAMP метода може користити и за детекцију *E. coli* у сложеним узорцима као што је високозагађена вода, позиционирајући LAMP методу као изузетно користан алат за примену у складу са приступом „Једно здравље“. Треба нагласити да протоколи за извођење LAMP-а и изолације ДНК развијени у оквиру ове докторске дисертације захтевају даље повећање ТРЛ-а пре комерцијалне примене на терену. Узимајући све наведено у обзир, ова дисертација представља значајан допринос истраживању метода молекуларне детекције и развоју иновативних дијагностичких алата за унапређење безбедности хране и воде, који могу бити од великог значаја у решавању глобалног изазова – постојање безбедне хране и животне средине за растућу популацију. Даља истраживања и примена ових метода могу у великој мери допринети превенцији тровања храном, управљању јавним здрављем и животном средином, као што је дефинисано у агенди „Једно здравље“.

Кључне речи: LAMP; изотермална метода; нуклеинске киселине; детекција микробиолошких патогена; сигурност хране; безбедност хране; теренска детекција

1. Introduction

1.1 Foodborne and waterborne pathogens

The World Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that by 2050, there will be close to 10 billion people on Earth. The key goal is to ensure that everyone has access to adequate food and water supplies while also maintaining sustainable production methods (FAO, 2023). However, food- and waterborne pathogens consistently pose a challenge toward achieving this goal, given their annual increase and direct correlation with both human health and significant economic loss (Law et al., 2015).

Food- and waterborne pathogens can be found in a variety of foods that are consumed on a daily basis. Namely, food provide an excellent environment for the growth and development of microorganisms, which depends on factors such as the food's structure, pH, moisture content and availability of nutrients. External factors like temperature, relative humidity and gas availability (CO₂, O₂) also play an important role in the development of microorganisms. The emergence of food scandals over the last 20 years, coupled with the rising number of food poisoning cases at the international level, has led to an increasing demand for safer products that do not pose a threat to consumers (Quintela Baluja et al., 2014; Baraketi et al., 2018). It should be emphasized that water, essential for many food system activities including agriculture and food processing, can serve as a medium for microbiological hazards, necessitating the joint consideration of food and water pathogen risks. Efficient pathogen detection in both food and water is crucial for preventing contamination and ensuring public health within the “One Health” framework (FAO, 2023). Furthermore, for a sustainable food production system, it is also essential to ensure the absence of pathogens which are known to have a negative impact on the yield and quality in the production process of agricultural crops.

There are over 250 different foodborne diseases known to affect approximately one-third of the World's population annually (Stein and Chirilă, 2017). However, the incidence of these diseases has been underreported and underestimated. The process of globalization, the transportation of food products over longer distances from their original locations, and the numerous stages where contamination can occur have collectively heightened the difficulty of investigating foodborne and waterborne outbreaks (Stein and Chirilă, 2017). Specifically, it is recognized that foodborne pathogens can enter, transmit, and potentially (cross)contaminate at any stage of the food chain (Stein and Chirilă, 2017; Sahoo et al., 2022).

Another significant threat posed by pathogenic bacteria in food and water is their increasing resistance to antibiotics (White et al., 2002; Taviani et al., 2022). In 2017, the World Health

Organization published a "list of bacteria in urgent need of new antibiotics" (Tacconelli and Magrini, 2017). This list was further updated by WHO in May 2024 to guide and encourage the research and development (R&D) of new antibiotics and tools to combat growing global antimicrobial resistance (WHO, 2024). The list includes bacteria known to be transmitted through food and water, which pose a particular threat in hospitals, nursing homes, and among patients using devices such as ventilators and blood catheters. In this doctoral dissertation, *Klebsiella* spp., and *Escherichia coli* are used as models for general food and waterborne pathogens, respectively. The model pathogen bacteria are used for e.g. novel primer design (*K. aerogenes*), DNA extraction protocol from different matrices, comparison of different LAMP approaches, and comparison to Real Time PCR as a standard method. In addition, *Klebsiella* spp. and *E. coli*, are among the highlighted species on the WHO list of bacteria in urgent need of new antibiotics, rendering obtained data on model bacteria relevant as novel findings as well.

Given the acknowledged necessity of enhancing food production through the development of tools for detecting pathogens detrimental to agricultural crops, this doctoral dissertation focuses on development of a LAMP assay for detection of the significant pathogen in agrifood sector, the *Trichoderma* fungus. Importantly, the assay development comprises steps that increase the technology readiness level (TRL) for real-life application of the developed LAMP assay. Further elaboration on the importance of detecting this fungus will be provided in subsequent sections.

1.1.1 *Klebsiella aerogenes* as a model of foodborne bacteria

Klebsiella aerogenes is a facultatively anaerobic gram-negative bacterium belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, which comprises over 30 genera. Bacteria from this family are known for their respiratory and fermentative metabolism i.e. their ability to adapt to aerobic and anaerobic metabolism (Gundogan, 2014; Buckle, 2015).

They are commonly found in soil, water, plants and in the gastrointestinal tract of various animals, ranging from worms and insects to humans (Gundogan, 2014). Many enterobacteria are human pathogens, while *K. aerogenes* belongs to the group of opportunistic pathogens, which typically cause infections under specific conditions as is the case e.g. in nosocomial (healthcare related) infections. Instances commonly arise in patients with compromised immune systems or individuals with impaired intestinal mucosal barrier of the intestine. From there, this bacterium can lead to infections of the respiratory, circulatory, or urinary systems.

Compared to other enterobacteria, *K. aerogenes* is the leading cause of sepsis and even patient mortality (Gu et al., 2022). Statistics indicate that this species is a prevalent cause of gastrointestinal infections (Kamio and Espinoza, 2022). Additionally, *Klebsiella* rapidly develops resistance to antibiotics, making treatment complicated and time-consuming, although still feasible (Miró et al., 1995; Uzeh and Imafidon, 2022; Kamio and Espinoza, 2022). Given all these considerations, the development of tools for early and specific detection of this bacterium in different types of samples is of great importance.

In this thesis, *K. aerogenes* is used as a model for foodborne pathogens, based on the fact that it can survive the wastewater treatment process, potentially contributing to water contamination, and consequently to the food contamination since contaminated water can enter the food production pipeline via irrigation systems (El-Sayed et al., 2015). For *K. aerogenes*, novel primers were designed, tested, and validated. DNA extraction protocols from various matrices (vegetables and meat) were optimized for intended use in the field. Subsequently, the formulated DNA extraction protocols were tested for both Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR (as standard method) to evaluate the effectiveness of the developed LAMP assay.

1.1.2 *Trichoderma* spp. – pathogenic fungus in edible mushroom production

It has been previously emphasized that one of the main problems facing society today is how to provide enough food for everyone in the future. This challenge has led to a growing interest in sustainable food sources and urban agriculture. One crop that has emerged as a popular choice for urban farms are edible mushrooms (Okuda, 2022; FAO, 2023).

Cultivated edible mushrooms represent a significant nutritional source and hold economic importance in various regions across the world (Marshall, 2009; Shamugam and Kertesz, 2023). Apart from their nutritional value, mushrooms are appealing due to their antioxidant activity and therapeutic properties. Additionally, their distinctive taste and unique texture make them an attractive choice for inclusion as a food ingredient or as a substitute for food additives (Okuda, 2022; FAO, 2023) both in traditional food products and in the emerging field of alternative proteins.

In addition to their positive nutritional characteristics, mushrooms are already a sustainable food source that can be grown using organic waste products and minimal resources. As a result, many urban farms are choosing to grow and sell mushrooms to promote sustainable agriculture and provide fresh, local food to their communities (Dorr et al., 2021; Prajapati et al., 2023).

Modern mushroom farming carries various environmental impacts (Chang and Wasser, 2020). However, these impacts can be mitigated through the application of circular economy principles, particularly by upcycling organic waste in the cultivation process. Specifically, the cultivation of *Agaricus bisporus* (champignon), one of the most commonly grown and consumed mushroom species (Zicari et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2020), involves using compost, an organic substrate produced through a thermophilic microbial process that includes crop residues, underutilized wood, nitrogen-containing additives (such as poultry or horse manure) (Figure 1A), seed meal, or synthetic nitrogen sources like urea or ammonium nitrate, along with gypsum. Compost serves as both a growing medium for mushroom mycelium and a source of nutrition, as the mycelium degrades organic material to release essential nutrients (Kertesz and Thai, 2018; McGee 2018). In addition, during the fruit-bearing phase, adding a layer of peat, known as casing soil (Figure 1A), to the composted substrate is essential for optimal mushroom growth (Šašić Zorić et al., 2023; Djisalov et al., 2024). Finally, casing soil induces the growth of mushroom fruiting bodies and maintains the environmental conditions in the compost (McGee 2018).

In champignon production, the emergence of green mold in the nursery is a prominent issue. This disease, caused by the rapid invasion of fungi from the genus *Trichoderma* spp. in cultivation bags, significantly impedes mushroom fructification (Figure 1B). When compost or casing are infected with aggressive species such as *Trichoderma harzianum*, the production of mushrooms is suspended in the affected areas. *Trichoderma*, known for its voracious consumption of various fungi and its high capability for nutrient uptake, monopolizes the available nutrients, preventing mushroom growth (Castle et al., 1998; Zicari et al., 2012).

Trichoderma spores infiltrate mushroom-growing facilities through contaminated spawn, compost, casing soil and wood. The spread of green mold is further facilitated by contaminated tools, substrate, and clothing of mushroom growers. Additionally, transmission can occur through contaminated air and insect vectors, such as sciarid mushroom flies (Maeda et al., 2011; Šašić Zorić et al., 2023; Djisalov et al., 2024).

Early detection of *Trichoderma* spp. on the substrate for growing edible mushrooms is crucial since the infection becomes visible only after the formation of dark green spores, when it is already too late to intervene (Figure 1B). more compact. This doctoral dissertation aims to develop a molecular tool for early and specific detection of this fungal pathogen to enhance organic mushroom production, as green mold disease in *A. bisporus* can lead to yield losses of

60% to 100%, significantly impacting producers' profits (Šašić Zorić et al., 2023). Since some species of *Trichoderma* can adversely affect human health (Chouaki et al., 2002; Sal et al., 2022), the development of this molecular tool is beneficial for ensuring health and safety.

Figure 1. A) Illustration of main stages in mushroom cultivation process; B) Images of mushroom-growing substrate contaminated with *Trichoderma harzianum*. (Adapted from Djisalov et. al., 2024).

1.1.3 *Escherichia coli* as a model of waterborne bacteria

Contamination of water (and food) with fecal bacteria persists as a significant problem with profound implications for public health and the economy (Walker et al., 2019). *Escherichia coli* is considered as the best biological indicator for water contamination (Edberg et al., 2000). Depending on environmental conditions such as temperature and microflora, this rod-shaped, facultatively anaerobic, Gram-negative bacterium can survive in drinking water during 4 to 12 weeks (Edberg et al., 2000).

E. coli, a member of the fecal coliform subgroup, is commonly found in the intestines of both humans and animals. While the majority of *E. coli* strains are non-pathogenic, some can cause serious gastrointestinal and urinary illnesses, including fatalities (Kirschner et al., 2009).

Globally, there is a crucial need for a rapid and sensitive detection of microbial contamination in water samples to control waterborne diseases. Addressing this challenge requires the use of innovative molecular methods to reliably identify harmful bacteria known to be present in very complex and difficult-to-manipulate water samples, such as highly polluted river water samples near city sewage outfalls.

In this thesis, *E. coli* is used as a model for waterborne pathogens, found in complex and difficult-to-manipulate water samples based on the fact that it is the best biological indicator for water contamination with fecal bacteria. For *E. coli*, primers from literature were tested and validated. DNA extraction protocol from raw water samples (Danube river) was modified for time and cost efficiency. Subsequently, the formulated DNA extraction protocol was validated by both Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR (as standard method).

1.2 Overview of methods for foodborne and waterborne pathogen detection

Development and integration of sensitive and efficient methods for detecting the presence of pathogens are crucial for food safety control and the establishment of a sustainable food production system (Zhang, 2013). Ideally, a method for detecting pathogens should align with the World Health Organization's ASSURED criteria (Land et. al., 2019):

- **A** – Affordable to end-users and the health system;
- **S** – Sensitive;
- **S** – Specific;
- **U** – User-friendly;

- **R** – Rapid and robust;
- **E** – Equipment free or simple;
- **D** – Deliverable to end-users.

1.2.1 Microbiological methods for pathogen detection

The standard approach for detecting pathogens in food involves microbiological cultivation on a nutrient medium. This method comprises three basic steps for its execution (Figure 2): 1) sample preparation which involves homogenization of the sample; 2) cultivation of microbes on a nutrient medium – which consists of cultivating the samples firstly in enrichment broth (in order to increase a small number of desired organisms to detectable levels), then on selective medium (required for different bacterial strains to grow), and finally on isolation medium, and 3) biochemical identification – which implies conducting a large number of biochemical tests to confirm the presence of certain types of microorganisms (Cai et al., 2007; Wang and Duncan, 2017; Vidic et al., 2019).

Figure 2. Classic microbiological method for pathogen detection. Image created with BioRender.com

Although still commonly employed as a fundamental method for pathogen detection, the microbiological cultivation technique based on nutrient media is known for the considerable time investment and resource requirements, which may pose practical limitations in certain contexts. Namely, the average duration of the analysis is estimated to be 3–4 days (Figure 2), but it can even last longer. Further, to conduct this type of analysis, several essential components are required, including a nutrient medium, a series of selective cultivation media

with defined compositions, precise oxygen concentrations, and suitable incubation temperatures, which may vary depending on the bacterial species under examination. Once all the cultivation conditions have been met, the process proceeds to isolate and identify microorganisms to ascertain the number of bacterial cells in the sample. In cases where bacteria are present in low numbers, confirming the presence of the pathogen in the sample may take up to seven days (Vidic et al., 2019; Nehra et al., 2022).

The deficiency of classical microbiological methods is also evident in their incapacity to detect the presence of bacteria known as "viable but non-culturable" (VBNC). These bacteria do not form visible colonies, rendering classical microbiological cultivation methods inadequate for their detection (Gao et al., 2021). Examples of such pathogens include *Klebsiella aerogenes* (which is in the focus of this doctoral dissertation), *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Chlamydia* spp., *Gardnerella vaginalis*, and various other bacterial species that exhibit similar characteristics (Oliver, 2010; Gao et al., 2021). Since VBNC bacteria are pathogens found in food and the environment, detecting their presence is crucial.

1.2.2 Molecular methods in microbiological diagnostics

The emergence of molecular diagnostic techniques, especially polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods, has revolutionized the detection of microorganisms, facilitated swifter and more accurate identification while upholding stringent specificity standards. Molecular diagnostic methods operate on targeted detection of genetic material, specifically DNA or RNA i.e. nucleic acids (NAs), allowing for both qualitative and quantitative analyses. Utilizing molecular techniques for pathogen detection typically involves four basic steps (Figure 3): 1) sample preparation, which includes homogenizing of the sample; 2) using an enrichment broth to increase the number of desired organisms to detectable levels; 3) NA extraction; and 4) targeted amplification of specific segment/region of NA using PCR or similar methodologies (Moreno et al., 2018).

PATHOGEN DETECTION USING MOLECULAR METHODS

Figure 3. Molecular methods for pathogen detection. Image created with BioRender.com

1.2.2.1 PCR methods

Currently, the most commonly used molecular methods for pathogen detection are PCR-based methods. These methods overcome the limitations encountered when using classical microbiological detection methods, as they provide a large number of copies of a certain segment of DNA in a short period of time from a small amount of initial DNA, enabling a high rate of specificity and sensitivity (Law et al., 2015; Nehra et al., 2022). These characteristics enable their application for early diagnostics, i.e., detection of pathogens in the sample shortly after infection, when concentration of bacterial cells is low, and well before the onset of the disease itself. Additionally, the PCR methods are well-suited for detecting infectious diseases

by identifying microbes that cannot be cultivated (VBNC pathogens) or those that require a long growth time (Law et al., 2015).

In standard PCR, product quantification can be done at the end of the PCR reaction (Endpoint PCR) and requires the analysis of results by visualization through electrophoresis, constituting an additional step in the process. On the other hand, Real Time PCR, an enhanced version of the Endpoint PCR method, allows the indirect, real time monitoring of the increase in the amount of amplified genetic material. This is achieved through the measurement of fluorescence levels of the implemented fluorescent dyes/reporters, enabling quantitative analysis of the genetic material present in the sample (Kralik and Ricchi, 2017).

Similar to many molecular methods, PCR methods possess inherent limitations. Specifically, while this type of analysis takes much less time compared to microbiological methods for pathogen detection, each step can be time-consuming (as described in Figure 3), with the estimated total analysis time being up to 1–2 days. Additionally, a constraint is their dependence on precise instruments and sterile working conditions, rendering their utilization impractical on the field. Moreover, PCR methods are very sensitive to reaction inhibitors, which are frequently found in complex samples like food matrices, soil, and heavily polluted water. In addition, PCR can give false-positive or false-negative results due to use of nonspecific primers or due to the lack of differentiation between NAs of the living (active) and dead (inactive) cells (Cangelosi and Meschke, 2014).

1.3 LAMP methodology

Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) represents a rapid and user-friendly technique for NA amplification, developed in 2000 by a group of Japanese scientists (Notomi et al., 2000). This method stands out as the currently most studied among isothermal amplification techniques and exhibits a remarkably broad range of applications such as for point-of-care (POC) testing for diseases, environmental monitoring, and food safety. The widespread application of the LAMP method today is also reflected in the availability of commercially available LAMP diagnostic kits for various diseases, such as SARS-CoV-2, malaria, tuberculosis, pneumonia, and others (WHO, 2013; Cuadros et al., 2017; Iqbal et al., 2022; Martín-Ramírez et al., 2022; Node et al., 2024).

Its user-friendliness, sensitivity, high specificity and tolerance to inhibitors sets it apart from other isothermal amplification methods (Becherer et al., 2020). Resistance to inhibitors is

especially important when working with complex samples, such as clinical samples, food, water, and soil. Additionally, in the case of LAMP, simple methods of sample preparation can be utilized, facilitating the performance of this assay directly at the point of need (PoN), which further reduces the costs of analysis compared to classic PCR methods (Moehling et al., 2021). In particular, it is well established that the cost of LAMP is typically 2 to 3 times lower than that of PCR. This cost advantage is further enhanced in cases involving simple matrices, where nucleic acid extraction is either unnecessary or can be performed using straightforward protocols that involve only mechanical homogenization with a lysis buffer (Quoc et al., 2018; Panno et al., 2020; Iqbal et al., 2022). In addition to DNA amplification, LAMP, when combined with the reverse transcription reaction, can amplify RNA sequences (Li et al., 2022).

The adaptability of LAMP allows for real time monitoring of reactions directly within the reaction vessel, eliminating the need for subsequent analyses and thereby significantly mitigating the risk of sample contamination. The ability to monitor reactions in real time is facilitated using affordable handheld devices, making it exceptionally convenient for in-field testing, which contributes to the popularity of this method in the realm of PoN diagnostics (Džisalov et al., 2021).

Contrary to the PCR reaction which requires cyclic changes in temperature during amplification facilitated by thermal cycler, the LAMP reaction occurs at a constant temperature (isothermal conditions). This process involves the use of four (up to six) different primers that bind to six (up to eight) different regions within the target gene (Figure 4). Such design ensures a high specificity of the reaction under isothermal conditions. The achievement of isothermal conditions is made possible by employing *Bst* DNA polymerase isolated from *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* (formerly known as *Bacillus stearothermophilus*). This polymerase exhibits high strand displacement activity as well as 5'–3' polymerase activity, while lacking 3'–5' exonuclease activity (Soroka et al., 2021).

1.3.1 LAMP primers

As previously mentioned, to conduct LAMP reaction it is necessary to use a set of four (up to six) specific primers complementary to six (up to eight) different regions of the target gene (Figure 4).

Basically, the LAMP primers consist of:

- Two outer primers

- forward outer primer (F3);
- backward outer primer (B3).
- Two inner primers
 - forward inner primer (FIP);
 - backward inner primer (BIP).

The F3 primer is composed of an oligonucleotide sequence that is complementary to the F3c region of the target gene, whereas the B3 primer consists of an oligonucleotide sequence that is complementary to the B3c region of the target gene.

Each inner primer of LAMP comprises two regions: F2 and F1c of FIP, and B2 and B1c of BIP. In this arrangement, F2 and B2 are complementary to F2c or B2c regions on the template sequence, respectively, while F1c and B1c share identical sequences with the regions F1c and B1c on template, and are complementary to sequences F1 and B1, respectively (Notomi et al., 2000; Djisalov et al., 2021).

Two additional primers can be also included in the reaction, although they are not essential for the LAMP process:

- Two loop primers
 - loop forward (LF);
 - loop backward (LB).

The loop primers LF and LB are specifically designed to be complementary to the loop region of a dumbbell-like structure (see below) situated between F1 and F2 and B1 and B2, respectively. They are frequently utilized to enhance the speed of the LAMP reaction.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of LAMP primers (Djisalov et al., 2021).

1.3.1.1 LAMP primer design

Designing LAMP primers is a complex process considering both the number of primers and the number of regions in the target sequence to which the primers bind. To ensure a successful reaction, it is necessary to meet several conditions when initiating LAMP primers design, described in following.

1. Appropriate melting temperatures (T_m):
 - a. $\sim 65\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($64\text{--}66\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for F1c and B1c regions (of FIP and BIP primers);
 - b. $\sim 60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($59\text{--}61\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for F2, B2 regions (of FIP and BIP primers) and F3 and B3 primers;
 - c. $\sim 65\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($64\text{--}66\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for loop primers (LF and LB).
2. The ends of the primers should exhibit a specific degree of stability. This is important as a reduction in the Gibbs free energy $-\Delta G$ (less than -4 kcal/mol) for the 3' ends of the primers enhances their binding rate to the target sequence.
3. The content of GC base pairs should be around 50–60%.
4. Designed primers, especially internal ones, should not form any secondary structures, such as primer dimers or hairpins, which can be prevented by designing them without complementary 3' ends and avoiding excessively high GC base pair content.
5. The distance between the end of the F2 and the B2 regions of FIP and BIP primers (the sequence that will be amplified) should be approximately 120–180 base pairs (bp). Additionally, the distance between the 5' end of the F2 and the 5' end of the F1 (the part that forms the loop) should be in the range of 40–60 bp. Meanwhile, the distances

between the binding sites of the F2 region of the FIP primer and the F3 primer, as well as between the binding sites of the B2 region of the BIP primer and the B3 primer, should be within 0–20 bp (Eiken Chemical Co. Ltd., 2005).

1.3.2 LAMP reaction mechanism

The LAMP reaction requires the following conditions:

1. a thermostable DNA polymerase with strand displacement activity (*Bst* DNA polymerase);
2. free deoxyribonucleoside triphosphates, i.e., nucleotides (dNTPs);
3. a specific set of primers;
4. target DNA sequence to be amplified;
5. a constant reaction temperature within the range of 60–65°C for 30–60 minutes.

The mechanism of the LAMP reaction involves three main steps:

1. Initial amplification;
2. Cyclic amplification;
3. Elongation and recycling.

Unlike PCR, LAMP employs a DNA polymerase with high strand displacement activity. This characteristic allows the polymerase to synthesize, displace, and release single-stranded DNA during the amplification process (Notomi et al., 2000; Park, 2022). The first step involves the use of two inner primers (FIP and BIP) and two outer primers (F3 and B3) to form a stem-loop structure, i.e. dumbbell-like structure (Figure 5).

The LAMP reaction initiates with the binding of the F2 region of the FIP primer to the 3' complementary region of the DNA template stand (F2c), leading to the subsequent release of the template strand and the synthesis of a new strand facilitated by the presence of *Bst* DNA polymerase (Figure 5.1).

In the next step, the F3 primer binds to the F3c location on the template, upstream of the target region, inducing strand displacement DNA synthesis and the release of FIP-linked complementary single-stranded DNA (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5. Mechanism of LAMP reaction: schematic representation of the generation of primary LAMP products (dumbbell-like structure) (Djusalov et al., 2021).

The released single strand forms a stem-loop structure at the 5' end, driven by the complementarity between F1c and F1 regions (Figure 5.3 and 5.4).

The released single-stranded DNA (ssDNA), serving as a template for BIP and B3, respectively, contributes to the synthesis of a new strand (Figure 5.4). This new strand contains self-complementarity regions between B1c and B1, forming a stem-loop structure, i.e. dumbbell-like structure. The formed dumbbell structure (Figure 5.5) serves as the starting material for the subsequent amplification of the target DNA molecule (LAMP cycling).

This structure contains numerous LAMP replication initiation regions at the 3' ends of the loops, along with regions for binding internal primers, FIP and BIP. The F2 region of FIP

primer (Figure 6.5) and the B2 region of BIP primer (Figure 6.7) anneal to the ssDNA regions within the stem loop structures, facilitating the synthesis of new strands while simultaneously releasing the previously synthesized strands (Figures 6.6. and 6.8). At the 3' ends, the single strands that have been freed from stem loop structures and extend new strands through self-priming activity (Figures 6.9 and 6.10). This enables the creation of concatemeric structures with an increasing number of synthesis initiation regions (Figures 6.11 and 6.12). When used in the reaction, the loop primers (LF and LB), featuring sequences complementary to the single loop (between F1c and F2c regions, and the B1 and B2 regions, respectively), contribute to wider range of starting points for the synthesis of a new DNA strand through the LAMP method (Deng and Gao, 2015; Džisalov et al., 2021).

As a result of this process, diverse structures with varying sizes, composed of alternately inverted repeats of the target sequence, are formed. The combination of the non-requirement of a denaturation step and the self-priming activity at the 3'-end of the dumbbell structure leads to the generation of a substantial quantity of LAMP-amplified products, reaching up to 10^9 copies of the target within an hour (Notomi et al., 2000).

Figure 6. Further mechanism of the LAMP reaction: formation of secondary structures of various sizes (Djialov et al., 2021).

1.3.3 Detection of LAMP products

The LAMP reaction results in rapid accumulation of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) products (LAMP amplicons) and a substantial amount of detectable by-products (such as magnesium pyrophosphate, pyrophosphate ions, hydrogen ions), which can be identified using various endpoint or real time detection technologies (Mori et al., 2001; Zhang et al., 2014; Becherer et al., 2020).

Furthermore, LAMP stands out for its isothermal and energy-efficient amplification requirements, making it an ideal choice for affordable diagnostics and in-field analysis. Over the last decade, various sequence-specific methods for detection of LAMP amplicons have emerged, employing a diverse array of sensing techniques, including optical, magnetic, piezoelectric, electrochemical and magnetoresistive sensing (Becherer et al., 2020).

This doctoral dissertation will focus on the description of the most commonly used detection approaches i.e. visual detection, turbidity, and real time detection using DNA intercalating dyes for real time fluorescence (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Overview of the most commonly used approaches for detection of LAMP products.

1.3.3.1 Visual detection of LAMP products

To visually detect LAMP products, common choices include metal indicators, DNA intercalary dyes, or pH sensitive indicators. In all three cases, distinguishing a positive from a negative LAMP reaction is based on observing a color in visible spectrum where change of the color in the reaction mixture means positive reactions, while the unchanged color means negative reactions. This straightforward and cost-effective method of visual detection is the simplest way to identify LAMP products.

Endpoint detection with metal indicators

When using metal indicators for visual detection, change in the color in a positive LAMP reaction is directly influenced by the type of metal indicators employed, commonly including calcein, hydroxy naphthol blue, and malachite green.

Calcein is a metal indicator dye that combines with manganese ions (Mn^{2+}) from $MnCl_2$ before amplification, causing the reaction solution to turn orange (Figure 8A, left) (Xie et al., 2014). Subsequently, during the amplification process, pyrophosphate ions (PPi^-) are released, which can displace the Mn^{2+} from calcein, leading to the emission of fluorescence from calcein, causing the assay turns to light green under natural light (Figure 8A-right) (Pang et al., 2019). Manganese ions form an insoluble salt with the pyrophosphates generated during reaction, while the free calcein interact with magnesium ions (Mg^{2+}) from the reaction mixture, resulting in stronger fluorescence emission (Tomita et al., 2008).

On the other hand, hydroxy naphthol blue and malachite green operate on the same principle for indicating a positive LAMP reaction. In both cases, the color change is triggered by a decrease in Mg^{2+} ions during the LAMP process. This change causes hydroxy naphthol blue to shift from purple to blue (Figure 8B) (Goto et al., 2009) and malachite green to transition from colorless to blue (Figure 8C) (Lucchi et al., 2016).

However, employing metal indicators has several disadvantages. One of them is certainly the difficulty of analyzing the color change. Furthermore, it has been observed that adding indicators to the reaction mixture can adversely affect the efficiency of the LAMP reaction, thereby reducing the sensitivity of the reaction to 100–1000 copies of the target (Tanner et al., 2015).

Figure 8. Monitoring LAMP reaction by visual detection using metal indicators: calcein (A), hydroxy naphthol blue (B) and malachite green (C) (Adapted in accordance with: Britton et al. (2015), Li et al. (2017) and Tavakoli-Koopaei et al. (2023)).

Endpoint detection with DNA intercalary dyes

Another approach for the visual detection of LAMP products involves the application of intercalating DNA dyes, which bind to dsDNA, and trigger higher fluorescence. After amplification, the amount of double-stranded LAMP products is increased, and therefore more intercalating dyes can bind to DNA and emit their fluorescence (van der Velden et al., 2001; Gard, 2002; Dragan et al., 2010). In contrast to metal indicators, these dyes are added to the solution after the completion of the reaction. In a positive reaction, a color change is observed under ambient light, transitioning from orange to green (SYBR Green I, PicoGreen) (Figures 9A and 9B) or orange to light pink (Propidium Iodide) (Figure 9C) (Parida et al., 2006; Hill et al., 2008; El-Kholy et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2014).

Using DNA dyes for colorimetric detection is as simple as metal indicators, without the need for optical detection integration. Furthermore, distinguishing between negative and positive reactions is more evident, compared to using metal indicators (Figure 9). The sensitivity of color change detection using DNA dyes is comparable to real time LAMP detection and gel electrophoresis (Quyen et al., 2019b). However, adding the intercalating dye after completing the reaction increases the risk of contamination (Goto et al., 2009).

Figure 9. Monitoring LAMP reaction by visual detection using DNA intercalary dyes: SYBR Green I (A), PicoGreen (B) and Propidium Iodide (C) (Adapted in accordance with: Parida et al. (2006), Hill et al. (2008) and El-Kholy et al. (2014).

Endpoint detection with pH-sensitive indicators

Visualizing the LAMP products using pH-sensitive dyes has also been reported as a visual detection method with best visibility compared to the use of metal indicators and DNA dyes (Tanner et al., 2015). By using highly sensitive-pH indicators, the positive reactions could be identified by a change of color in positive LAMP reactions. As mentioned earlier, the outcome of the DNA polymerization reaction (i.e., LAMP reaction) is generation of not only amplified products or by-products (pyrophosphate ions) (Reaction 1 first line), but also hydrogen ions, which are formed as a result of pyrophosphate hydrolysis (Reaction 1 second line), thereby reducing the pH of the LAMP reaction mixture.

Reaction 1. DNA polymerization reaction (Mori et al., 2001).

For instance, the color changes from red to yellow when using phenol red or cresol red, from light yellow to red when using the neutral red pH-sensitive indicator, or from purple to yellow when using the cresol purple pH-sensitive indicator (Figure 10) (Tanner et al., 2015; Poole et al., 2017).

Figure 10. Monitoring LAMP reaction by visual detection using pH-sensitive indicators: phenol red (A), cresol red (B) and neutral red (C) (Adapted in accordance with: Schellenberg et al. (2020) and Martínez and Federici (2022)).

1.3.3.2 Turbidity detection of LAMP products (Real Time and Endpoint)

Turbidimetric detection of LAMP products is based on the fact that the by-product generated during NA synthesis, the pyrophosphate, combines with magnesium ions to form white crystals of magnesium pyrophosphate (Reaction 2.).

Briefly, DNA polymerase catalyzes the synthesis of DNA during DNA polymerization, utilizing deoxyribonucleotide triphosphates (dNTPs) and releasing pyrophosphate ions as by-products (Reaction 1 first line). The reaction leads to production of significant amount of pyrophosphate ions, which, in turn, react with magnesium ions to form white precipitates ($Mg_2P_2O_7$) (Reaction 1 second line) (Mori et al., 2001).

Reaction 2. Magnesium pyrophosphate formation during the LAMP reaction (Mori et al., 2001).

This approach yields a higher amount of magnesium pyrophosphate compared to conventional PCR, and it can be continuously monitored in real time using a turbidimeter or directly by the naked eye after the completion of the amplification reaction (Figure 11) (Mori et al., 2004, 2013a).

Figure 11. Monitoring LAMP reaction (A) in real time by a turbidimeter or (B) at the endpoint by naked eye (Adapted in accordance with: Arunrut et al. (2014) and Ghasemian et al. (2014)).

Turbidity detection offers cost advantages by eliminating the need for probes or special reagents, making the reaction more economical. Integrating optical detection into instruments based on turbidity is also simpler and more cost-effective than fluorescence detection, which demands filters for both excitation and emission lights. However, turbidity detection faces limitations – a failure to differentiate specific from non-specific amplification (Mori et al., 2001), and its reported sensitivity is 10 times lower than fluorescence-based detection (Chen and Ge, 2010). Moreover, the presence of MgSO_4 (which is used in this detection approach) is crucial for the full effectiveness of *Bst* Polymerase, which operates most efficiently at pH 8.5 in a buffer containing 4–20 mM MgSO_4 and 50–350 mM salt (NaCl or KCl) at 65 °C (Notomi et al., 2000; Fischbach et al., 2015). MgSO_4 also serves as a source of Mg^{2+} ions, necessary for the generation of magnesium pyrophosphate.

1.3.3.3 DNA Intercalating Dyes for Real Time Fluorescence Detection of LAMP products

Similar to Real Time PCR, a straightforward method for monitoring the Real Time LAMP reaction involves the use of DNA intercalating dyes (Figure 12). This method entails adding the DNA dye to the reaction during the preparation of the master mixture. In a LAMP negative reaction, the DNA dye remains unbound and has low background, as there is an absence of amplified product (dsDNA). Conversely, in a LAMP positive reaction, the DNA intercalating dye intercalates with dsDNA and exhibits higher fluorescence (see Figure 12 B).

Figure 12. Monitoring LAMP reaction by real time fluorescence using DNA intercalating dyes: A) Real Time LAMP fluorescence detection and B) the mechanism of fluorescence emission during application of a DNA intercalating dye.

Investigating the inhibition effect and fluorescence intensity of dyes in the LAMP reaction is crucial for selecting an optimal dye for real time monitoring of LAMP amplification, particularly in small, affordable, and portable PoN systems for which it is necessary to use compact and cost-effective optical components. As in turbidity detection, this method fails to differentiate between specific and non-specific amplification, as the DNA dye can bind to any double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) in the mixture (Cao et al., 2015). While SYBR Green I, a commonly used DNA intercalating dye for monitoring PCR reactions, can be applied to LAMP, it is noteworthy to mention that this dye exerts a strong inhibitory effect on the LAMP reaction when present at concentrations of 1–5 μM or when 0.5 mM Mn^{2+} is added to the pre-reaction solution (Cao et al., 2015).

Extensive investigations have been conducted on commonly available DNA intercalating dyes, spanning various groups like SYTO, SYBR Green I, EvaGreen, Miami, etc., each with distinct optical properties. These studies, encompassing four groups of dyes, thoroughly explored the inhibitory effect and fluorescence intensity in LAMP reactions (Quyen et al., 2019a; Seyrig et al., 2015). The insights gained from these investigations play a pivotal role in selecting the most suitable dye for the development of PoN devices reliant on fluorescence detection using DNA intercalating dyes.

2. Hypothesis and aims

Contamination of food and water with pathogens poses a great challenge for food safety, contributing to elevated mortality rates, human and animal suffering, and substantial economic burdens. With the growing global population, it becomes imperative to take action to ensure an adequate and safe food and water supply for all. This goal can be attained by developing innovative diagnostic tools for rapid and efficient pathogen detection throughout the whole food value chain including field conditions.

According to all above, the dissertation concentrates on the advanced development and application of the isothermal loop-mediated amplification (LAMP) method, which allows for fast, simple, and reliable field detection. The hypotheses of this dissertation are:

- 1)) LAMP-based detection is appropriate for pathogen detection in water and food of animal and plant origin and in the environment, which corresponds to the “One health” paradigm, recommended by the FAO and
- 2) LAMP is superior to the most commonly used methods for pathogen detection such as cultivation methods and the PCR method.

In order to evaluate the above stated hypothesis, the primary objectives (**O**) of this doctoral dissertation are defined as follows:

O1: Contribution to the development of LAMP method for research and practical purposes i.e. for application in the field, to detect pathogens in different complex matrices comprising food (meat and vegetable), river water, and soil-like matrix, as well as a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of this method compared to conventional methods based on pathogen cultivation and the PCR method as the “gold standard” for NA amplification procedure;

- **O1.1** Development of a concise and clear protocol for LAMP detection of bacterial pathogens in various food matrices using pathogenic *Klebsiella aerogenes* bacterium as a model system; The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers;
- **O1.2** developing LAMP protocol for early detection of pathogenic fungi *Trichoderma* spp. in soil-like matrix (compost and casing soil used for mushroom-growing). The protocol development includes *de novo* design of the specific primers. Defining the final protocol includes implementation of colorimetric detection of the LAMP products using gold nanoparticles, thereby increasing the technology readiness level (TRL) for real-life application of the developed protocol;

O2 focuses on evaluation of the potential application of the LAMP method in detecting fecal indicator bacteria (FIB), such as *E. coli*, for river water quality assessment;

O3 deals with enhancing extraction protocols for rapid DNA isolation, concretely:

- **O3.1.1** from the foodstuffs and **O3.1.2** from soil-like real-life samples (Chelex 100 method) and
- **O3.2** from highly contaminated river water samples (a syringe-based DNA isolation method);

O4 aims to provide final conclusions on the applicability of developed LAMP protocols for use in early detection of pathogens of bacterial and fungal origin, in the field conditions.

Research concept toward achieving primary objectives of this dissertation is summarized in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Schematic representation of the research concept conducted in doctoral dissertation. TRL – technology readiness level; FIB – fecal indicator bacteria.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Development of a LAMP-based assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in food matrices

To develop a LAMP-based assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in food matrices, the following experimental setup, as presented in Figure 14, was performed.

Figure 14. Experimental outline for optimization of LAMP based *Klebisella aerogenes* detection in food matrices. Image created with BioRender.com.

3.1.1 Biological material

3.1.1.1 Bacterial cultures

All bacterial cultures used in this part of doctoral dissertation were prepared by cultivation on Tryptone Soya Agar medium (TSA) (Millipore, USA) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours (overnight).

Used bacterial cultures included following Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial species:

Gram-positive bacterial species:

- *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Alcaligenes faecalis*.

Gram-negative bacterial species:

- *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli*.

All bacterial species used in this dissertation originate from the BioSense Culture Collection of Bacteria (BSCCB), which can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/11385670>.

3.1.1.2 Vegetable material

Soil can be a source of contamination by *Klebsiella* spp., as this bacterium is commonly found in the soil. It can contaminate vegetables, especially those that are in direct contact with the soil. Accordingly, cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) and lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.), whose edible parts are in direct contact with the soil, and carrots (*Daucus carota* L.), whose edible roots grow within it, these vegetables were specifically selected for all planned analyses (Gundogan, 2014; Tan and Karwe, 2021). This choice allows for a broader exploration within this experimental framework. All vegetables were purchased from local store in Novi Sad on March 10, 2023.

For each vegetable two different DNA extraction methods were applied. DNA extraction was done from different plant parts using 125 mg of plant tissue as starting material (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Vegetable material used in this doctoral dissertation. A) lettuce; B) cucumber; C) carrot; D) vegetable samples in Petri dishes. Image created with BioRender.com.

To ascertain the potential presence of the pathogen *K. aerogenes* in the plant cultures (vegetables) used for subsequent research, the following steps were employed:

- A piece of vegetable (carrot, cucumber, lettuce) was washed with 3 mL of PCR water each and 1 mL of water was subsequently transferred to a TSA plate per sample type, followed by an incubation at 37 °C for 24 hours.
- Bacterial cultures that had grown were then sampled from the plates and prepared for 1) DNA isolation using The GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Thermo Scientific™, USA); and 2) sub-cultivation of individual colonies on TSA in order to obtain clean colonies that will be subjected to biochemical tests for microbial identification.
- DNA isolation was performed by following the isolation procedure for the isolation of Gram-negative bacteria, considering that *K. aerogenes* is a Gram-negative bacterium. The isolation protocol is described in *Section 3.1.2.1*.

- After isolation, the Real Time LAMP analysis was performed in order to confirm the presence of *K. aerogenes* in the grown cultures. The detection of *K. aerogenes* was performed using the primer candidate 2 (PC2) primer set (for details see *Section 4.1.2*).

3.1.1.3 Meat and meat products

As the literature attests, poultry meat is one of the most frequently contaminated with *Klebsiella* spp. Consequently, the meat material utilized in all planned analyses was sourced from: fresh chicken breasts and from chicken salami from local meat producer (Figure 16). Both type of meat products were purchased at local store in Novi Sad on July 18, 2023.

DNA extraction from 250 mg of meat products was done using two different extraction methods.

Figure 16. Meat and meat product samples used in this doctoral dissertation. A) chicken breasts; B) salami; C) meat samples in Petri dishes. Image created with BioRender.com.

To confirm the potential presence of *K. aerogenes* in the chicken breasts and salami the following experiment was conducted:

- 250 mg of each meat samples (chicken breasts and salami) was incubated in 2 mL Tryptone Soya Broth (TSB) (Oxoid, UK) at 37 °C for 24 hours in thermostat incubator (Incubator IN55, Memmert, Germany).

- These samples were then used for the DNA extraction using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (Qiagen, Germany) and the Chelex 100 method, as described in *Section 3.1.2.3*.
- Extracted gDNA was used for the Real Time LAMP. The detection of *K. aerogenes* was performed using the PC2 primer set (for details see *Section 4.1.2*).
- The confirmation of the presence of *K. aerogenes* in meat samples through biochemical tests was conducted in the same manner as outlined for vegetable material in *Section 3.1.1.2*.

3.1.2 DNA extraction

DNA Extraction was performed using either the Chelex 100 method, suitable for in-field application, or commercially available spin-column-based kits for the isolation from bacteria, vegetable, and meat materials.

3.1.2.1 DNA extraction from bacterial cultures

The GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Thermo Scientific™, USA) was used for the isolation of gDNA from pure bacterial cultures (gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria). Isolation protocols are described below.

A) DNA isolation from gram-positive bacteria

Materials:

- GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Thermo Scientific™, USA) which includes:
 - Proteinase K Solution;
 - RNase A Solution;
 - Digestion Solution;
 - Lysis Solution;
 - Wash Buffer I;
 - Wash Buffer II;
 - Elution Buffer (10 mM Tris-Cl, pH 9.0, 0.1 mM EDTA);
 - GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification Columns pre-assembled with Collection Tubes;
 - Collection Tubes;
- Gram-positive Bacteria Lysis Buffer (20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 2 mM EDTA, 1.2% Triton X-100, with added lysozyme to 20 mg/mL);

- Overnight bacterial culture on TSA;
- Test tubes containing 5 mL of 0.9% sterile saline solution;
- 50% ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Sterile 2 mL tubes.

Procedure:

1. Overnight bacterial cultures were scraped from TSA and transferred into a tube containing 5 mL of 0.9% sterile saline solution;
2. The bacterial suspension was adjusted to 1.5×10^9 CFU/mL (5 McF) using a DEN-1 densitometer (BioSan, Latvia);
3. 2 mL of the prepared bacterial suspension was then transferred into a new sterile 2 mL tube and centrifuged for 10 min at 5000g;
4. Supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was resuspended in 180 μ L of Gram-positive Bacteria Lysis Buffer and incubated for 30 min at 37 °C in thermostat incubator (Incubator IN55, Memmert, Germany);
5. 200 μ L of Lysis Solution and 20 μ L of Proteinase K were added. The tube was thoroughly mixed by vortexing and pipetting to achieve a uniform suspension;
6. The sample was incubated at 56 °C for 30 min with occasional vortexing;
7. 20 μ L of RNase A Solution was added, and the content of the tube was mixed by vortexing. Afterwards, the tube was left for incubation for 10 min at room temperature;
8. 400 μ L of 50% ethanol was added and mixed by vortexing;
9. The lysate was transferred to a GeneJET purification column placed on the collection tube. The column was centrifuged for 1 minute at 6000g. The collection tube with the contents (flow-through solution) was then discarded, and the GeneJET purification column was placed in the new 2 mL collection tube;
10. 500 μ L of Wash Buffer I (with added ethanol) was added to the GeneJET column and centrifuged for 1 minute at 8000g. The flow-through contents were discarded, and the GeneJET column was then returned to the collection tube;
11. 500 μ L of Wash Buffer II (with added ethanol) was added to the GeneJET column and centrifuged for 3 min at maximum speed (18000g);

12. 200 μL of Elution Buffer was added to the center of the membrane on the GeneJET purification column to precipitate the gDNA. The tube was finally incubated for 2 min at room temperature and centrifuged for 1 minute at 8000g.
13. gDNA was stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further manipulation.

B) DNA isolation from Gram-negative bacteria

Materials:

- GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Thermo Scientific™, USA);
- Overnight bacterial culture on TSA;
- Test tubes containing 5 mL 0.9% sterile saline solution;
- 50% ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Sterile 2 mL tubes.

Procedure:

1. Overnight bacterial cultures were scraped from TSA and transferred into a tube containing 5 mL of 0.9% sterile saline solution;
2. The bacterial suspension was set to 1.5×10^9 CFU/mL (5 McF) using a DEN-1 densitometer (BioSan, Latvia);
3. 2 mL of the prepared bacterial suspension was then transferred into a new sterile 2 mL tube and centrifuged for 10 min at 5000g;
4. Supernatant was discarded and the bacterial pellet was resuspended in 180 μL of the Digestion solution. Subsequently, 20 μL of Proteinase K was added and vortexed thoroughly;
5. The sample was incubated for 30 min at $56\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at TS-100C Thermo-Skaker (BioSan, Latvia) and occasionally vortexed;
6. 20 μL of RNase A solution was added to the sample, vortexed thoroughly, followed by incubation for 10 min at room temperature;
7. After incubation, 200 μL of Lysis solution was added to the sample, and the content of the tube was vortexed for 15 seconds until a homogeneous mixture was created;
8. 400 μL of 50% ethanol was added to the sample, and the contents of the tube were vortexed;
9. The lysate was transferred to a GeneJET purification column placed on a collection tube. The column was centrifuged for 1 minute at 6000g. Subsequently, the

- collection tube with the flow-through solution was discarded, and the GeneJET purification column was transferred to the new 2 mL collection tube;
10. 500 μ L of Wash Buffer I was added to the column, and the tube was centrifuged for 1 minute at 8000g. The filtrate was then discarded, and the GeneJET column was returned to the collection tube;
 11. Next, 500 μ L of Wash Buffer II was added to the GeneJET column, and the tube with the column was centrifuged for 3 min (18000g);
 12. After centrifugation, 200 μ L of Elution Buffer was added to the center of the membrane on the GeneJET purification column to elute the genomic DNA (gDNA). The tube was then incubated for 2 min at room temperature and centrifuged for 1 minute at 8000g.
 13. gDNA was stored at -20 °C until further manipulation.

3.1.2.2 DNA extraction from vegetable material

To extract DNA from vegetable material, two methods were employed: 1) the Chelex 100 method (suitable for in-field applications) (Gautam, 2022) and 2) the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit (Norgen Biotek, Canada). To enhance DNA extraction efficiency and its usability in the field, the standard Chelex 100 method was modified by introducing an alkaline-PEG buffer into the preparation process, using the recipe described in Tomlinson and Boonham (2015).

For both methods, 125 mg of each plant sample was used as starting material.

A) Chelex 100 - DNA extraction method applicable in the field

Materials:

- PEG lysis buffer: 60% of polyethylene glycol 200 (PEG 200) (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC, Germany), 20 mM NaOH (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), pH 13.3–13.5;
- 0.4 g of Chelex[®] 100 sodium form (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC, Germany);
- Tris-EDTA buffer (TE buffer), pH 7.4 (Supelco, USA);
- Sterile 5 mL tubes;
- 10 mm sterile metal balls;
- Vegetable material (125 mg).

Procedure (Figure 17):

1. 900 μL of PEG lysis buffer and 0.4 g of Chelex® 100 were added to an isolation tube (5 mL) containing a metal ball for homogenization;
2. 125 mg of vegetable material was added to the tube;
3. The content of the tube was strongly mixed by twisting it up and down for 1 minute;
4. The tube was incubated for 20 min at room temperature to allow the Chelex® 100 to settle;
5. The supernatant containing the gDNA was transferred into a new sterile tube by pipetting;
6. The resulting extract was diluted 50 times by adding 980 μL of TE buffer to 20 μL of extract to achieve final volume of 1 mL.

Figure 17. Chelex 100 extraction procedure: sequential steps. A) sterile 5 mL tube containing 10 mm sterile metal ball; B) tube after adding Chelex® 100, PEG lysis buffer and plant material (before mixing); C) tube content after mixing (plant DNA extract).

B) DNA extraction by using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation KitMaterials:

- Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit (Norgen Biotek, Canada) which includes:
 - Lysis Buffer L;
 - Binding Buffer I;
 - Solution WN;
 - Wash Solution A;
 - Elution Buffer B;

- RNase A;
- Filter Columns;
- Spin Columns;
- Collection Tubes;
- Elution tubes (1.7 mL);
- Sterile glass beads (1.25-1.65 mm);
- Sterile 2 mL tubes;
- Ice;
- 70% ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Vegetable material (125 mg)

Procedure:

1. 0.8 g of sterile glass beads for mechanical homogenization were weighed and transferred into a sterile 2 mL tube;
2. 125 mg of vegetable material (cucumber, carrot, and lettuce) was added to the tube with the beads;
3. 500 μ L of Lysis Buffer L was added and the mixture was vortexed for 7 min at maximum speed;
4. After homogenization, 1 μ L of RNase A was immediately added to the lysate and vortexed for about 20 seconds;
5. The tube was incubated on a TS-100C Thermo-Shaker (BioSan, Latvia) at 65 °C for 10 min. During the incubation period, the sample was occasionally mixed by inverting the tube.
6. Following that, 100 μ L of Binding Buffer I was gently added to the lysate, thoroughly mixed by vortexing, and then the tube was incubated for 5 min on ice;
7. Afterward, the filter column was carefully placed in a collection tube and the lysate was pipetted into the filter column. The tube with the column was centrifuged for 2 min at 14000g;
8. Only the clear supernatant from the collection tube was transferred with a pipette to a clean DNase-free tube;
9. An equal volume of 70% ethanol was added to the lysate (lysate:ethanol ratio = 1:1), followed by vortexing;
10. The spin columns were then placed on collection tubes. Clear lysate with ethanol (650 μ L) was transferred to the spin column, followed by centrifugation for 1 minute at

- 10000g. The contents of the tube were discarded, and the step was repeated with the remaining lysate;
11. Next, 500 μ L of WN solution was added to the spin column, and then the tube with the column was centrifuged for 1 minute at 10000g. The flow-through was discarded;
 12. Next, 500 μ L of washing buffer, Wash Solution A was added to the spin column and the tube with the column was centrifuged for 1 minute 10000g. The flow-through was discarded; this step was repeated twice;
 13. The tube with the empty column was centrifuged for 2 min at 14000g in order to thoroughly dry the resin;
 14. The column was transferred to the elution tube;
 15. 100 μ L of Elution Buffer B was added to the spin column and the tube with the column was incubated for 1 minute at room temperature;
 16. Then, the tube with the column was centrifuged for 1 minute at 10000g to elute gDNA from the spin column membrane.
 17. gDNA was stored at -20 °C until further manipulation.

3.1.2.3 DNA extraction from meat and meat products

To extract DNA from meat samples, two methods were employed: the Chelex 100 method (suitable for in-field applications) and the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (Qiagen, Germany). For both methods, 250 mg of each sample was used as starting material.

A) Chelex 100 - DNA extraction method applicable in the field

The isolation procedure was done according to the methodology outlined in the *Section 3.1.2.2* under *A* with additional maceration step which is described in *Section 3.1.2.3* under *B* 1–3 procedure points.

B) DNA extraction by using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit

The protocol for "Isolating DNA Directly from Food Without Culturing" was employed, following the manufacturer's instructions with a few modifications. Additionally, to enhance extraction efficiency, the initial four steps involved sample maceration, as in the case of Chelex 100 method.

Materials:

- DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (Qiagen, Germany) which includes:
 - PowerBead Tubes, Garnet (0.5 ml);

- MB Spin Columns;
- Solution MBL;
- Solution IRS;
- Solution MR;
- Solution PW;
- Ethanol;
- Solution EB;
- Collection Tubes (2 ml);
- Sterile 1 x Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution;
- Sterile tube homogenizer;
- Sterile 2 mL tubes;
- Absolute ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Meat sample (250 mg)

Procedure:

1. The meat samples were placed in sterile 2 mL tubes and 750 μ L of 1x PBS was added;
2. The sample was macerated using a sterile tube homogenizer for approximately 2 min until a homogeneous mixture was achieved;
3. The tube was left for 10 min to allow larger pieces to fall to the bottom of the tube;
4. The homogenate was carefully transferred to a new sterile 2 mL tube, avoiding large meat pieces;
5. The tube was centrifuged for 3 min at 13000g, and the supernatant was carefully decanted without disturbing the precipitate;
6. The pellet was resuspended with 450 μ L of warm (55 °C) MBL Solution;
7. The homogenate was transferred into PowerBead tubes;
8. The tubes were vortexed horizontally at maximum speed for 10 min;
9. The tubes were centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g;
10. The supernatant was transferred into new 2 mL collection tubes;
11. 100 μ L of IRS Solution was added, vortexed, and the sample was incubated at 2–8 °C for 5 min;
12. The tubes were centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g;
13. The supernatant was transferred into new 2 mL tubes;
14. 900 μ L of warm (55 °C) MR Solution was added to the supernatant and vortexed;

15. 650 μL of the sample was transferred to the MB spin column and centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g. The flow-through was discarded and this step was repeated until all of the sample had passed through the column;
16. The MB spin column was placed into a new 2 mL tube;
17. 650 μL of PW Solution was added and the tube was centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g;
18. The flow-through was discarded and 650 μL of ethanol was added. The tube was then centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g;
19. The flow-through was discarded and the tube was centrifuged for 2 min at 13000g;
20. The MB spin column was transferred to a new 1.5 mL tube;
21. 100 μL of EB Solution was added and the tube was centrifuged for 1 minute at 13000g.
22. gDNA was stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further manipulation.

3.1.3 Targeted, controlled contamination of food material

3.1.3.1 Contamination of vegetable samples

Targeted, controlled contamination of vegetable samples was conducted using two approaches:

A) Spiking with *K. aerogenes* gDNA

Procedure:

Genomic DNA from *K. aerogenes* (concentration of 59.9 ng/ μL) was directly added to a tube containing a vegetable gDNA extract (carrot, lettuce, cucumber) with the aim of achieving a final concentration of 1 ng/ μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA in the spiked DNA sample. This spiked gDNA extract is subsequently used for the LAMP analyses.

B) Inoculation with *K. aerogenes* bacterial suspension

Procedure:

Initially, the *K. aerogenes* bacterial suspension was adjusted to a concentration of 1.5×10^9 CFU/mL (5 McF) using a DEN-1 densitometer (BioSan, Latvia). Inoculation was performed by adding 100 μL of above-mentioned *K. aerogenes* suspension directly to the tube containing 125 mg of vegetable material, aiming to achieve a final concentration of 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL of *K. aerogenes* in the spiked sample. Subsequently, these samples underwent DNA extraction, as detailed in *Section 3.1.2.2*.

3.1.3.2 Contamination of meat samples

Targeted, controlled contamination of meat samples was conducted using two approaches:

A) Spiking with *K. aerogenes* gDNA

Procedure:

Genomic DNA from *K. aerogenes* (concentration of 59.9 ng/ μ L) was directly added to a tube containing a meat DNA extract (fresh chicken breasts, chicken salami) with the aim of achieving a final concentration of 1 ng/ μ L for *K. aerogenes* gDNA in the spiked sample. This spiked meat DNA extract is subsequently used for LAMP analyses.

B) Inoculation with *K. aerogenes* bacterial suspension

Procedure:

Initially, the *K. aerogenes* bacterial suspension was adjusted to a concentration of 1.5×10^9 CFU/mL (5 McF) using a DEN-1 densitometer (BioSan, Latvia). Inoculation was carried out by adding 100 μ L of the above-mentioned *K. aerogenes* suspension directly to the tube containing 1650 μ L TSB and 250 mg of each meat sample. The tube containing the 8.57×10^6 CFU/mL *K. aerogenes* was incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Subsequently, only the meat samples from the solution with *K. aerogenes* underwent DNA extraction, as detailed in *Section 3.1.2.3*.

3.1.4 Concentration and purity of DNA

The concentration and the DNA purity were determined spectrophotometrically using a BioSpec-nano spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) by measuring the absorbance of 2 μ L DNA samples at 260, 280, and 230 nm.

The purity of total DNA was assessed using the A_{260}/A_{280} ratio, and the A_{260}/A_{230} ratio. The A_{260}/A_{280} ratio is expected to be between 1.7 and 1.9, and the A_{260}/A_{230} ratio between 2.0 and 2.2 for satisfactory purity (Wilfinger et al., 1997).

3.1.5 LAMP primer design for *K. aerogenes*

Since *K. aerogenes* is known to be a histamine-producing bacteria (HPB), this characteristic was utilized for primer design.

The target gene chosen for LAMP primer design was the histidine decarboxylase coding gene (*HDC*), an enzyme that catalyzes the decarboxylation of histidine into histamine (Zou et al., 2015), taken from the NCBI GenBank (Gene ID: 66602288).

Before designing LAMP primers, the same gene was analysed using the online software Nucleotide Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (Nucleotide BLAST; <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) to check if the chosen target gene (*HDC*) is highly conserved across other organisms.

After conducting a thorough analysis of parameters for primer design (previously described within *Section 1.3.1.1*), three sets of highly promising primer candidates (PCs) that specifically target the *HDC* gene of *K. aerogenes* were identified. LAMP primers were designed and analysed using online version of Primer Explorer V5 software (<http://primerexplorer.jp>). The positioning of the LAMP primers along the target sequence is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Positioning of LAMP primers within the target sequence: F3 – forward outer primer; B3 – backward outer primer; FIP – forward inner primer; BIP – backward inner primer; LF – loop forward primer; LB – loop backward primer.

3.1.6 LAMP assay

In this doctoral dissertation, two types of LAMP assay were performed: Real Time LAMP and Colorimetric LAMP.

WarmStart[®] LAMP Kit (DNA & RNA) (New England BioLabs, France) was used for the Real Time LAMP assay, while WarmStart[®] Colorimetric LAMP 2x Master Mix (DNA & RNA) kit (New England BioLabs, France) was used for Colorimetric LAMP assay.

All LAMP reactions were conducted at 65 °C according to the manufacturer's recommendation.

The calculation for LAMP primer mixture preparation is summarized in Table 1. The reaction components and volumes for the of Real Time LAMP reaction are provided in Table 2, while those for the Colorimetric LAMP reaction are presented in Table 3. Each reaction was carried out in a total volume of 25 µL.

In all the conducted reactions, *K. aerogenes* gDNA (with the concentration of 59.9 ng/µL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as the negative control (no template control, NTC).

Table 1. Summarized LAMP primer mix preparation.

LAMP primer	10x concentration (stock)	1x concentration (final)
FIP	16 μ M	1.6 μ M
BIP	16 μ M	1.6 μ M
F3	2 μ M	0.2 μ M
B3	2 μ M	0.2 μ M
Loop F	4 μ M	0.4 μ M
Loop B	4 μ M	0.4 μ M

Table 2. Components of Real Time LAMP Reaction mixture.

Component	Volume for one reaction [μ L]
WarmStart LAMP 2x Master Mix	12.5
LAMP Fluorescent Dye	0.5
Primer mix (10x concentration)	2.5
Sample (target DNA)	1.0
PCR H₂O	8.5
Total volume per reaction	Σ 25.0

Table 3. Components of Colorimetric LAMP Reaction mixture.

Component	Volume for one reaction [μ L]
WarmStart Colorimetric LAMP 2X Master Mix	12.5
Primer mix (10x concentration)	2.5
Sample (target DNA)	1.0
PCR H₂O	9.0
Total volume per reaction	Σ 25.0

The interpretation of the Real Time LAMP reaction results was based on graphical representations illustrating the dependence of the change of fluorescence intensity on the reaction time. The amount of product in the Real Time LAMP reaction was determined based on the Time to Threshold value (Tt), i.e., based on the time required to amplify the product in an amount sufficient to cross the threshold fluorescence (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Real Time LAMP reaction: amplification graph.

The Colorimetric LAMP positive results were interpreted based on the change of the indicator color (phenol red) present in the LAMP reaction mixture from pink to yellow (or orange) (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Change of indicator color in Colorimetric LAMP reaction. Image created with BioRender.com

3.1.7 Optimization of LAMP assay for *K. aerogenes* detection

In order to optimize the LAMP reaction, the efficiency of different primer sets and reaction times were tested.

3.1.7.1 Evaluation of LAMP primer sets

To identify suitable primer candidates, all three designed primer sets (*Section 4.1.2*) were tested under identical reaction conditions (65 °C for 45 min). Reactions were carried out on the Genie[®] III instrument (OptiGene, United Kingdom). All reactions were performed in triplicate.

3.1.7.2 Specificity evaluation of best performing primer set (PC2)

The specificity of the chosen LAMP primer set (PC2) was further tested using gDNA originating from two different Gram-positive bacterial strains (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*) as well as from three Gram-negative bacterial strains (*A. faecalis*, *S. enterica*, *E. coli*). The primer specificity was assessed using both LAMP approaches: Colorimetric and Real Time which are performed at 65 °C for 30 min. All LAMP assays were performed in triplicate. Amplification products were analyzed by 2% w/v agarose gel electrophoresis.

3.1.7.3 LAMP assay sensitivity

After identifying the PC2 primer set as optimal and confirming its specificity, the next step involved testing the detection limit for the LAMP reaction. For this purpose, serial dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (59.9 ng/μL) were prepared: 1:10 (5.99 ng/μL), 1:100 (0.599 ng/μL), 1:1000 (59.9 pg/μL), and 1:10000 (5.99 ng/μL). The sensitivity was assessed through both LAMP approaches: Colorimetric and Real Time, both conducted at 65 °C for 30 min. All LAMP assays were carried out in triplicate.

3.1.8 *K. aerogenes* detection in spiked food samples

3.1.8.1 Testing food for *K. aerogenes* contamination

To evaluate the potential contamination of selected vegetable and meat samples with *K. aerogenes* before artificial contamination, gDNA isolates from bacterial cultures grown from the food samples were subjected to testing. This involved the Real Time LAMP assay with the PC2 primer set, as well as performing the most classical biochemical tests for identifying *Klebsiella aerogenes*. These tests include Gram staining, morphology, nitrate reductase test, catalase test, oxidase test, indole test, Voges-Proskauer test, and methyl-red test (Aryal, 2022).

3.1.8.2 Testing the effect of DNA isolation on *K. aerogenes* detection using LAMP

To assess ability to detect *K. aerogenes* gDNA in both vegetable and meat DNA isolates, the effect of DNA isolation methods was compared. For vegetable DNA isolates, the Chelex 100 method and the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit were employed, while for meat DNA isolates, the Chelex 100 method was compared with the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit.

In this experiment, both vegetable and meat DNA samples were artificially contaminated (spiked) by adding *K. aerogenes* gDNA at a concentration of 59.9 ng/ μ L (as described in Sections 3.1.3.1 A and 3.1.3.2 A), ensuring that the final concentration of *K. aerogenes* gDNA in all spiked food DNA extracts is 1 ng/ μ L.

Vegetable and meat DNA isolates that were not artificially contaminated were used as an internal negative control.

3.1.8.3 LOD of LAMP assay for spiked DNA samples isolated by Chelex 100 method and a commercial DNA isolation kit

To assess the LOD of LAMP assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in vegetable and meat DNA extracts obtained with the Chelex 100 method and the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit (for vegetables) or the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (for meat), spiked DNA isolates from each sample were used to prepare serial dilutions (1:10, 1:100, 1:1000, 1:10000). The testing process involved a Real Time LAMP reaction conducted in three replicates for both vegetable and meat DNA extracts.

The significance of the differences in Tt values recorded for all tested food DNA samples (both vegetable and meat) obtained using the Chelex 100 approach and commercial kits for extraction, and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA, was determined using a one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) and Tukey's multiple comparison test for a significance level of $p < 0.05$. GraphPad Prism 8 software was used for statistical data analysis.

3.1.9 *K. aerogenes* detection in inoculated food samples

All food materials underwent artificial contamination by inoculating them with a *K. aerogenes* culture, as detailed in Sections 3.1.3.1 B and 3.1.3.2 B. The main goal was to evaluate the suitability of the proposed DNA extraction methods for subsequent *K. aerogenes* detection using Real Time LAMP. The Chelex 100 method was applied to all inoculated food samples, the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit was used for inoculated vegetables, and the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit was employed for inoculated meat samples. Prior to analysis,

concentrations of isolated DNA were adjusted to 1 ng/μL, and the DNA isolates were then analyzed in Real Time LAMP reactions. All Real Time LAMP assays were carried out in triplicate for vegetables and duplicate for meat samples.

3.1.10 Real Time PCR assay

For Real Time PCR analysis, MyGo Mini S Real Time PCR Instrument (Azura Genomics Inc., USA) was used. The kit used in all Real Time PCR analyses was the Maxima SYBR Green/ROX qPCR Master Mix (2X) (Thermo Scientific, USA).

3.1.10.1 Comparative analysis of the impact of different DNA isolation methods on success of the Real Time PCR assay

To compare Real Time LAMP with Real Time PCR, the same inoculated food DNA extracts obtained as described in the previous section were used for Real Time PCR. Real Time PCR reaction mixtures were prepared based on the calculations provided in Table 4. Each reaction was carried out in a total volume of 15 μL.

In all of the conducted reactions, *K. aerogenes* gDNA (with the concentration of 59.9 ng/μL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as the negative control (no template control).

Table 4. Components of Real Time PCR Reaction mixture.

Component	Volume for one reaction [μL]
Maxima SYBR Green/ROX qPCR Master Mix (2X)	7.5
F3 primer	0.45
B3 primer	0.45
Sample (target DNA)	5.0
PCR H ₂ O	1.6
Total volume per reaction	Σ 15.0

The interpretation of the Real Time PCR reaction results was based on graphical representations illustrating the dependence of the change in fluorescence intensity on reaction time and the dependence of the change in fluorescence intensity related to the number of cycles.

The amount of products in the Real Time PCR reaction was determined based on the Ct value (cycle threshold) (Figure 21), which shows the number of cycles required for the multiplication of a sufficient number of NA copies to cross the limit, i.e. fluorescence threshold.

Figure 21. Amplification graph in Real Time PCR reaction.

3.1.10.2 PCR primers

For Real Time PCR analysis, F3 and B3 from the PC1 LAMP set were used (details in *Section 4.1.2*). Primers were prepared at a concentration of 10 μ M (as recommended by the manufacturer of the mixture used for Real Time PCR). The program for Real Time PCR assay used in this experiment is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Real Time PCR program.

Step	Parameters		
	T (°C)	t (min:sec)	Condition
1. Initial denaturation	95	10:00	∅
2. DNA denaturation	95	0:30	
3. Annealing of primers	56	0:30	Go back to step 2 and repeat 29 times
4. Elongation and detection	72	0:30	
5. a) High Resolution Melting – initial phase	65	0:60	Temperature increase 1.5 °C/second
5. b) High Resolution Melting – final phase	95	0:01	Temperature increase 0.05 °C/second

The melting curve of the Real Time PCR reaction product was documented using the High Resolution Melting (HRM) technique. The specificity of the PCR reaction product was confirmed by the distinctive bell-shape of the melting curve. This curve is represented by the dependence of the change in fluorescence upon temperature change (dF/dT), contingent on the temperature of heating the mixture.

3.1.11 Agarose gel electrophoresis

Products of the Real Time LAMP and Colorimetric LAMP reactions were analyzed on the agarose gel electrophoresis.

2% w/v gel was prepared by dissolving 0.6 g of agarose in 30 mL of TBE buffer (tris/borate/EDTA). For DNA visualization, 1.5 μ L of ROTI[®]GelStain dye (Carl Roth GmbH & Co., Germany) was added directly in the dissolved agarose.

Next, 1 μ L of 6X TriTrack DNA Loading Dye (ThermoScientific, USA) was mixed with 5 μ L of the sample. 6 μ L of such mixture was applied to the gel. 4 μ L of GeneRuler DNA Ladder Mix (ThermoScientific, USA) was also applied to the gel. The voltage was setup to 140V and the run lasted 45 min.

3.2 Development of a LAMP-based assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection in champignon production

To develop a LAMP-based assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection in champignon production, the following experimental setup, as presented in Figure 22, was performed.

Figure 22. Experimental outline for optimization of LAMP based *Trichoderma* spp. detection in champignon production. Image created with BioRender.com

3.2.1 Biological material

3.2.1.1 Fungal cultures

All fungal cultures used in this doctoral dissertation were prepared by cultivation on Malt Agar (MA) (Torlak, Serbia) and incubated at 26 °C for 5–7 days.

Fungal cultures used in this research were: *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Aspergillus carbonarius*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Penicillium halotolerans*, *Cladosporium allicinum*.

All fungal cultures used in this dissertation originate from the BioSense Culture Collection of Fungi (BSCCF), which can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/11385670>.

In all experiments, *T. harzianum* was used as a model for highly aggressive *Trichoderma* spp.

3.2.1.2 Compost and casing soil

All compost and casing soil samples (Figure 23) used in this study were gathered from the organic mushroom production nursery of EKOFUNGI DOO Padinska Skela, Belgrade in the period June-July 2021, in different stages of *Agaricus bisporus* (button mushroom, champignon) cultivation (Table 6).

Figure 23. Compost (left) and casing soil (right) samples used in this doctoral dissertation.

Compost sampling was conducted in three time series:

- Immediately after the composting process, when the inoculated substrate was placed into cultivation bags within the cultivation tunnel (samples from 11/06/2021 labelled as K1-K10 in Table 6);
- Two weeks after inoculation, just before the application of the casing soil layer (samples from 25/06/2021 labelled as K1*-K10* in Table 6);
- After the formation of fruiting bodies, one month after inoculation (samples from 14/07/2021 labelled as K1#-K10# in Table 6);

Casing soil samples were collected before the racking of cultivation bags (samples from 02/07/2021 labelled as P1-P10, Table 6).

Table 6. Compost and casing soil samples from the organic mushroom production nursery collected in different stages of *Agaricus bisporus* cultivation.

Cultivation bag number	Compost 11/06/21	Compost 25/06/21	Casing soil 02/07/21	Compost 14/07/21
1	K1	K1*	P1	K1#
2	K2	K2*	P2	K2#
3	K3	K3*	P3	K3#
4	K4	K4*	P4	K4#
5	K5	K5*	P5	K5#
6	K6	K6*	P6	K6#
7	K7	K7*	P7	K7#
8	K8	K8*	P8	K8#
9	K9	K9*	P9	K9#
10	K10	K10*	P10	K10#

Environmental DNA (eDNA) was extracted from the collected compost and casing soil samples, as described in *Section 3.2.2*. The potential presence of *Trichoderma* spp. in the compost and casing soil used for subsequent research was checked by three different ways:

1. By morphological observation:

Visual inspection with the naked eye, in order to determine whether *Trichoderma* spp. appeared on the cultivating bags.

2. Macro- and microscopic identification to the species level:

By isolation through cultivation and co-cultivation process from the mushroom substrate samples (compost/casing soil). Initially, cultures were grown on Rose Bengal Agar (RBA) (Merk, Germany), at 26 °C for 5–7 days. Subsequently, they were transferred to MA and

allowed to grow at 26 °C for another 5–7 days to obtain pure cultures, which were identified by microscopic observation.

3. Molecular identification:

DNA was extracted from a pure *Trichoderma harzianum* culture obtained through cultivation and co-cultivation using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit. Additionally, eDNA was also extracted from compost and casing soil samples using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC, Germany).

- Genomic DNA of *T. harzianum* in analysed DNA samples obtained from pure fungal culture and compost/casing soil samples was confirmed by: 1) Real Time LAMP using the PC2 primer set (see *Section 4.2.2*), and 2) by DNA metabarcoding approach.
- Sample preparation for DNA metabarcoding analysis was conducted in the Biochemistry and Molecular Biology laboratory at the BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad within the DRAGON project (GA 810775). The internal transcribed spacer 2 (ITS2) sequences of the nuclear ribosomal DNA produced using primer pair ITS3-2024F/ITS4-2409R (White et al., 1990) was used as a DNA barcode for molecular identification of fungal species. Details on the analysis are available in DRAGON Report on S&T dedicated workshops (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/810775/reporting>).

After employing various described approaches to confirm the presence of *Trichoderma* spp., a few samples (9 in total) were selected for further analysis (as described in *Section 4.2.7*).

3.2.2 DNA extraction

3.2.2.1 DNA extraction from fungal cultures

A pure fungal culture, prepared as outlined in *Section 3.2.1.1*, served as the starting material for DNA isolation. This culture was meticulously scraped from the cultivation plate using a spatula and transferred to a 2 mL tube.

The Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit was employed for the isolation of DNA from pure fungal cultures. The isolation procedure was done according to the methodology outlined in *Section 3.1.2.2 B*.

3.2.2.2 DNA extraction from compost and casing soil

To extract DNA from compost and casing material, two methods were employed: the Chelex 100 method (suitable for in-field applications) and the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC, Germany).

For both methods, 250 mg of each sample was used as starting material.

A) Chelex 100 - DNA extraction method

The isolation procedure was done according to the methodology outlined in *Section 3.1.2.2 A*.

B) DNA extraction by using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit

Materials:

- GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC, Germany) which includes:
 - Lysis Buffer G;
 - Lysis Additive A;
 - Binding Buffer I;
 - OSR Solution;
 - Lysis Buffer QP;
 - Binding Buffer B;
 - Wash Solution A;
 - Elution Buffer B;
 - Bead Tubes;
 - Spin Columns;
 - Collection Tubes;
 - Elution tubes;
- Sterile 2 mL tubes;
- Ice;
- Absolute ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Compost/casing soil samples (250 mg).

Procedure:

1. 250 mg of compost/casing soil sample was added to a provided Bead Tube;
2. 750 μ L of Lysis Buffer G was added, vortexed, and then 200 μ L of Lysis Additive A was added;
3. The tube was vortexed in a horizontal position for 5 min at maximum speed;
4. The tube was centrifuged for 1 minute at 20000g;
5. The supernatant was transferred to a sterile 2 mL tube (not provided in the kit);
6. 100 μ L of Binding Buffer I was added, mixed by inverting the tube a few times, and incubated on ice for 5 min;
7. The tube was centrifuged for 5 min at 20000g;
8. Up to 700 μ L of supernatant was transferred into a new sterile microtube (2 mL) and 50 μ L of OSR solution was added;
9. The tube was mixed by inverting it a few times and incubated for 5 min on ice;
10. The tube was then centrifuged for 10 min at 20000g (at 4 °C);
11. 700 μ L of supernatant was transferred into a new sterile microtube (2 mL) and 400 μ L of Lysis Buffer QP along with 550 μ L of 96–100% ethanol were added. The mixture was briefly vortexed;
12. The tube content was mixed, and 600 μ L of the mixture was transferred onto the Spin Column (grey o-ring) and centrifuged for 30 sec at 10000g;
13. The flowthrough was discarded, and step 12 was repeated as many times as needed for total lysate mixture (from step 12) pass through the column;
14. 500 μ L of Binding Buffer B was added to the column and centrifuged for 1 min at 10000g. The flowthrough was discarded;
15. 500 μ L of Wash Solution A was added and centrifuged for 1 min at 10000g. The flowthrough was discarded;
16. Steps 14 and 15 were repeated;
17. The column was centrifuged for 2 min at 20000g. The collection tube was discarded;
18. The column was placed into the elution tube, 100 μ L of Elution Buffer B was added, and it was incubated for 1 min at room temperature;
19. The column was then centrifuged for 1 min at 10000g to elute DNA.
20. DNA was stored at -20°C.

3.2.3 Targeted, controlled contamination of compost and casing soil

Targeted, controlled contamination of compost and casing soil samples was conducted using two approaches:

A) Spiking with *Trichoderma harzianum* gDNA

Procedure:

Genomic DNA from *Trichoderma harzianum* gDNA (concentration 229.31 ng/μL) was directly added to a tube containing compost/casing soil eDNA extract with the aim of achieving a final concentration of 1 ng/μL for *T. harzianum* gDNA in the spiked sample. This concentration is subsequently used for the LAMP analyses.

B) Inoculation with *Trichoderma harzianum* pure culture

Procedure:

Inoculation was carried out by adding 50 mg of a pure *T. harzianum* culture into a 2 mL tube containing 250 mg of compost/casing soil (in a 1:5 proportion). Subsequently, these samples underwent DNA extraction, as detailed in *Section 3.2.2.2*.

3.2.4 Concentration and purity of DNA

The determination of concentration and evaluation of DNA purity were performed as described in *Section 3.1.4*.

3.2.5 LAMP primer design for *Trichoderma* spp.

The target gene chosen for LAMP primer design was the *tef1* gene (GeneBank OL435125), which codes translation elongation factor 1 alpha (EF1 α) and is well known as a secondary fungal DNA barcode for *Trichoderma* species (Meyer et. al., 2019).

Before designing LAMP primers, the same gene was analysed using the online software Nucleotide Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (Nucleotide BLAST; <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) to check if the chosen target gene (*tef1*) is highly conserved across other organisms.

Upon conducting an extensive analysis of parameters for primer design (previously described within *Section 1.3.1.1*), two sets of highly promising primer candidates (PCs) that exhibit specificity towards the *tef1* gene of *Trichoderma* spp. were produced. LAMP primers were designed and analyzed using online software Primer Explorer V5 (<http://primerexplorer.jp>).

3.2.6 LAMP assay

All LAMP reactions in this experimental section of the dissertation were conducted following the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.6*.

In all the conducted reactions, *T. harzianum* gDNA (concentration 229.31 ng/μL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as the negative control (no template control).

3.2.7 Optimization of LAMP assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection

In order to optimize the LAMP reaction, the efficiency of different primer sets and reaction times were tested.

3.2.7.1 Evaluation of LAMP primer sets

To identify suitable primer candidates, two newly designed primer sets (see *Section 4.2.2*) were tested under identical reaction conditions (65 °C for 60 min). Reactions were carried out on the Genie® III instrument (OptiGene, United Kingdom). All reactions were performed in triplicate.

3.2.7.2 Specificity evaluation of best performed primer set (PC2)

The specificity of the chosen LAMP primer set (PC2) was further tested using gDNA extracted from various fungal cultures, those that are commonly found in substrates for mushroom cultivation: *A. carbonarius*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. alternata*, *P. halotolerans*, and *C. allicinum*. The specificity was assessed using both, Colorimetric and Real Time LAMP performed at 65 °C for 30 min. All LAMP assays were performed in triplicate. Amplification products were analyzed by 2% w/v agarose gel electrophoresis.

Additionally, to confirm that the developed LAMP primers are genus-specific, primer specificity was tested *in silico* using sequences of *tefl* genes from different *Trichoderma* species in BioEdit v7.2.0 software (Informer Technologies, Inc.). This analysis was based on the complementarity of LAMP primer sequences with homologous target regions of the *tefl* gene sequences from *T. harzianum* (GenBank: OL435125) and seven other *Trichoderma* species: *T. auriculariae* (GenBank: OR548070), *T. endophyticum* (GenBank: KX689257), *T. lentinulae* (GenBank: OP832395), *T. pollinicola* (GenBank: MF939621), *T. simmonsii* (GenBank: OP562772), *T. vermifimicola* (GenBank: MN605882), and *T. xixiacum* (GenBank: MN605885).

3.2.7.3 LAMP assay sensitivity

After identifying an optimal primer set (PC2) and confirming its specificity, the next step involved testing the detection limit for the LAMP reaction. For this purpose, serial dilutions of *T. harzianum* gDNA (concentration 229.31 ng/ μ L) were prepared: 1:10 (22.931 ng/ μ L), 1:100 (2.2931 ng/ μ L), 1:1000 (229.31 pg/ μ L), and 1:10000 (22.931 pg/ μ L). The sensitivity was assessed for both LAMP approaches, Colorimetric and Real Time LAMP, conducted at 65 °C for 30 min. All LAMP assays were carried out in triplicate.

3.2.8 *Trichoderma* spp. detection in spiked compost and casing soil samples

3.2.8.1 Testing compost and casing soil extracts for *Trichoderma* spp. contamination

The evaluation of potential *Trichoderma* spp. contamination in selected compost and casing soil samples, before artificial contamination, was conducted following the procedure outlined in Section 3.2.1.2.

3.2.8.2 Testing the effect of DNA isolation from compost and casing soil samples on *Trichoderma* spp. detection using LAMP

To evaluate the detection capability of *Trichoderma* spp. gDNA in compost and casing soil isolates, we compared the effect of isolation methods. Specifically, the Chelex 100 method was compared with the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit for this purpose.

In this experiment, samples were artificially contaminated by adding *T. harzianum* gDNA (concentration 229.31 ng/ μ L) in eDNA extracted from compost and casing soil samples (as described in Section 3.2.3.1 A), ensuring that the final concentration of *T. harzianum* gDNA in all spiked eDNA extracts is 1 ng/ μ L.

Compost and casing soil isolates that were not artificially contaminated were used as an internal negative control.

3.2.8.3 LOD of LAMP assay for spiked eDNA samples isolated by Chelex 100 method and a commercial DNA isolation kit

To assess LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. detection in compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained through the Chelex 100 method and by using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, spiked eDNA extracts from each sample were utilized to prepare serial dilutions (1:10, 1:100, 1:1000, 1:10000). The LOD is assessed for Real Time LAMP reaction conducted in three replicates for all tested samples.

3.2.9 *Trichoderma* spp. detection in inoculated compost and casing soil samples

All compost and casing soil materials were artificially contaminated by inoculating them with a *T. harzianum* pure culture, as outlined in *Section 3.2.3 B*. This was done to assess the effect of the applied DNA extraction methods for subsequent detection of *Trichoderma* spp. using Real Time LAMP.

3.2.10 Real Time PCR assay

All Real Time PCR reactions in this experimental section of the dissertation were conducted in accordance with the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.10*.

For all the conducted reactions, *T. harzianum* gDNA (with a concentration of 229.31 ng/μL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as the NTC (no template control).

3.2.10.1 PCR primers

For the Real Time PCR analysis, testing of F3 and B3 from both the PC1 and PC2 LAMP sets (from Table 22, *Section 4.2.2*) was performed. The primers were initially assessed for specificity using gDNA from other non-target fungal strains (*Section 3.2.7.2*) as a target.

Furthermore, PCR primers from the literature (Lee et al., 2020) targeting conserved regions of ITS1 and ITS2 that are specific to *Trichoderma* spp. (Table 7) were also tested.

Table 7. PCR primers for *Trichoderma* spp. detection from the literature (Lee et al., 2020).

Primer name	Sequence 5'-3'	T _m (°C)	Length (bp)
TDP-F	CGAGTTTACAACCTCCCAA	49.9	19
TDP-R	GAAAGTTGGGTGTTTAACG	49.3	19

The primers were prepared at a concentration of 10 μM, as recommended by the manufacturer of the mixture used for Real Time PCR.

The Real Time PCR assay program for F3 and B3 from the PC1 and PC2 sets is outlined in Table 5 in *Section 3.1.10.2*.

For the TDP-F and TDP-R primers from the literature (Lee et al., 2020), the same PCR program was applied, with a modification in the annealing temperature to 50 °C.

3.2.11 Agarose gel electrophoresis

The products of the Real Time LAMP and Colorimetric LAMP reactions were examined through agarose gel electrophoresis, following the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.11*.

3.2.12 LAMP assay coupled with Gold Nanoparticles for Colorimetric Detection of *Trichoderma* spp.

One of the experimental goals of this doctoral dissertation was the development of innovative approaches for the visualization of positive LAMP reactions in the detection of *Trichoderma* spp. For these purposes, a LAMP assay coupled with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) was developed.

The assay is based on salt-induced aggregation of AuNPs that is being prevented by the amplicons produced in case of positive LAMP reaction. As the solution colour changes from red to violet upon nanoparticle aggregation, change in color can be observed with the naked eye (Figure 24), the developed LAMP-AuNPs assay can be easily operated to provide a simple initial screening for the rapid detection of *Trichoderma* during mushroom cultivation.

Figure 24. The principle of LAMP-AuNP assay for *Trichoderma* detection. (Đisalov et. al., 2024).

3.2.12.1 LAMP assay

In this experimental section of the dissertation, all LAMP reactions were carried out according to the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.6*. The PC2 primer set, previously validated for specificity and sensitivity as described in *Sections 3.2.7.2* and *3.2.7.3*, was used.

3.2.12.2 AuNPs

20 nm AuNPs were synthesized and characterized in the MicrobAdapt group's lab at Micalis Institute (INRAe, Jouy-en-Josas, France) using the reduced citrate method explained in Braiek et al., 2016.

3.2.12.3 LAMP-AuNP assay optimization

Optimization of salt concentration

For the sensitive detection of LAMP products, it's crucial to ensure that AuNPs aggregate appropriately in response to a minimal amount of salt. When exposed to high salt conditions, citrate-capped AuNPs easily aggregate, and a considerable number of amplicon molecules are required to prevent this aggregation.

In order to improve the sensitivity of the colorimetric detection, the concentration of MgCl₂ using 1, 5, and 10 µL of MgCl₂ with varying molarities (2 mM, 20 mM, and 2M) was tested. The impact of salt concentration on the aggregation of AuNPs was examined in a 150 µL volume containing 2 x 10⁹ NPs. This volume was selected to align the assay with a multiplex 96-well microplate format.

Optimization of incubation temperature and time

Next, various temperatures and time conditions were tested to improve binding of the LAMP products to AuNPs. For this purpose, 2 µL of the obtained LAMP amplicons (with the concentration range from 2400 ng/µL to 2.4 fg/µL) were carefully transferred to the well containing 50 µL of AuNPs and 98 µL of MilliQ water. Next, the mixture was tested for different conditions: 1. without incubation; 2. incubation at 55 °C for 20 min; and 3. incubation at 65 °C for 10 min. Subsequently, 2.5 µL of 20 mM MgCl₂ was added and the color change was observed by naked-eye or by measuring the absorption of solution using the SPARK multimode microplate reader (Tecan Global Headquarters, Männedorf, Switzerland).

LAMP-AuNP assay specificity

To assess the specificity of the LAMP-AuNP assay, AuNPs were incubated with a positive LAMP reaction obtained using gDNA of *T. harzianum* and negative LAMP reaction performed without DNA template, or with non-specific gDNA from *B. subtilis* (concentration 26.01 ng/µL) together with LAMP master mix (WarmStart LAMP Reagent containing deoxynucleotides dNTPs, *Bst* 2.0 WarmStart DNA Polymerase, isothermal amplification buffer, LAMP primers and PCR-grade water).

After addition of 2.5 μL of 20 mM MgCl_2 the color change was observed by naked-eye or by measuring the absorption of solution using the SPARK multimode microplate reader (Tecan Global Headquarters, Männedorf, Switzerland).

LAMP-AuNP assay sensitivity

To ascertain the minimum detectable amount of the LAMP product by AuNPs, an investigation was carried out involving a 10-fold serial dilution of positive LAMP reaction products in the context of *T. harzianum* gDNA detection. In parallel, serial dilutions of the no-template reaction was also tested. Ten-fold serial dilutions of all products from the LAMP reaction were performed using PCR-grade water, ranging from dilutions at 2400 ng/ μL to 2.4 fg/ μL .

3.3 LAMP-based assay for *E. coli* detection in highly polluted water samples

3.3.1 Biological material

3.3.1.1 Bacterial cultures

The pure culture of *E. coli* used in this experimental section of the presented doctoral dissertation was prepared by cultivating on TSA (Millipore, USA) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours (overnight) in thermostat incubator (Incubator IN55, Memmert, Germany).

3.3.1.2 Water samples

Water samples used in this part of doctoral dissertation were collected from the Danube River in Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia from three different sampling sites near one of the sewage outfalls (Figures 25-26):

- Sampling site 1 (S1) – upstream of the city sewage outfall (coordinates on Google maps: 45.2537700, 19.8555206)
- Sampling site 2 (S2) – city sewage outfall (coordinates on Google maps: 45.2530608, 19.8558857)
- Sampling site 3 (S3) upstream of S1 (coordinates on Google maps: 45.2561503, 19.8551548)

Figure 25. Google Earth satellite image of the study area – sampling points at Danube River in Novi Sad. S1 – sample point 1 upstream of the city sewage outfall; S2 – sample point 2 at the city sewage outfall; S3 – sample point 3 upstream of S1.

Figure 26. City sewage outfall. (Coordinates on Google maps: 45.2530608, 19.8558857). Image taken by Mila Đisalov, on 22.05.2022.

From each sampling site, 500 mL of river water was collected using a sampling stick and stored in sterile glass bottles at 4 °C until further analyses (up to 24h).

3.3.2 Microbiological confirmation of *E. coli* presence in water samples

Microbiological confirmation of *E. coli* presence in tested river water samples - S1, S2 and S3 was done by spread plate seeding on Chromogenic Coliform Agar (CCA) (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) plates, a selective media used for enumeration of *E. coli* and coliform bacteria. Dilutions of the raw water samples, ranging from 1/2 to 10⁻², were applied and plates were cultivated at 37 °C for 24 h in thermostat incubator (Incubator IN55, Memmert, Germany). The quantification of *E. coli* in the samples was achieved by counting only the colonies that tested positive for both β-galactosidase and β-glucuronidase, enzymes contained in CCA, resulting in a dark blue to violet color of colonies. To calculate the final CFU per 1 mL i.e., per 100 mL, the test was performed in duplicate.

3.3.3 DNA extraction

3.3.3.1 DNA extraction from bacterial cultures

The DNA extraction from pure bacterial cultures was done by using the protocol described in *Section 3.1.2.1*.

3.3.3.2. DNA extraction from highly polluted water sample

The extraction of eDNA from environmental, water samples (S1, S2, and S3) was conducted using the modified protocol described by Kesberg and Schleheck (2013), taking a step forward towards its applicability in the field (see Figure 27).

Figure 27. Procedure for DNA extraction from highly polluted water samples. A) pre-filtration steps; B) syringe filter-based DNA extraction modified from Kesberg and Schleheck (2013).

Materials:

- Sterile 10 µm pore-size filter (WhatmanTM, United Kingdom);
- Sterile 0.45 µm pore-size filter (Filtres Fioroni, France);
- Sterile 0.22 µm pore-sized Vented Millex - GS syringe filters (Millipore, USA);
- Sterile 1x TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl; 1 mM EDTA, pH 7.4);
- Sterile TL buffer (10mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 10mM EDTA, 7.5 mg/mL lysozyme);
- Sterile TPS buffer (10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 10 mM EDTA, 300 µg/mL proteinase K, 1% SDS (w/v));
- Sterile washing buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 1 mM EDTA pH 8.0, 70% ethanol);
- 70% ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA);
- Water samples.

Procedure:

1. Water samples were pre-filtered through a 10 µm pore-size filter (Whatman™, United Kingdom), followed by filtration through a 0.45 µm pore-size sterile filter (Filtres Fioroni, France);
2. The 0.45 µm filter was placed into a sterile 15 mL Falcon tube containing 10 mL of TE buffer;
3. The tubes containing concentrated samples in TE buffer were further sonicated for 2 min to detach cells collected on the filter;
4. 10 mL of each sample was filtered through 0.22 µm pore-sized Vented Millex – GS syringe filters (Millipore, USA) and washed by filtering through 500 µL of TE buffer;
5. The syringe filter was then inverted to backwash in the direction opposite from filtration using 300 µL of lysis buffer - TL, with an additional 150 µL added to the flow-through;
6. The flow-through was mixed by pipetting;
7. 500 µL of TPS buffer was filtered in the same direction (backwash);
8. The flow-through was incubated at 65 °C for 15 min to increase eDNA yield;
9. An additional 500 µL of TPS buffer was filtered, and 500 µL was added to the flow-through;
10. The flow-through was mixed by pipetting, and the filter was backflushed 3 times with air to ensure the complete drainage of the eDNA retentate;
11. The filter was discharged;
12. 500 µL of the washing buffer was added;
13. The sample was centrifuged for 2 min at 10000g;
14. The sample was washed twice with 70% ethanol;
15. After each wash, the sample was centrifuged for 2 min at 10000g;
16. The supernatant was discarded;
17. The eDNA was dissolved in 50 µL of the TE buffer;
18. The eDNA was stored at -20°C.

3.3.4 Concentration and purity of DNA

The determination of concentration and evaluation of DNA purity were performed as described in *Section 3.1.4*.

3.3.5 LAMP primers for *E. coli* detection

LAMP primers used in this study are taken from the literature (Table 8) (Song et al., 2019). The primers are targeting *malB* gene (maltose protein operon B), known to be conserved in several different strains of *E. coli* (including the tested strain, ATCC® 25922™).

Table 8. LAMP Primer set for *E. coli* detection (Song et al., 2019).

Primer ID	Sequence (5' - 3')
<i>E. coli</i> - F3	CACCTTCATGGATATCGAGATT
<i>E. coli</i> - B3	TGGAGGATTTAAGCCATCTC
<i>E. coli</i> - FIP(F1c+F2)	CGAGCGTACAGCTGCAAATGATATCTTTTCGATACCACGACCT
<i>E. coli</i> - BIP(B1c+B2)	CCCTTCTCCCTTTGTAACAAGATGACGCATAGTCAGCCCAT
<i>E. coli</i> - LF	TAACGAAAGCCTGGGGCG
<i>E. coli</i> - BF	CCTGTCATCGACAGCAACATTCA

3.3.6 LAMP assay

All LAMP reactions in this experimental section of the dissertation were conducted following the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.6*.

In all the conducted reactions, *E. coli* gDNA (concentration 50 ng/μL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as the NTC (no template control).

3.3.7 Real Time PCR assay

All Real Time PCR reactions in this experimental section of the dissertation were conducted following the procedure outlined in *Section 3.1.10*.

In all the conducted reactions, *E. coli* gDNA (concentration 50 ng/μL) served as the positive control, while PCR-grade water was employed as NTC (no template control).

3.2.7.1 PCR primers

For Real Time PCR analysis, F3 and B3 from the LAMP set were used (Table 8 in *Section 3.3.5*). Primers were prepared at a concentration of 10 μM (as recommended by the manufacturer of the mixture used for Real Time PCR). The program for Real Time PCR assay used in this experiment is showed in Table 5, *Section 3.1.10.2*).

4. Results

4.1 Development of a LAMP-based assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in food matrices

Results presented in this section pertain to all experiments described within *Section 3.1*.

The first part of *Section 4.1* presents the results of DNA extraction from bacterial species used in further experiments, as well as from food samples (both artificially contaminated and non-contaminated) using two different extraction approaches: laboratory and field applicable (*Section 4.1.1*). This was done to evaluate the efficiency of the DNA extraction method optimized within this dissertation for field application and to consider the further application of such DNA extracts in bacterial pathogen detection using the LAMP assay.

4.1.1 Concentration and purity of DNA

Concentration and purity of gDNA isolated for the experiments with *K. aerogenes* are presented in Tables 9–13.

4.1.1.1 Bacterial cultures

Table 9 represents the concentration values of gDNA acquired through isolation from bacterial species available in BioSense Culture Collection of Bacteria.

Table 9. Concentration and purity of gDNA from bacterial species used to verify the specificity of the PC2 LAMP primer set for *Klebsiella aerogenes*.

Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
<i>Alcaligenes faecalis</i>	52.15	2.20	1.07
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	26.01	1.96	1.83
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	66.26	2.37	1.98
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	50.00	1.60	1.19
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	40.07	1.72	1.87
<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>	59.90	1.91	1.84

The concentration values of gDNAs isolated from selected bacterial cultures varied between 26.01 ng/μL and 66.26 ng/μL. Listed gDNA samples were used to assess the specificity of the PC2 LAMP primer set for *K. aerogenes* (see *Section 4.1.2*).

4.1.1.2 Vegetable material

The concentration values of gDNAs isolated from bacterial cultures, cultivated from vegetable samples, varied between 31.04 ng/μL and 101.02 ng/μL (Table 10).

Table 10. Concentration and purity of gDNA from bacterial cultures microbiologically cultivated from vegetable samples.

Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
Bacterial culture from carrot	31.04	2.45	1.89
Bacterial culture from cucumber	32.89	2.49	2.42
Bacterial culture from lettuce	101.22	2.10	2.72

The highest gDNA concentration was achieved through the isolation from bacterial cultures originating from lettuce samples (101.02 ng/μL). Concentrations of bacterial gDNA from cultures derived from carrot and cucumber samples exhibited similar values, 31.04 ng/μL and 32.89 ng/μL, respectively.

For all three gDNA extracts originating from bacteria cultured from vegetable samples, the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ absorbance ratio was higher than the upper reference value of 1.9.

The absorbance ratio A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀ for the gDNA extract from carrot bacterial culture was below the lower reference value – 1.89.

For gDNA samples from cucumber and lettuce bacterial cultures, the absorbance ratio A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀ (2.42 and 2.72) exceeded the reference value.

The concentration values of DNA samples obtained using Chelex 100 isolation method, including both artificially inoculated and non-inoculated vegetable DNA extract samples, ranged from 70.20 ng/μL to 273 ng/μL. On the other hand, the concentration values of the DNA samples obtained using Plant/Fungi DNA isolation kit, including both inoculated and non-inoculated vegetable DNA extracts, ranged from 5.31 ng/μL to 28.35 ng/μL (Table 11).

Table 11. Concentration and purity of gDNA isolated by Chelex 100 method and using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit (Norgen Biotek, Canada) from vegetable samples after inoculation with bacterial suspension.

DNA extraction – Chelex 100 method			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀	A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀
Carrot + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	79.29	0.94	0.29
Cucumber + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	129.84	1.49	0.50
Lettuce + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	273.00	1.54	0.75
Carrot	70.20	2.53	0.40
Cucumber	123.40	1.47	0.59
Lettuce	126.48	1.50	0.30
DNA extraction using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀	A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀
Carrot + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	28.35	3.62	0.47
Cucumber + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	14.86	3.01	0.45
Lettuce + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	16.00	1.37	0.92
Carrot	14.37	2.62	0.43
Cucumber	6.75	6.70	0.21
Lettuce	5.31	1.52	0.65

For both, artificially inoculated and non-inoculated DNA extracts, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} was consistently below 1.7 using the Chelex 100 method, indicating values lower than the lower reference threshold. The only exception was noted in the non-artificially contaminated carrot DNA extract sample. The absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} for this sample was higher than the above reference value, i.e, higher than 1.9.

The A_{260}/A_{230} absorbance ratio for DNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 isolation method ranged from 0.29 to 0.75 (lower than the specified lower reference threshold).

For samples obtained using the Plant/Fungi DNA isolation kit, the A_{260}/A_{280} absorbance ratio values varied significantly among the samples. For both the inoculated and the non-inoculated lettuce DNA extracts, the A_{260}/A_{280} ratio values were below the lower reference value. For all other samples, the value of the A_{260}/A_{280} ratio was higher than the above reference value (Table 11).

The A_{260}/A_{230} absorbance ratio values using Plant/Fungi DNA isolation kit ranged from 0.21 to 0.92, thus, below the lower reference threshold.

4.1.1.3 Meat and meat products

The concentration of gDNAs isolated from bacterial cultures, cultivated from meat samples, were 98.07 ng/μL and 101.02 ng/μL for chicken breasts and chicken salami, respectively (Table 12).

Table 12. Concentration and purity of gDNA isolated from bacterial cultures from microbiologically cultivated meat samples.

Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
Bacterial culture from chicken breasts	98.07	1.89	0.68
Bacterial culture from chicken salami	272.94	1.56	0.6

For gDNA samples obtained from bacterial cultures cultivated from chicken breasts, the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ absorbance ratio (1.89) falls within the range of reference values. Conversely, the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ absorbance ratio for gDNA extracted from cultures grown from chicken salami was below the lower reference value, measuring at 1.56.

The A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀ absorbance ratio for the gDNA samples isolated from bacterial cultures grown from chicken breasts and chicken salami was below the lower reference threshold (0.60 and 0.68, respectively).

Concentrations of gDNA from artificially inoculated and non-inoculated meat samples obtained using the Chelex 100 isolation method, ranged from 10.08 ng/μL to 59.42 ng/μL (Table 13).

Table 13. Concentration and purity of gDNA isolated using Chelex 100 method and DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (Qiagen, Germany) from meat samples, after inoculation with bacterial suspension.

DNA extraction – Chelex 100 method			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
Chicken breasts + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	59.42	2.17	0.43
Chicken salami + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	19.71	1.21	0.54
Chicken breasts	26.84	1.33	0.36
Chicken salami	10.08	1.52	0.54
DNA extraction by using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
Chicken breasts + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	17.69	1.92	1.63
Chicken salami + <i>K. aerogenes</i>	10.88	1.81	0.10
Chicken breasts	11.16	1.74	0.73
Chicken salami	10.18	1.62	0.10

Similarly, the concentration values of samples obtained through isolation with the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit, including both inoculated and non-inoculated meat gDNA extracts ranged from 10.18 ng/μL to 17.69 ng/μL. These values fall within the concentration range observed for meat extracts obtained by the Chelex 100 method.

For both inoculated extracts and non-artificially contaminated extracts, the absorbance ratio A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ consistently remained below 1.7 in samples obtained through the Chelex 100 method, indicating values lower than the lower reference threshold. However, an exception was observed in the artificially contaminated chicken breasts gDNA extract sample. The absorbance ratio A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ for this specific sample was 2.17, falling to the range of recommended reference values. On the other hand, the A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀ absorbance ratio ranged from 0.36 to 0.54 (lower than the specified lower reference threshold).

For gDNA samples obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit, the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ absorbance ratio values did not vary significantly among the samples. For all inoculated and

non-inoculated meat extract samples, the values of A_{260}/A_{280} ratio were within the range of recommended reference values. The only exception was observed in the case of the non-inoculated chicken salami gDNA extract, which exhibited an A_{260}/A_{280} ratio value of 1.62. The A_{260}/A_{230} absorbance ratio ranged from 0.10 to 1.63 (below the lower reference threshold).

4.1.2 LAMP primers for *K. aerogenes*

The results of the LAMP primer design for the detection of *K. aerogenes* are described in the following section, as well as results of primer sets comparison leading to selection of the best performing primer candidate. The specificity of the selected primer set was further tested, and its limit of detection (LOD) was determined (see *Section 4.1.3*).

The BLAST analysis results have indicated that the sequence of the *HDC* gene (Gene ID: 66602288), used for LAMP primer design, shows high similarity with all 76 *HDC* gene sequences from various *K. aerogenes* strains. These sequences exhibit a query coverage of 100%, with a percentage of identity ranging from 97.83% to 100%.

The designed primer sequences, along with their respective positions on the *K. aerogenes HDC* gene, are presented in Table 14 and Figures 28–30, respectively.

Table 14. LAMP primers for *K. aerogenes* designed *de novo*

Primer candidate (PC)	Primer name	Sequence 5'-3'	Position	Length (bp)
PC1-HDC	PC1-F3	ATTATCTACACGCGGATGCC	587-606	20
	PC1-B3	GCGTGACCCTGAAATCGT	799-816	18
	PC1-FIP (F2+F1c)	TGTCCGGAACGCCAATCGAAT-TGATCTTGCCTTTCGTGGAG	N.A.	42
	PC1-BIP (B2+B1c)	TGGTAGCCAAGAAAGCCAACGT-TATCGTGGGCGGAGATGT	N.A.	40
	PC1-LF	GCGAAGGTAAACGGTTGTGGA	642-662	21
	PC1-LB	GACCGTATCAGCGTAGAGATCG	754-775	22
PC2-HDC	PC2-F3	ACGGTCATACCCCTTTGATG	818-837	20
	PC2-B3	CCAGGCAGTGTTCCTTCCAT	1005-1024	20
	PC2-FIP (F2+F1c)	CGGCGTATTTCCGCCATGTTGAG-GTTCGCAGCCATACCGAT	N.A.	40
	PC2-BIP (B2+B1c)	AAGCAGCAGGTATTGACGCGC-CCCATTGAGAAGGCTTCGG	N.A.	40
	PC2-LF	GCTGTGACCAATGCGGC	881-897	17
	PC2-LB	CACAAAACTCCATCACGGTGG	958-979	22
PC3-HDC	PC3-F3	CTCAACATGGCGAAATACGC	989-917	20
	PC3-B3	GCCAGGTCGGCAATTACG	1104-1121	18
	PC3-FIP (F2+F1c)	TCGGAAAGACCACCGTGATGGA-ATCGCTTAAAGCAGCAGGT	N.A.	42
	PC3-BIP (B2+B1c)	CGTAGCCCATCTGATCACCACC-ATCGATCAGCGCATCAATCC	N.A.	42
	PC3-LB	TCACCACCTGGACAGTTCCC	1062-1081	20

Figure 28. Schematic illustration of *HDC* gene showing positions and directions of LAMP primer candidate 1 (PC1).

Figure 29. Schematic illustration of *HDC* gene showing positions and directions of LAMP primer candidate 2 (PC2).

Figure 30. Schematic illustration of *HDC* gene showing positions and directions of LAMP primer candidate 3 (PC3).

4.1.3 Optimization of LAMP assay for *K. aerogenes* detection

Results from primer candidate evaluation revealed that a reaction time of 30 min consistently produced positive and stable outcomes. Reaction that last more than 30 min resulted in false positives. Thus, reaction time of 30 min was considered optimal and was applied across all subsequent LAMP assays.

4.1.3.1 Evaluation of LAMP primer sets

The results of the LAMP primer candidates evaluation are depicted in Graphs 1–3.

Graph 1. Real Time LAMP amplification graph of primer candidates for *K. aerogenes* detection. *Klebsiella aerogenes* gDNA was used as a template for all primer set candidates. PCR-grade water was used instead of DNA for the non-template control (NTC) for each primer candidate (PC). Red curve – LAMP amplification with PC1, orange curve – LAMP amplification with PC2, yellow curve – LAMP amplification with PC3, light blue curve – non-templet control (NTC) for PC1, dark blue curve – NTC for PC2, pink curve – NTC for PC3.

Graph 2. Tt values of different primer candidates for *K. aerogenes* detection-PC1, PC2 and PC3.

The amplification curve for primer candidate PC1 (red curve) appears first, with a Tt of approximately 12 min (Graph 1 & 2). However, a false positive result was observed in the

control test, suggesting that this particular primer set may not be suitable for future analyses. Amplification with PC3 takes place after approximately 21 min (yellow curve), indicating a longer time compared to the amplification with PC2. Furthermore, a peak of amplification in the negative control is observed after about 38 min (purple curve). For candidate PC2, the T_t was approximately 16 min (green curve). Additionally, no amplification was observed in the negative control for candidate PC2. This primer candidate set has been chosen for further optimization of the LAMP based detection protocol for *K. aerogenes*.

After the Real Time LAMP reaction for primer candidates performance evaluation, the melting curves depicted in Graph 3 were obtained. The lower peak values were observed for the NTCs of primer candidates PC1 and PC3 (dark blue and purple curves) compared to the positive reactions. suggest that the amplification results for these samples represents false positives.

Graph 3. Real Time LAMP melting curve of amplification products produced with different primer candidates for *K. aerogenes* detection. *Klebsiella aerogenes* gDNA was used as a template for all primer set candidates. PCR-grade water was used instead of DNA for non-template controls (NTCs) for each primer candidate (PC). Red curve – LAMP amplification with PC1, orange curve – LAMP amplification with PC2, yellow curve – LAMP amplification with PC3, light blue curve – non-templet control (NTC) for PC1, dark blue curve – NTC for PC2, pink curve – NTC for PC3.

4.1.3.2 Specificity evaluation of best performed primer set (PC2)

The results of the evaluation of PC2 specificity obtained by the Real Time and Colorimetric LAMP methods are shown in Graphs 4–5, and Figure 31 respectively. The results from Graph 4 indicate that a positive result was observed only for the species *K. aerogenes* (red curve in the Graph).

Graph 4. Amplification graph for assessing the specificity of PC2 for *K. aerogenes* detection using the Real Time LAMP method with the following templates: *K. aerogenes* gDNA for specific reaction (red curve), *A. faecalis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (orange curve), *E. coli* gDNA for non-specific reaction (yellow curve), *S. enterica* gDNA for non-specific reaction (light green curve), *S. aureus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (dark green curve), *B. subtilis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (blue curve), and non-template control (NTC) for PC2 (pink curve).

Based on the results presented in Graph 5 and the characteristic shape of the melting curve in the sample where amplification occurred the specificity of the PC2 primer set has been validated.

Graph 5. Melting curve for checking the specificity of PC2 for *K. aerogenes* detection using the Real Time LAMP method with the following templates: *K. aerogenes* gDNA for specific reaction (red curve), *A. faecalis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (orange curve), *E. coli* gDNA for non-specific reaction (yellow curve), *S. enterica* gDNA for non-specific reaction (light green curve), *S. aureus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (dark green curve), *B. subtilis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (blue curve), and non-template control (NTC) for PC2 (pink curve).

The assessment of the PC2 primer set's specificity was additionally conducted using the Colorimetric LAMP method. The results, as illustrated in Figure 31, indicated a positive reaction exclusively for the *K. aerogenes* sample after 30 min, visualized by the transition of the indicator colour from pink to yellow.

Figure 31. Confirmation of the specificity of the PC2 primer set for *K. aerogenes* using the Colorimetric LAMP method with the following templates: *K. aerogenes* gDNA for specific reaction (resulted in yellow solution), *A. faecalis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *E. coli* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *S. enterica* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *S. aureus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *B. subtilis* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), non-template control (NTC) for PC2 (resulted in pink solution).

The specificity assays for the products of the PC2 primer set, obtained through both the Real Time LAMP and Colorimetric LAMP approaches, were subsequently confirmed using agarose gel electrophoresis (Figures 32–33).

Figure 32. Agarose gel electrophoresis of products from Real Time LAMP reaction for assessing the specificity of PC2 for *K. aerogenes*.

Figure 33. Agarose gel electrophoresis of products from Colorimetric LAMP reaction for assessing the specificity of PC2 for *K. aerogenes*.

4.1.3.3 LAMP assay sensitivity

The results indicating the detection limit of developed LAMP assay are presented in Graphs 6-8 for Real Time LAMP, and in Figure 34 for the Colorimetric LAMP method.

Graph 6 illustrates the outcomes of the assessment of the Real Time LAMP limit of detection (LOD) for *K. aerogenes*, employing the PC2 primer set.

Graph 6. Assessment of the Real Time LAMP limit of detection for *K. aerogenes* using primer set PC2. Used dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA: 59.9 ng/μL (red curve), 59.9×10^{-1} ng/μL (orange curve), 59.9×10^{-2} ng/μL (yellow curve), 59.9×10^{-3} ng/μL (light green curve), 59.9×10^{-4} ng/μL (dark green curve), 59.9×10^{-5} ng/μL (light blue curve), 59.9×10^{-6} ng/μL (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The determined LOD corresponds to a dilution of 10^{-4} (dark green curve), equivalent to a *K. aerogenes* gDNA concentration of 59.9×10^{-4} ng/μL. Hence, at a concentration of 2.4×10^{-4} ng/μL in LAMP reaction (for reaction volume of 25 μL), the LOD for the PC2 primer candidate is determined to be 240 fg/μL.

Additionally, in Graph 6 it is notable that the signals for the dilution series occur at regular time intervals. Additionally, the amount of product decreases towards the lowest concentration, aligning with the higher T_t values for these samples (Graph 7).

Graph 7. Tt values of Real Time LAMP for various tested concentrations of *K. aerogenes* gDNA using PC2. The graph represents only amplified dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA: 59.9 ng/μL (red bar), 59.9×10^{-1} ng/μL (orange bar), 59.9×10^{-2} ng/μL (yellow bar), 59.9×10^{-3} ng/μL (light green bar), 59.9×10^{-4} ng/μL (dark green bar).

Graph 8 indicates that the amplification is specific, since melting curves of amplified dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA overlap with the positive control (Graph 8).

Graph 8. Assessing the Real Time LAMP limit of detection for *K. aerogenes* using primer set PC2 – melting curves. Used dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA: 59.9 ng/μL (red curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (orange curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻² ng/μL (yellow curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻³ ng/μL (light green curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (dark green curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻⁵ ng/μL (light blue curve), 59.9 ng/μL × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The results of determining the LOD of the *K. aerogenes* species using the Colorimetric LAMP approach are presented in Figure 34.

Figure 34. The Colorimetric LAMP limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using the PC2 primer set and following dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA: 59.9 ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), 59.9 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), 59.9 × 10⁻² ng/μL (resulted in yellow-to-orange solution), 59.9 × 10⁻³ ng/μL (resulted in pink solution), 59.9 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (resulted in pink solution), 59.9 × 10⁻⁵ ng/μL (resulted in pink solution), 59.9 × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL (resulted in pink solution), NTC – non-template control (resulted in pink solution).

The determined LOD corresponds to a dilution of 10⁻², equivalent to a concentration containing 59.9 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA. Hence, at a concentration of 2.4 × 10⁻² ng/μL, corresponding to a volume of 25 μL, the LOD for the PC2 primer candidate is determined to be 24 pg/μL.

4.1.4 *K. aerogenes* detection in spiked food samples

Results presented in the following section pertain to the evaluation of the effect of DNA isolation from food samples (vegetable and meat) using Chelex 100 and a commercial DNA isolation kit (adapted for each type of sample) on LAMP reaction performance and the detection of *K. aerogenes* in spiked DNA extracts.

Firstly, gDNA isolates obtained from bacterial cultures grown from the food samples (vegetables and meat) were screened for the *K. aerogenes* contamination (see *Section 4.1.4.1*). Next, food DNA extracts spiked with different dilutions of *K. aerogenes* gDNA were used to evaluate developed LAMP assay for *K. aerogenes* detection (see *Section 4.1.4.2*).

4.1.4.1 Testing food samples for *K. aerogenes* contamination

The Real Time LAMP results of testing gDNA samples, which were derived from bacterial cultures cultivated from different food samples, for *K. aerogenes* contamination are presented in Graphs 9 and 10 for vegetable material and 11 and 12 for meat and meat products, respectively. In both cases, *K. aerogenes* gDNA was exclusively detected in the positive controls (red curve), confirming that neither vegetable nor meat samples were naturally contaminated with this bacterium.

The Real Time LAMP results for testing gDNA samples, which were derived from various food sample extracts for *K. aerogenes* contamination, are presented in Graphs 9 and 10 for vegetable materials and in Graphs 11 and 12 for meat and meat products, respectively.

Graph 9. Real Time LAMP amplification graph: Results obtained using gDNA isolates derived from bacterial cultures cultivated from different vegetable samples. Red curve – positive control, i.e. *K. aerogenes* gDNA, orange curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from carrot, green curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from lettuce, blue curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from cucumber, pink curve – non-templet control for PC2 (NTC).

Graph 10. Real Time LAMP melting curves for gDNA isolates derived from bacterial cultures cultivated from different vegetable samples. Red curve – positive control, i.e. *K. aerogenes* gDNA, orange curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from carrot, green curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from lettuce, blue curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from cucumber, pink curve – non-templet control for PC2 (NTC).

Graph 11. Real Time LAMP amplification graph: Results obtained using gDNA isolates derived from bacterial cultures cultivated from different meat samples. Red curve – positive control, i.e. *K. aerogenes* gDNA, yellow curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from chicken breasts, green curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from salami, dark blue curve – non-templet control for PC2 (NTC).

Graph 12. Real Time LAMP melting curves for gDNA isolates derived from bacterial cultures cultivated from different meat samples. Red curve – positive control, i.e. *K. aerogenes* gDNA, yellow curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from chicken breasts, green curve – gDNA isolate obtained from bacterial cultures grown from salami, dark blue curve – non-templet control for PC2 (NTC).

The results of biochemical tests for microbial identification indicated that there was no *K. aerogenes* present in any of the tested food samples (Supplementary Table 1).

4.1.4.2 Testing the effect of DNA isolation on K. aerogenes detection using LAMP

The results of *K. aerogenes* detection using Real Time LAMP reaction for samples isolated using the Chelex 100 method are illustrated in Graphs 13–23 and Table 13, while those obtained for samples isolated with the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit are presented in Graphs 24–30 and Table 14. Additionally, Graphs 31–35 and Table 15 showcase the results for samples isolated using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit.

DNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method

The Real Time LAMP reaction results indicate that the limit of detection (LOD) for *K. aerogenes* gDNA in food DNA extracts obtained using the Chelex 100 method and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dilution 10^{-2} , depicted by the light green curve in Graphs 13, 15, 17, 19, 21) was consistent across all three vegetable samples (carrot, cucumber, lettuce) and both tested

meat samples (chicken breasts and salami). This finding, equivalent to 0.4 pg/μL of , highlights the method's effectiveness.

Graphs 14, 16, 18, 20 and 22 reveals that the melting curve values for all tested samples (orange, yellow, and green curves) where amplification occurred are within the range of positive control values (red curve), indicating specific amplification.

Graph 13. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for the limit of detection determination for *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked carrot DNA extract samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method. Used templates: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), carrot gDNA extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻³ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure carrot DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 14. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked carrot DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), carrot extract DNA spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure carrot DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 15. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked cucumber DNA extract samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), cucumber extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure cucumber DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 16. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked cucumber DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (red curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure cucumber DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 17. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked lettuce DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure lettuce DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 18. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked lettuce DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), lettuce extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure lettuce DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 19. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked chicken breast DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure chicken breast DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 20. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked chicken breast DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure chicken breast DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 21. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked salami DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure salami DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 22. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in salami DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure salami DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The Graph 23 indicates that comparable Tt values with no statistically significant difference were observed for lettuce, cucumber, carrot and salami DNA samples across all three detected concentrations, with the most diluted samples requiring approximately 23-28 min to detect. In contrast, chicken breasts DNA samples exhibited the longest Tt values, taking more than 29 min for the most diluted sample. Statistically significant differences were observed between the largest dilution of lettuce and chicken breasts, as well as between the largest dilution of chicken breasts and salami (with $p < 0.05$) (Table 15).

Graph 23. Comparison of Tt values for various food DNA extracts extracted using Chelex 100 method and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA. The Graph summarized only amplified dilutions: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control for various food extracts, food extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, food extracts spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, food extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA.

Table 15. Results of the statistical analysis of the differences in Tt values recorded for all tested food DNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 approach.

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
59.9 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Carrot 59.9 vs. Cucumber 59.9	1.567	-1.703 to 4.837	No	ns	0.5066
	Carrot 59.9 vs. Lettuce 59.9	2.083	-1.187 to 5.353	No	ns	0.2696
	Carrot 59.9 vs. Chicken breasts 59.9	-0.075	-3.731 to 3.581	No	ns	>0.9999
	Carrot 59.9 vs. Salami 59.9	-0.575	-4.231 to 3.081	No	ns	0.9798
	Cucumber 59.9 vs. Lettuce 59.9	0.5167	-2.753 to 3.787	No	ns	0.9794
	Cucumber 59.9 vs. Chicken breasts 59.9	-1.642	-5.298 to 2.014	No	ns	0.5616
	Cucumber 59.9 vs. Salami 59.9	-2.142	-5.798 to 1.514	No	ns	0.3353
	Lettuce 59.9 vs. Chicken breasts 59.9	-2.158	-5.814 to 1.498	No	ns	0.329
	Lettuce 59.9 vs. Salami 59.9	-2.658	-6.314 to 0.9976	No	ns	0.1801
	Chicken breasts 59.9 vs. Salami 59.9	-0.5	-4.505 to 3.505	No	ns	0.9914
food DNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Carrot 1 vs. Cucumber 1	1.383	-1.342 to 4.109	No	ns	0.4567
	Carrot 1 vs. Lettuce 1	1.2	-1.525 to 3.925	No	ns	0.5779
	Carrot 1 vs. Chicken breasts 1	0.7917	-2.255 to 3.839	No	ns	0.8901
	Carrot 1 vs. Salami 1	1.292	-1.755 to 4.339	No	ns	0.6088
	Cucumber 1 vs. Lettuce 1	-0.1833	-2.909 to 2.542	No	ns	0.9992
	Cucumber 1 vs. Chicken breasts 1	-0.5917	-3.639 to 2.455	No	ns	0.9575
	Cucumber 1 vs. Salami 1	-0.09167	-3.139 to 2.955	No	ns	>0.9999
	Lettuce 1 vs. Chicken breasts 1	-0.4083	-3.455 to 2.639	No	ns	0.9888
	Lettuce 1 vs. Salami 1	0.09167	-2.955 to 3.139	No	ns	>0.9999
	Chicken breasts 1 vs. Salami 1	0.5	-2.838 to 3.838	No	ns	0.9831
food DNA extracts	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻¹	1.617	-1.177 to 4.411	No	ns	0.3454
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻¹	1.9	-0.8941 to 4.694	No	ns	0.223
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻¹	0.4667	-2.657 to 3.591	No	ns	0.9832
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻¹	3.042	-0.08229 to 6.166	No	ns	0.0566

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
spiked with 1 x 10⁻¹ ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻¹	0.2833	-2.511 to 3.077	No	ns	0.9961
	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻¹	-1.15	-4.274 to 1.974	No	ns	0.7141
	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻¹	1.425	-1.699 to 4.549	No	ns	0.5484
	Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻¹	-1.433	-4.557 to 1.691	No	ns	0.5434
	Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻¹	1.142	-1.982 to 4.266	No	ns	0.719
	Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻¹	2.575	-0.8471 to 5.997	No	ns	0.1603
food DNA extracts spiked with 1 x 10⁻² ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻²	2.733	-2.126 to 7.593	No	ns	0.3689
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻²	4.317	-0.5425 to 9.176	No	ns	0.0847
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻²	-1.317	-6.749 to 4.116	No	ns	0.9115
	Carrot 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻²	5.408	-0.02439 to 10.84	No	ns	0.0511
	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻²	1.583	-3.276 to 6.443	No	ns	0.7898
	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻²	-4.05	-9.483 to 1.383	No	ns	0.1655
	Cucumber 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻²	2.675	-2.758 to 8.108	No	ns	0.483
	Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻²	-5.633	-11.07 to -0.2006	Yes	*	0.0421
	Lettuce 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻²	1.092	-4.341 to 6.524	No	ns	0.9522
	Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻²	6.725	0.7738 to 12.68	Yes	*	0.0273

ns – not significant; * – significance level of p < 0.05

DNA samples obtained using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit

Considering that positive Real Time LAMP reaction for *K. aerogenes* was obtained for the sample containing the highest tested concentration of *K. aerogenes* in spiked carrot DNA extract (1 ng/μL) (orange curve on Graph 24), the estimated detection limit for bacterial gDNA in carrot DNA extract is 40 pg/μL. Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified sample that overlaps with melting peak of positive control (Graph 25).

Graph 24. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked carrot DNA extract samples obtained using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure carrot DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 25. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in carrot DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), carrot DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure carrot DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

For cucumber samples, the LAMP reaction results indicated that none of the extracts obtained through isolation with the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit, spiked with the lowest concentrations of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, were detectable. Graph 26 represents the only replicate where the 10^{-1} dilution was detected (yellow curve), although in this replicate there was no amplification for the cucumber extract containing 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA. Considering all this, it is assumed that detection limit for *K. aerogenes* gDNA in the cucumber extract isolated by this kit ranges between 40-400 pg/μL. Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified sample that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 27).

Graph 26. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked cucumber DNA extract samples obtained using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit and by using following templates: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure cucumber DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 27. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked cucumber DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), cucumber DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure cucumber DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The detection limit of bacterial gDNA in the lettuce DNA extract isolated by Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit is 40 pg/μL, as only a dilution of lettuce extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA was detected (Graph 28). Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified sample that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 29).

Graph 28. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked lettuce DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure lettuce DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 29. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked DNA lettuce extract samples obtained through isolation using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), lettuce DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure lettuce DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 30 illustrates a comparison of the Tt values in the tested vegetable DNA extracts obtained using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA. Observations indicate that the Tt values for 1 ng/μL gDNA of *K. aerogenes* in carrot and lettuce DNA extracts were similar, showing no statistically significant differences (Table 16), with values ranging between 23 and 26 minutes. When testing the same concentration in cucumber extract, no amplification was observed. For cucumber, amplification was observed at a dilution of 10⁻¹, with a Tt recorded at 29 minute, while no amplification was observed at this concentration for carrot and lettuce samples.

Graph 30. Comparison of Tt values for various vegetable DNA extracts extracted using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA. The graph summarized only amplified dilutions: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μL as a positive control for various vegetable DNA extracts, vegetable extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, vegetable extracts spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, vegetable extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA.

Table 16. Results of the statistical analysis of the differences in Tt values recorded for vegetable DNA samples obtained using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit.

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
59.9 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Carrot 59.9 vs. Cucumber 59.9	0.905	-5.083 to 6.893	No	ns	0.8146
	Carrot 59.9 vs. Lettuce 59.9	-1.425	-7.413 to 4.563	No	ns	0.6287
	Cucumber 59.9 vs. Lettuce 59.9	-2.33	-8.318 to 3.658	No	ns	0.3624
vegetable DNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Carrot 1 vs. Lettuce 1	0.075	-7.672 to 7.822	No	ns	0.9991

ns – not significant

DNA samples obtained using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit

The Real Time LAMP reaction results indicate that the limit of detection (LOD) for *K. aerogenes* gDNA in DNA extracts obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit was 10^{-2} dilution, (depicted by the green curve in Graphs 31 and 33) for both chicken breast and salami isolates, establishing the detection limit at 0.4 pg/ μ L.

Graphs 32 and 34 reveal that the melting curve values for all amplified dilutions fall within the range of the positive control value (red curve), indicating specific amplification.

Graph 31. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked chicken breast DNA extract samples obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. Following templates were used for Real Time LAMP reaction: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (red curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), chicken breast extract DNA spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), chicken breast extract DNA spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure chicken breast DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 32. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked chicken breast DNA extract samples obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. Following templates were used for Real Time LAMP reaction: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), chicken breast DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), chicken breast extract DNA spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), chicken breast extract DNA spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), pure chicken breast DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 33. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in spiked salami DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. Following templates were used for Real Time LAMP reaction: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), salami extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), salami DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 34. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining of the limit of detection of *K. aerogenes* using PC2 primer set in salami DNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. Following templates were used for Real Time LAMP reaction: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), salami extract spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (orange curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (yellow curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (dark green curve), salami DNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA (light blue curve), salami DNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 35 presents a comparison of the Tt values for the tested food DNA extracts obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA. The Graph indicates that similar values, with no significant differences (Table 17) were observed for both chicken breast and salami extracts across all three detected concentrations, with the most diluted samples requiring approximately 23.30–25.30 min for detection.

Graph 35. Comparison of Tt values for various meat DNA extracts extracted using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit and spiked with *K. aerogenes* gDNA. The Graph summarized only amplified dilutions: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control for various meat DNA extracts, meat extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, meat extracts spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, meat extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *K. aerogenes* gDNA.

Table 17. Results of the statistical analysis of the differences in Tt values recorded for meat DNA samples obtained using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit.

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
59.9 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Chicken breasts 59.9 vs. Salami 59.9	0.225	-4.607 to 5.057	No	ns	0.9795
meat DNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Chicken breasts 1 vs. Salami 1	0.8	-2.017 to 3.617	No	ns	0.6502
meat DNA extracts spiked with 1 x 10⁻¹ ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻¹	-1.867	-5.066 to 1.333	No	ns	0.2027
meat DNA extracts spiked with 1 x 10⁻² ng/μL of <i>K. aerogenes</i> gDNA	Chicken breasts 1 x 10 ⁻² vs. Salami 1 x 10 ⁻²	-0.3	-4.072 to 3.472	No	ns	0.9572

ns – not significant

4.1.5 *K. aerogenes* detection in inoculated samples

Real Time LAMP detection of *K. aerogenes* was performed in different food samples (vegetables and meat) inoculated with a *K. aerogenes* bacterial suspension. The DNA extraction from inoculated food samples was performed using both, laboratory intensive kit-based methods and field applicable Chelex 100 method. The effect of applied DNA isolation approach on Real Time LAMP for *K. aerogenes* detection was assessed and these results were compared with the results of Real Time PCR (Section 4.1.6). Prior to analysis DNA concentrations were adjusted to 1 ng/μL, and the DNA isolates were then analyzed in Real Time LAMP reactions. The results are presented in Graphs 36–39 for the Chelex 100 method, Graphs 40–41 for the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit, and Graphs 42–43 for the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit.

4.1.5.1 DNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method

For vegetable DNA samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method, a positive result of the Real Time LAMP for *K. aerogenes* was observed in inoculated carrot, with an amplification curve around the 29th minute (orange curve), and in inoculated lettuce, with a amplification curve around the 26th minute (green curve) (Graph 36). Conversely, no amplification occurred in the DNA sample of inoculated cucumber. Additionally, in the control samples, i.e., pure vegetable DNA extracts that were not purposefully contaminated, no positive reaction was detected. Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange and green curves) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 37).

Graph 36. Amplification graph of the Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light blue curve), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 37. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light blue curve), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

For meat DNA extract samples isolated using the Chelex 100 method, a positive Real Time LAMP reaction for *K. aerogenes* was observed in both tested samples - chicken breast and chicken salami - around the 16th minute, as indicated by the orange and green curves in Graph 38. In the control, i.e., pure meat extracts without intentional contamination, no positive reaction was detected. Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange and green curves) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 39).

Graph 38. Amplification graph of the Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated meat samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), salami DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve) NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 39. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of inoculated meat samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), salami DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve) NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

4.1.5.2 DNA samples obtained using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit

The following results show the outcomes of the Real Time LAMP reaction with inoculated vegetable samples isolated using the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit.

All three inoculated vegetable samples exhibited positive results of the Real Time LAMP for *K. aerogenes* detection, with amplification curves around minute 22nd for inoculated carrot and lettuce (represented by orange and green curves) and around minute 27th for inoculated cucumber (light blue curve) (Graph 40). In the internal control samples, i.e., pure vegetable DNA extracts from vegetable samples that were not intentionally inoculated with bacterial suspension, no positive reaction occurred.

Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange, green, and light blue curves) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 41).

Graph 40. Amplification graph of Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated vegetable samples isolated by Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light blue curve), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 41. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated vegetable samples isolated by Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light blue curve), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

4.1.5.3 DNA samples obtained using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit

The following results show the outcomes of the Real Time LAMP reaction with inoculated meat samples isolated using the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit.

Both meat samples exhibited positive *K. aerogenes* Real Time LAMP results within Tt around 17 min for chicken salami and around 18th min for chicken breasts (represented by orange and green curves, respectively) (Graph 42).

In the internal control samples, i.e., 'pure' meat extracts that were not intentionally inoculated, no positive reaction occurred. Specificity of the reaction was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange and green curves) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 43).

Graph 42. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated meat samples isolated by using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), salami DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve) NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 43. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated meat samples isolated by using DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (orange curve), chicken breast DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (yellow curve), 1 ng/μL of DNA extracts from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (light green curve), salami DNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve) NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

4.1.6 Real Time PCR assay

Graphs 44 and 45 display the results of Real Time PCR analysis conducted on DNA extracts of inoculated vegetable samples isolated using the Chelex 100 method.

The first graph illustrates positive results of the Real Time PCR reaction for the positive control (blue curve (A)) and for all targeted contaminated samples, including inoculated carrot DNA extract (B) with black and red curves, inoculated lettuce DNA extract (C) with dark green and pink curves, and inoculated cucumber extract (D) with dark blue and turquoise curves.

A positive results for inoculated samples are observed after the 25th cycle (Graph 44), equivalent to an hour of reaction time (Graph 45).

Graph 44. Real Time PCR Analysis for DNA extracts of inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method: amplification curve in relation to cycle number. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (blue curve, A), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (black and red curves, B), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (dark green and pink curves, C), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (dark blue and turquoise curves, D). Negative controls included carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated), and NTC (non-template control).

Graph 45. Real Time PCR Analysis for DNA extracts of inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method: amplification curve in relation to reaction time. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (blue curve, A), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (black and red curves, B), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (dark green and pink curves, C), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extract from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (dark blue and turquoise curves, D). Negative controls included carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated), and NTC (non-template control).

The results of the Real Time PCR analysis of the DNA extract from vegetable samples obtained using Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit were positive only for the positive control (blue curve in Graphs 46 and 47). In Graph 47, the positive control curve appears after the 30th minute.

Graph 46. Real Time PCR analysis for DNA extracts of inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit: amplification curve in relation to cycle number. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (blue curve, A), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified). Negative controls included carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated), and NTC (non-template control).

Graph 47. Real Time PCR analysis for DNA extracts of inoculated vegetable samples isolated by the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit: multiplication curve in relation to reaction time. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/ μ L as a positive control (blue curve, A), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from carrot sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from lettuce sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified), 1 ng/ μ L of DNA extracts from cucumber sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension (not amplified). Negative controls included carrot DNA extract (non-inoculated), lettuce DNA extract (non-inoculated), cucumber DNA extract (non-inoculated), and NTC (non-template control).

Results of Real Time PCR analysis of DNA extracts from meat samples obtained using both Chelex 100 and DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit are presented in Graphs 48 and 49. In Graph 49, it can be seen that the positive control curve appears after the 30th minute (A), which is 15

min longer than the time required for a positive result of the same sample in the Real Time LAMP reaction. Additionally, a positive reaction occurred only in spiked meat samples from which DNA was extracted using a commercial kit (B, C).

Graph 48. Real Time PCR analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated meat samples isolated using Chelex 100 and DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit: amplification curve in relation to cycle number. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (blue curve, (A)), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* and extracted using commercial kit (orange curve (B)), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension and extracted using commercial kit (green curve C), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* and extracted using Chelex 100 method (not amplified), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension and extracted using Chelex 100 method (not amplified). Negative controls included non-inoculated chicken breast and salami samples extracted using both the commercial kit and the Chelex 100 method, as well as a non-template control (NTC).

Graph 49. Real Time PCR analysis of DNA extracts from inoculated meat samples isolated by Chelex 100 and DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit: amplification curve in relation to reaction time. The following templates were used: gDNA of *K. aerogenes* 59.9 ng/μL as a positive control (blue curve, A), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* and extracted using commercial kit (orange curve, B), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension and extracted using commercial kit (green curve, C), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from salami sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* and extracted using Chelex 100 method (not amplified), 1 ng/μL of DNA extract from chicken breast sample inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension and extracted using Chelex 100 method (not amplified). Negative controls included non-inoculated chicken breast and salami samples extracted using both the commercial kit and the Chelex 100 method, as well as a non-template control (NTC).

Table 18 summarizes the efficiency of Real Time LAMP assay compared to the Real Time PCR in the context of tested sample type, DNA extraction method, and analysis time.

Table 18. Comparison of efficiency of *K. aerogenes* detection between Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR for tested food samples. The first number under “Time of analysis (estimated)” indicates the time needed for DNA extraction, while the second number indicates the time needed for analysis (Real Time LAMP or Real Time PCR).

Chelex 100						
Real Time LAMP assay				Real Time PCR assay		
Type of sample	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)
Vegetables	2/3	66.67%	30 + 30 min	3/3	100%	30 + 75 min
Meat	2/2	100%	35 + 30 min	0/2	Not efficient	35 + 75 min
Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit						
Real Time LAMP assay				Real Time PCR assay		
Type of sample	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)
Vegetables	3/3	100%	120 + 30 min	0/3	Not efficient	120 + 75 min
DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit						
Real Time LAMP assay				Real Time PCR assay		
Type of sample	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)	No. of positives	Efficiency	Time of analysis (estimated)
Meat	2/2	100%	150 + 30 min	2/2	100%	150 + 75

The table clearly indicates that when the Chelex 100 method was employed as an extraction method for tested vegetable food samples, Real Time LAMP exhibited an efficiency of 66.67%, whereas Real Time PCR achieved 100% detection efficiency. Conversely, for meat samples, Real Time PCR showed no effectiveness, while Real Time LAMP demonstrated 100% effectiveness.

However, with the use of commercial isolation kits for DNA extraction in food samples (Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit and DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit), LAMP showed 100% efficiency for both vegetable and meat samples, while Real Time PCR was ineffective for vegetable samples. In all cases, LAMP exhibited a significantly shorter analysis time.

4.2 Development of a LAMP-based detection of *Trichoderma* spp. detection in champignon production

The results presented in this section pertain to all experiments described in *Section 3.2*. The first part of *Section 4.2* presents the results of DNA extraction from fungal cultures used in all further experiments (see *Section 4.2.1.1*) The next part presents the results of DNA extraction from real compost and casing soil samples collected in mushroom nurseries during one production process, isolated using two different approaches: laboratory and field applicable (see *Section 4.2.1.2*). This section also shows the results of DNA extraction from artificially contaminated compost and casing soil samples using the same extraction principles as for the real samples. This was done to evaluate the efficiency of the DNA extraction method optimized within this dissertation for field application and to consider the further application of such DNA extracts in fungal pathogen detection using the LAMP assay.

4.2.1 Concentration and purity of DNA

Concentration and purity of DNA isolated for the experiments with *Trichoderma* spp. are presented in Tables 19-21.

4.2.1.1 Fungal cultures

Table 19 represents the concentration values of gDNA isolated from fungal cultures. This isolation was conducted to assess the specificity of the PC2 primer set (see *Section 4.2.2*, Table 22), adhering to the methodologies described in *Section 3.2.2.1*.

Table 19. Concentration and purity of gDNA from different fungal cultures.

Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
<i>Aspergillus carbonarius</i>	74.29	1.77	1.21
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	10.97	1.77	1.20
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	28.67	2.09	1.69
<i>Penicillium halotolerans</i>	40.48	1.85	0.90
<i>Cladosporium allicinum</i>	18.66	1.85	1.20
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	229.31	1.88	1.78

4.2.1.2 Compost and casing soil

Table 20 represents the concentration values of eDNA isolated from the real compost and casing soil samples (see Section 3.2.1.2).

Table 20. Concentration and purity of eDNA isolated from compost/casing soil samples using Chelex 100 method and GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kit.

eDNA extraction – Chelex 100 method			
Sample	eDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
Compost K1	35.56	1.3	0.54
Compost K7	13.55	1.95	0.42
Compost K7#	13.78	1.99	0.35
Compost K10	22.52	1.48	0.47
Compost K10*	20.18	1.51	0.86
Compost K10#	44.11	1.24	0.59
Casing soil P3	71.87	1.78	0.65
Casing soil P9	46.42	2.53	0.50
Casing soil P10	4.44	2.99	0.57

eDNA extraction using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit			
Sample	eDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀	A₂₆₀/A₂₃₀
Compost K1	23.81	2.16	1.03
Compost K7	53.79	2.14	0.65
Compost K7#	9.91	2.07	0.83
Compost K10	43.85	2.26	1.75
Compost K10*	21.85	1.97	0.65
Compost K10#	8.24	1.68	0.84
Casing soil P3	4.20	3.19	1.17
Casing soil P9	16.81	2.40	0.55
Casing soil P10	12.26	2.26	0.48

The concentration values of compost and casing soil eDNA extracts, isolated with both the Chelex 100 method and the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, exhibited similar concentration ranges. Specifically, the concentration values of compost and casing soil eDNA extracts isolated using the Chelex 100 method ranged from 4.44 ng/μL to 71.87 ng/μL. On the other hand, the concentration values of compost and casing soil eDNA extracts isolated with the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit ranged from 4.20 ng/μL to 53.79 ng/μL.

The absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} for compost eDNA extracts labelled as K1, K10, K10*, and K10# obtained using the Chelex 100 method was found to be lower than the recommended lower reference value, i.e., below 1.7. This suggests the presence of a significant amount of protein, phenolic compounds, and other contaminants, which exhibit an absorption maximum at 280 nm.

For two casing soil eDNA extracts isolated with the Chelex 100 method (P9 and P10), the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} was higher than the recommended upper reference value, i.e., above 1.9.

For all other compost extracts (K7 and K7#) and one casing soil extract (P3), the A_{260}/A_{280} ratio was within the range of reference values.

For all tested compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained using the Chelex 100 method, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{230} was consistently lower than the recommended lower reference value, i.e., below 2.0. The values for both, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts ranged from 0.35 to 0.86.

For all compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} was around 2.0, except for P3 and K10#, where it was 3.19 and 1.68, respectively.

For all tested compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{230} was consistently lower than the lower reference value, i.e., below 2.0. The values for both compost and casing soil eDNA extracts ranged from 0.48 to 1.75.

Table 21 represents the concentration values of eDNA isolated from inoculated compost/casing soil samples.

Table 21. Concentration and purity of eDNA isolated for experiments with inoculated compost/casing soil samples using Chelex 100 method and GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kit.

eDNA extraction – Chelex 100 method			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A_{260}/A_{280}	A_{260}/A_{230}
Compost + <i>T. harzianum</i>	58.63	1.21	0.49
Casing soil + <i>T. harzianum</i>	13.17	1.01	0.75
Compost	30.26	1.11	0.38
Casing soil	7.03	1.33	0.64
eDNA extraction using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit			
Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A_{260}/A_{280}	A_{260}/A_{230}
Compost + <i>Trichoderma</i> spp.	73.24	1.70	0.48
Casing soil + <i>Trichoderma</i> spp.	17.37	1.73	0.63
Compost	42.01	1.61	0.44
Casing soil	15.10	1.77	0.40

The concentration of eDNA extracts from compost and casing soil samples, artificially contaminated with fungal culture and obtained using Chelex 100 isolation method, ranged from 7.03 ng/ μ L to 58.63 ng/ μ L. The concentration values of eDNA extracts obtained using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, including both inoculated and non-inoculated compost and casing soil extracts, ranged from 15.10 ng/ μ L to 73.24 ng/ μ L.

For both, eDNA extracts from inoculated and not-artificially contaminated samples, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} was consistently below 1.70 in samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method, indicating values lower than the lower reference threshold. The A_{260}/A_{280} absorbance ratio for samples obtained using Chelex 100 method ranged from 0.38 to 0.75. Consequently, for all samples, the A_{260}/A_{230} ratio values were below 2.0, indicating values lower than the specified lower reference threshold.

For eDNA samples obtained using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit, the A_{260}/A_{280} absorbance ratio values did not vary significantly among the samples. The A_{260}/A_{280} ratio values were around 1.70, except for the non-inoculated compost extract, which measured 1.61. The A_{260}/A_{230} absorbance ratio values for the eDNA samples obtained using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit ranged from 0.40 to 0.63. Consequently, for all samples, the A_{260}/A_{230} ratio values were below the lower reference threshold.

4.2.2 LAMP primers for *Trichoderma* spp.

The results of the LAMP primer design for the detection of *Trichoderma* spp. are described in the following section, representing the selection of an adequate candidate primer. The specificity of the selected primer was further tested, and its limit of detection (LOD) was determined (see *Section 4.2.3*).

The BLAST analyses results have indicated that the sequence of the *tefl* gene (GeneBank OL435125), used for LAMP primer design, shows significant similarity with the *tefl* gene of different *Trichoderma* spp. In total, 99 sequences of *Trichoderma tefl* gene were found. Notably, 41 of these sequences belong to *T. harzianum*, with the majority displaying high query coverage values (over 96%) and percentage identity values within the range of 97.33% to 100%.

In addition to *T. harzianum*, 25 sequences were identified at the genus level only (*Trichoderma* spp.), while 33 sequences originated from 7 other *Trichoderma* species: *T. auriculariae*, *T. xixiacum*, *T. vermifimicola*, *T. simmonsii*, *T. pollinicola*, *T. lentinulae*, and *T. endophyticum*. It

is noteworthy that all non-*T. harzianum* sequences exhibited high query coverage values (ranging from 92% to 99%) and identity percent falling within the range of 97.72% to 99.84%.

Designed primer sequences and their relative positions on the *Trichoderma* spp. *tef1* gene are shown in Table 22 and Figures 35–36.

Table 22. LAMP primers for *Trichoderma* spp. *tef1* gene designed *de novo*.

Primer candidate (PC)	Primer name	Sequence 5'-3'	Position	Length
PC1-<i>tef1</i>	PC1-F3	CCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAC	846-864	19
	PC1-B3	CTTGACTTCAGTGGTGACGT	1054-1073	20
	PC1-FIP (F2+F1c)	GAAGACGGAGGGGCTTGTCC-AAGACCCTCCTTGAGGCTAT	N.A.	40
	PC1-BIP (B2+B1c)	TATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCG C-GCGAAGGTGACGACCATAC	N.A.	41
	PC1-LF	TTGGGGGGCTCGATGGA	903-919	17
	PC1-LB	CGTATCGAGACTGGTGTCCCT	999-1018	20
PC2-<i>tef1</i>	PC2-F3	GTATGGTCGTCACCTTCGC	1027-1045	19
	PC2-B3	GGGTGGTTCATGACGATGAC	1233-1252	20
	PC2-FIP (F2+F1c)	AACACCCTCGACGAGCTGCT-CCTCCAACGTCACCACTGA	N.A.	39
	PC2-BIP (B2+B1c)	AATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGC C-GAAAGAAGCGGCACCCAT	N.A.	40
	PC2-LF	GGTGCATCTCGACGGACTT	1071-1089	19
	PC2-LB	TGACTCCAAGAACGACCCC	1182-1201	19

Figure 35. Schematic illustration of *tef1* gene showing positions and directions for LAMP primer candidate set 1 (PC1).

Figure 36. Schematic illustration of *tef1* gene showing positions and directions for LAMP primer candidate set 2 (PC2).

4.2.3 Optimization of LAMP assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection

Results from primer testing revealed that a reaction time of 30 min consistently produced positive and stable outcomes. This optimal timeframe was then applied across all subsequent LAMP reactions.

4.2.3.1 Evaluation of LAMP primer sets

The results from testing the LAMP primer candidates are depicted in Graphs 50-52.

The amplification curve for primer candidate PC2 (dark blue curve) emerges first, with a Tt of approximately 17 min, while the amplification curve for PC1 (red) becomes visible after 30 min. There were no false positives in all tested non-template controls (PC1 NTC and PC2 NTC).

Due to the shorter reaction time exhibited by candidate PC2 (Graph 51), it was selected for further subsequent experimental work in optimizing the LAMP method for detecting *Trichoderma* spp.

After the Real Time LAMP reaction, during which the primer candidates were tested, the melting curves depicted in Graph 52 were obtained.

Graph 52. Real Time LAMP melting curve for testing primer candidates for *Trichoderma* spp. detection using *T. harzianum* gDNA as a template for positive controls and PCR-grade water for non-template controls (NTCs) for each primer candidate (PC). The graph includes following curves: amplification with PC1 (red curve), PC1 NTC – non-template control for PC1 (light green curve), PC2 NTC – non-template control for PC2 (light blue curve), and amplification with PC2 (dark blue curve).

4.2.3.2 Evaluation of PC2 specificity

The results of the evaluation of PC2 specificity obtained by the Real Time and Colorimetric LAMP methods are shown in Graphs 53–54, and Figure 37 respectively.

The results from Graph 53 indicate that a positive result was observed only for *Trichoderma* spp. (red curve in the Graph).

Graph 53. Amplification graph for assessing the specificity of PC2 set for *Trichoderma* spp. amplification using the Real Time LAMP method with the following templates: *T. harzianum* gDNA for specific reaction (red curve), *A. carbonarius* gDNA for non-specific reaction (orange curve), *A. fumigatus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (yellow curve), *A. alternata* gDNA for non-specific reaction (light green curve), *P. halotolerans* gDNA for non-specific reaction (dark green curve), *C. allicinum* gDNA for non-specific reaction (blue curve), and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

Based on the results presented in Graph 54 and the characteristic shape of the melting curve in the sample where amplification occurred the specificity of the PC2 primer set has been validated.

Graph 54. Melting curve for assessing the specificity of PC2 set for *Trichoderma* spp. amplification using the Real Time LAMP method with the following templates: *T. harzianum* gDNA for specific reaction (red curve), *A. carbonarius* gDNA for non-specific reaction (orange curve), *A. fumigatus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (yellow curve), *A. alternata* gDNA for non-specific reaction (light green curve), *P. halotolerans* gDNA for non-specific reaction (dark green curve), *C. allicinum* gDNA for non-specific reaction (blue curve), and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

The assessment of the PC2 primer set's specificity was additionally conducted by applying Colorimetric LAMP method. The results, as illustrated in Figure 37, indicated a positive reaction exclusively for the *T. harzianum* sample after 30 min, characterized by the transition of the indicator colour from pink to yellow.

Figure 37. Confirmation of the specificity of the PC2 primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. amplification using the Colorimetric LAMP method with the following templates: *T. harzianum* gDNA for specific reaction (resulted in yellow solution), *A. carbonarius* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *A. fumigatus* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *A. alternata* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *P. halotolerans* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), *C. allicinum* gDNA for non-specific reaction (resulted in pink solution), NTC – non-template control for PC2 (resulted in pink solution).

The specificity assays for the products of the PC2 primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. obtained through both, the Real Time LAMP and Colorimetric LAMP approaches, were subsequently confirmed using agarose gel electrophoresis (Figures 38–39).

Figure 38. Agarose gel electrophoresis of products from Real Time LAMP reaction for assessing the specificity of PC2 for detection of *Trichoderma* species.

Figure 39. Agarose gel electrophoresis of products from Colorimetric LAMP reaction for assessing the specificity of PC2 for detection of *Trichoderma* species.

Additionally, *in silico* analysis confirmed the genus-level specificity of the developed LAMP primers, as shown in Supplementary Figure 1.

4.2.3.3 LAMP assay sensitivity

The results, demonstrating the detection limit of the developed LAMP assay, are presented in Graphs 55–57 for Real Time LAMP and in Figure 40 for the Colorimetric LAMP.

Graph 55 specifically illustrates the outcomes of establishing the limit of detection (LOD) of the Real Time LAMP method for *Trichoderma* spp. detection using the PC2 primer set and *T. harzianum* gDNA as a template.

Graph 55. Amplification graph showing LOD of the Real Time LAMP for detection of *Trichoderma* spp. using primer set PC2. Following dilutions were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL (red curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (orange curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻² ng/μL (yellow curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻³ ng/μL (light green curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (dark green curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁵ ng/μL (light blue curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The determined LOD corresponds to a dilution of 10⁻⁴ (dark green curve), equivalent to a *T. harzianum* gDNA concentration of containing 229.31 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL. Hence, at a concentration of 9.17 ng/μL × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (for reaction volume of 25 μL), the LOD for the PC2 primer candidate is determined to be 917 fg/μL i.e. 0.92 pg/μL.

In Graph 56, it is notable that the signals for the dilution series occur at regular time intervals. Additionally, the amount of product decreases towards the lowest concentration, aligning with the higher Tt values for these samples.

Graph 56. Tt values for various tested concentrations of *T. harzianum* gDNA using PC2 in Real Time LAMP. The Graph represents only amplified dilutions: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL (red bar), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (orange bar), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻² ng/μL (yellow bar), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻³ ng/μL (light green bar), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (dark green bar).

The results presented in Graph 57 shows that the amplification is specific, as all amplification curves exhibit a characteristic shape indicative of specific amplification. Additionally, the specificity of the reaction is further evidenced by the peak values of the melting curves for samples where amplification occurred (orange, yellow, light and dark green curves), falling within the range of the peak values observed for the positive control (red curve).

Graph 57. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP amplification products from reaction for determining the LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using primer set PC2. Dilutions tested: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL (red curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (orange curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻² ng/μL (yellow curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻³ ng/μL (light green curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (dark green curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁵ ng/μL (light blue curve), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The results for determining the Colorimetric LAMP LOD of the *Trichoderma* spp. using the PC2 primer set and *T. harzianum* gDNA as a template are presented in Figure 40.

Figure 40. Results of determining the Colorimetric LAMP LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using the PC2 primer set. Following dilutions were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻² ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻³ ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁴ ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁵ ng/μL (resulted in yellow solution), gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL (resulted in yellow-to-orange solution), NTC – non-template control (resulted in pink solution).

The determined LOD corresponds to a dilution of 10⁻⁶, equivalent to a *T. harzianum* gDNA concentration of 229.31 × 10⁻⁶ ng/μL. Hence, at a concentration of 9.17 ng/μL × 10⁻⁶ (for reaction volume of 25 μL), the LOD for the PC2 primer candidate is determined to be 9.17 fg/μL.

4.2.4 *Trichoderma* detection in spiked compost and casing soil samples

Results presented in the following section pertain to evaluation of the effect of DNA isolation from compost and casing soil samples using Chelex 100 and a commercial DNA isolation kit (adapted for this type of sample) on performance of LAMP reaction and the detection of *T. harzianum* in spiked eDNA extracts.

Firstly, different compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained by various DNA extraction approaches were tested for the presence of *Trichoderma* spp. contamination (see *Section 4.2.4.1*). Next, eDNA from non-contaminated compost and casing soil samples was spiked with *T. harzianum* gDNA and used to evaluate efficiency of the developed LAMP assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection (see *Section 4.2.4.2*).

4.2.4.1 Testing compost and casing soil eDNA extracts for Trichoderma spp. contamination

The Real Time LAMP results for testing compost and casing soil eDNA extracts for *Trichoderma* spp. contamination are presented in Graphs 58-59, utilizing eDNA extracts obtained using both, Chelex 100 method (Graphs 60–61) and GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit.

Graph 58. Results of *Trichoderma* spp. Real Time LAMP amplification from eDNA extracted from compost and casing soil using Chelex 100 isolation approach. Following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from compost (yellow curve), eDNA from casing soil (dark blue curve) and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

Graph 59. Melting curve graph of *Trichoderma* spp. Real Time LAMP amplification from eDNA extracted from compost and casing soil using Chelex 100 isolation approach. Following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from compost (yellow curve), eDNA from casing soil (dark blue curve) and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

Graph 60. Results of *Trichoderma* spp. Real Time LAMP amplification from eDNA extracted from compost and casing soil using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. Following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from compost (yellow curve), eDNA from casing soil (dark blue curve) and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

Graph 61. Melting curve graph of *Trichoderma* spp. Real Time LAMP amplification from eDNA extracted from compost and casing soil using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. Following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from compost (yellow curve), eDNA from casing soil (dark blue curve) and NTC – non-template control for PC2 (pink curve).

4.2.4.2 Testing the effect of DNA isolation from compost and casing soil samples on *Trichoderma* spp. detection using LAMP

The Real Time LAMP reaction results for eDNA samples isolated using the Chelex 100 method are illustrated in Graphs 62-66 and Table 23, while those obtained from eDNA samples isolated with the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit are presented in Graphs 67-71 and Table 24.

eDNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method

The results of the Real Time LAMP reaction demonstrate that the LOD for *Trichoderma* spp. in compost eDNA extracts, obtained using the Chelex 100 method was at a dilution of 10^{-1} , which is depicted by the orange curve in Graph 62. In the case of casing soil eDNA extracts, the LOD was observed at a 10^{-2} dilution (green curve at Graph 64). This finding, equivalent to 4 pg/μL for compost and 0.4 pg/μL for casing soil eDNA extract, emphasizes the effectiveness of the method.

Furthermore, the specificity was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange and yellow curves for compost and orange, yellow, and green curves for casing soil samples) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graphs 63 and 65).

Graph 62. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in compost eDNA extract samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method. Following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), compost eDNA sample spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), compost eDNA sample spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), compost samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure compost eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 63. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in compost eDNA extract samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method. Following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), compost eDNA sample spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure compost eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 64. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in casing soil eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure casing soil eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 65. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining LOD of detection of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in casing soil eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the Chelex 100 method and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure casing soil eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 66 illustrates a comparison of the Tt values in the tested compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with *T. harzianum* gDNA. The graph indicates that the lower values are obtained with casing soil extracts (in comparison with compost extracts). Additionally, a higher dilution (1×10^{-2}) for LOD was detected in these samples compared to the compost, requiring approximately 27–28 min for detection.

Contrarily, in the case of compost extracts, significantly higher Tt values were recorded for all tested *T. harzianum* gDNA dilutions. It takes up to 6-7 min more to detect the 1×10^{-1} dilution of *T. harzianum* gDNA in the compost sample compared to the casing soil samples. Additionally, there was a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level in Tt values

between the positive controls and eDNA extracts from compost and casing soil, which contained 1 and 1×10^{-1} ng/ μ L of *T. harzianum* gDNA (Table 23).

Graph 66. Comparison of Tt values for compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained using Chelex 100 method and spiked with *T. harzianum* gDNA. The graph summarizes only amplified dilutions: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/ μ L as a positive control for various soil-like extracts, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/ μ L of *T. harzianum* gDNA, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/ μ L of *T. harzianum* gDNA, compost and casing soil eDNA extract spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/ μ L of *T. harzianum* gDNA.

Table 23. Results of the statistical analysis of the differences in Tt values recorded for compost and casing soil eDNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 approach.

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
229.31 ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 229.31 vs. Casing soil 229.31	4.225	0.07594 to 8.374	Yes	*	0.0477
soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 1 vs. Casing soil 1	7	3.536 to 10.46	Yes	**	0.0072
soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 1 × 10 ⁻¹ vs. Casing soil 1 × 10 ⁻¹	6.975	3.814 to 10.14	Yes	**	0.0055

* – significance level of p < 0.05; ** – significance level of p < 0.01

eDNA samples obtained using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit

LOD for *Trichoderma* spp. in eDNA extract from compost samples isolate using commercial DNA isolation kit is 0.4 pg/μL. This corresponds to eDNA sample that contain 1×10^{-2} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (green curve, Graph 67). For eDNA from casing soil samples, LOD is 4 pg/μL corresponding to the eDNA sample that contains 1×10^{-1} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve, Graph 69).

Furthermore, the specificity was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange, yellow and green curves for compost and orange and yellow cuves for casing soil samples) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graphs 69 and 70).

Graph 67. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in compost eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure compost eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 68. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in compost eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), compost eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure compost eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 69. Real Time LAMP amplification graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in casing soil eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), of casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), of casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), of casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), of casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure casing soil eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 70. Real Time LAMP melting curve graph for determining LOD of *Trichoderma* spp. using PC2 primer set in casing soil eDNA extract samples obtained through isolation using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and by using following templates: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (orange curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-1} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (yellow curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-2} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-3} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (dark green curve), casing soil eDNA samples spiked with 1×10^{-4} ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA (light blue curve), pure casing soil eDNA extract (non-spiked) as a negative control (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 71 illustrates a comparison of the Tt values in the tested compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with *T. harzianum* gDNA. Observations indicate that the Tt values for positive controls (229.31 ng/μL) and eDNA extracts from compost and casing soil containing 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA were similar, showing no statistically significant differences (Table 24). However, there was a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level in the case of the 1×10^{-1} dilution between the same samples. In the case of the casing soil eDNA sample, there was no detection if 1×10^{-2} dilution of *T. harzianum* gDNA was used for spiking. Conversely, for the same dilution for compost eDNA extract, there was positive Real Time LAMP reaction within a time range of around 24 to 26 minutes.

LOD - GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit

Graph 71. Comparison of Tt values for compost and casing soil eDNA extracts extracted using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and spiked with different concentration of *T. harzianum* gDNA. The graph presents Tt only for eDNA samples with positive LAMP reaction: gDNA *T. harizanium* 229.31 ng/ μL as a positive control for various soil-like extracts, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 × 10⁻¹ ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA, compost and casing soil eDNA extract spiked with 1 × 10⁻² ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA.

Table 24. Results of the statistical analysis of the differences in Tt values recorded for compost and casing soil eDNA extracts obtained using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit.

	Samples	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	P Value
229.31 ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 229.31 vs. Casing soil 229.31	1.375	-2.090 to 4.840	No	ns	0.3519
soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 1 vs. Casing soil 1	1.5	-1.744 to 4.744	No	ns	0.2749
soil eDNA extracts spiked with 1 x 10 ⁻¹ ng/μL of <i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA	Compost 1 x 10 ⁻¹ vs. Casing soil 1 x 10 ⁻¹	2.925	0.2088 to 5.641	Yes	*	0.0412

ns – not significant; * – significance level of p < 0.05

4.2.5 *Trichoderma* spp. detection in inoculated samples

Real Time LAMP detection of *T. harzianum* was performed in different soil-like samples (compost and casing soil) inoculated with a *T. harzianum* culture. The DNA extraction from inoculated compost and casing soil samples was performed using both, laboratory intensive, kit-based method and field applicable Chelex 100 method (see *Sections 4.2.5.1* and *4.2.5.2*). The effect of applied DNA isolation approaches on Real Time LAMP for *Trichoderma* spp. detection was assessed and these results were compared with the results of Real Time PCR. Real Time PCR was performed using published primers (Lee et al., 2020) as well as F3 and B3 primers from the LAMP PC1 and PC2 sets for *Trichoderma* spp. detection, developed within this doctoral dissertation (see *Section 4.2.6*).

Prior to analysis, concentrations of eDNA extracts were adjusted to 1 ng/μL and the eDNA isolates were then analyzed in Real Time LAMP reactions. The results are presented in Graphs 72–75 for the Chelex 100 method and Graphs 76–79 for the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit.

4.2.5.1 eDNA samples obtained using the Chelex 100 method

It can be observed that in the case of eDNA samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method, no amplification occurred in the eDNA sample from inoculated compost (Graph 72-73). A positive result in the Real Time LAMP reaction was observed only for eDNA from inoculated casing soil samples, with Tt around the 22nd minute (orange curve) (Graph 74). In the controls, i.e., non-inoculated compost and casing soil eDNA extracts, no positive reaction was detected. The specificity was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange curve in the case of casing soil sample) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graph 75).

Graph 72. Amplification graph of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated compost samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from compost sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), compost eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 73. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated compost samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from compost sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), compost eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 74. Amplification graph of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated casing soil samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from casing soil sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), casing soil eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 75. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated casing soil samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from casing soil sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), casing soil eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

4.2.5.2 eDNA samples obtained using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit

The results indicate that the Real Time LAMP reaction with compost and casing soil eDNA samples isolated using the GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit was more successful than the Real Time LAMP reaction with eDNA samples isolated using the Chelex 100 method. Specifically, in the case of compost material, successful detection occurred after approximately 20 min (orange curve on Graph 76), in contrast to Chelex isolates where no detection was observed.

Furthermore, there was effective detection in inoculated casing soil samples, with a detection time around the 18th minute (Graph 78, orange curve), which was a lower detection time compared to casing soil eDNA isolates using the Chelex method.

In both sample types, the specificity was confirmed based on melting peak of amplified samples (orange curve in the case of compost and orange curve in the case of casing soil sample) that overlap with melting peak of positive control (Graphs 77 and 79).

Graph 76. Amplification graph of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated compost samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from compost sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), compost eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 77. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated compost samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from compost sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), compost eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 78. Amplification graph of Real Time LAMP analysis eDNA from of inoculated casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA casing soil sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), casing soil eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 79. Melting curve Graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from inoculated casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), 1 ng/μL of eDNA from casing soil sample inoculated with *T. harzianum* culture (orange curve), casing soil eDNA extract (non-inoculated) as a negative control (dark green curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

4.2.6 Real Time PCR assay

Graphs 80 and 81 present the results of Real Time PCR analysis conducted using F3 and B3 primers from the PC1 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. The Real Time PCR reaction yielded positive results not only for the positive control (*T. harzianum* gDNA, represented by the blue curve, C) but also for samples containing *P. halotolerans* gDNA (red curve, A), *A. carbonarius* gDNA (black curve, B), and *A. fumigatus* gDNA (orange curve, D). Samples with no template DNA were negative.

Graph 80. Amplification graph of Real Time PCR Analysis for testing specificity of F3 and B3 primers from the PC1 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. detection: amplification curve in relation to cycle number. The following templates were used: *P. halotolerans* gDNA (red curve, A), *A. carbonarius* gDNA (black curve, B), *T. harzianum* gDNA (blue curve, C), *A. fumigatus* gDNA (orange curve, D), *A. alternata* gDNA (not amplified), *C. halotolerans* gDNA (not amplified), and NTC (non-template control).

Graph 81. Amplification graph of Real Time PCR Analysis for testing specificity of F3 and B3 primers from the PC1 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. detection: amplification curve in relation to reaction time. The following templates were used: *P. halotolerans* gDNA (red curve, A), *A. carbonarius* gDNA (black curve, B), *T. harzianum* gDNA (blue curve, C), *A. fumigatus* gDNA (orange curve, D), *A. alternata* gDNA (not amplified), *C. halotolerans* gDNA (not amplified), and NTC (non-template control).

Graphs 82 and 83 showcase the results of Real Time PCR analysis performed using F3 and B3 primers from the PC2 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. The Real Time PCR reaction produced positive results in all tested samples, except in NTC. Sample with no template DNA was negative.

Graph 82. Amplification graph of Real Time PCR Analysis for testing specificity of F3 and B3 primers from the PC2 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. detection: amplification curve in relation to cycle number. The following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green and blue curves), *P. halotolerans* gDNA (dark blue and dark green curves), *C. allicinum* gDNA (pink and orange curves), *A. alternata* gDNA (blue and black curves), *A. fumigatus* gDNA (turquoise and black curves) and NTC - non-template control (not amplified).

Graph 83. Amplification graph of Real Time PCR Analysis for testing specificity of F3 and B3 primers from the PC2 LAMP primer set for *Trichoderma* spp. detection: amplification curve in relation to reaction time. The following templates were used: *T. harzianum* gDNA (light green and blue curves), *P. halotolerans* gDNA (dark blue and dark green curves), *C. allicinum* gDNA (pink and orange curves), *A. alternata* gDNA (blue and black curves), *A. fumigatus* gDNA (turquoise and black curves) and NTC - non-template control (not amplified).

The results of testing the TDP-F and TDP-R PCR primers described in the study by Lee et al.(2020). showed that there was no amplification in the positive controls. Consequently, they were not further utilized for the comparative study of the efficiency of Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR.

4.2.7 The detection of *Trichoderma* spp. using LAMP assay in real samples

The results obtained in this section were further utilized to assess the application of the LAMP assay in detecting *Trichoderma* spp. in compost and casing soil samples obtained from organic mushroom production, as described in *Section 3.2.1.2*. For this purpose, when selecting samples for LAMP analysis, we considered the results of sequencing, macroscopic, and microscopic analysis (refer to Table 25). These results were used to determine:

- Whether the LAMP method is more effective for early *Trichoderma* spp. detection compared to traditional cultural methods;
- Whether LAMP is the preferred method for early *Trichoderma* spp. detection during mushroom cultivation.

Morphological observation of the cultivation bags during production period showed that there was the obvious presence of *Trichoderma* spp. on the cultivation bag i.e. on sample 10 (Figure 41).

Figure 41. *Trichoderma* spp. (green mold) on cultivation bag observed by naked eye during mushroom cultivation.

Table 25 presents the summarized results of *Trichoderma* spp. detection in compost and casing soil samples through: sequencing and macro- and microscopic analysis.

Table 25. Presence of *Trichoderma* spp. in compost and casing soil samples determined based on sequencing results and traditional cultivation methods. The first brackets indicate the presence (+) or absence (-) of *Trichoderma* spp. determined by sequencing. The second brackets indicate the presence (+) or absence (-) of *Trichoderma* spp. based on results of macro and microscopic identification methods.

Cultivation bag number	Compost 11/06/21	Compost 25/06/21	Casing soil 02/07/21	Compost 14/07/21
1	K1 (+), (-)	K1* (-), (-)	P1 (-), (-)	K1# (-), (-)
2	K2 (-), (-)	K2* (-), (-)	P2 (+), (-)	K2# (+), (+)
3	K3 (-), (-)	K3* (-), (-)	P3 (+), (+)	K3# (-), (+)
4	K4 (-), (-)	K4* (-), (+)	P4 (+), (+)	K4# (-), (+)
5	K5 (+), (-)	K5* (-), (-)	P5 (+), (+)	K5# (-), (+)
6	K6 (+), (-)	K6* (-), (-)	P6 (+), (-)	K6# (-), (+)
7	K7 (-), (-)	K7* (+), (-)	P7 (+), (+)	K7# (+), (-)
8	K8 (-), (-)	K8* (-), (-)	P8 (+), (+)	K8# (-), (+)
9	K9 (-), (-)	K9* (+), (-)	P9 (-), (-)	K9# (-), (-)
10	K10 (-), (-)	K10* (-), (-)	P10 (+), (-)	K10# (-), (+)

***Samples highlighted with light green were further selected for LAMP analysis.

Selected samples for LAMP based *Trichoderma* spp. detection:

K1 – The sequencing results indicated the presence of *Trichoderma* spp., whereas the microbiological cultivation did not yield similar findings. The decision to use K1 as a sample aimed to assess whether the LAMP method is more effective for the early detection of *Trichoderma* spp. compared to traditional culture methods.

K7 and K7# – The sequencing results indicated the presence of *Trichoderma* spp. at the end of the mushroom cultivation process (K7# sampled on 14/07/21), whereas at the beginning, sequencing results showed no *Trichoderma* in the cultivation bag (K7 sampled on 11/06/21). In both samples, microbiological cultivation did not yield positive findings. These two samples were chosen to assess LAMP as the method of choice for the early detection of *Trichoderma* spp. during mushroom cultivation.

P3 – Both sequencing results and microbiological cultivation provided positive results for the presence of *Trichoderma* spp. This made it the sample of choice for the LAMP reaction to assess the efficiency of LAMP against these two methods.

P9 – Selected for its negative results in both sequencing and microbiological cultivation for the presence of *Trichoderma* spp., this sample became the focal point for the LAMP reaction to evaluate the efficiency of LAMP against these two methods.

K10, K10*, K10# and P10 – Given the observation that the presence of *Trichoderma* was visible with the naked eye on cultivation bag number 10, compost samples from all three sampling points (K10 sampled on 11/06/21, K10* sampled on 25/06/21, and K10# sampled on 14/07/21), as well as casing soil sample P10, were selected to determine the efficiency of the developed LAMP assay.

Graphs 84-87 display the results of the LAMP reaction for all tested compost and casing soil samples) isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. In Graph 84, it can be observed that the amplification curves of all the samples that yielded a positive LAMP reaction (K1 – orange curve, K7# – light green curve, P3 – dark green curve, and P9 – dark blue curve) appeared relatively late, around 28th and 29th min.

Graph 84. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K1 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K7 sample (yellow curve), eDNA from K7# sample (light green curve), eDNA from P3 sample (dark green sample), eDNA from P9 sample (light blue curve), eDNA from P10 sample (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 85. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K1 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K7 sample (yellow curve), eDNA from K7# sample (light green curve), eDNA from P3 sample (dark green sample), eDNA from P9 sample (light blue curve), eDNA from P10 sample (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 86. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K10 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K10* sample (light green curve), eDNA from K10# sample (light blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 87. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K10 sample (orange curve), eDNA from 10* sample (light green curve), eDNA from K10# sample (light blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

It can be observed that, in the case of selected compost and casing soil samples isolated by the Chelex 100 method, there were no positive results in the Real Time LAMP reaction (Graphs 88–91).

Graph 88. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K1 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K7 sample (yellow curve), eDNA from K7# sample (light green curve), eDNA from P3 sample (dark green sample), eDNA from P9 sample (light blue curve), eDNA from P10 sample (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 89. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K1 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K7 sample (yellow curve), eDNA from K7# sample (light green curve), eDNA from P3 sample (dark green sample), eDNA from P9 sample (light blue curve), eDNA from P10 sample (dark blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 90. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K10 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K10* sample (light green curve), eDNA from K10# sample (light blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 91. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from compost and casing soil samples isolated by Chelex 100 method. The following templates were used: gDNA *T. harzianum* 229.31 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from K10 sample (orange curve), eDNA from K10* sample (light green curve), eDNA from K10# sample (light blue curve), NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Finally, Table 26 represents the number of successful detections in all replicates (3 in total).

Table 26. LAMP detection success (number of positive reaction/total number of reactions) for compost and casing soil eDNA samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit and Chelex 100 method.

Sample ID	No. of positives Samples isolated by GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit	No. of positives Samples isolated by Chelex 100 method
Positive control (<i>T. harzianum</i> gDNA)	3/3	3/3
K1	1/3	0/3
K7	0/3	0/3
K7#	2/3	0/3
K10	0/3	0/3
K10*	0/3	0/3
K10#	0/3	0/3
P3	1/3	0/3
P9	1/3	0/3
P10	0/3	0/3
NTC	0/3	0/3

4.2.8 LAMP assay coupled with Gold Nanoparticles for Colorimetric Detection of *Trichoderma* spp.

The results presented in this section pertain to all the experiments described in *Section 3.2.12*. The first part presents the results obtained from optimizing the salt concentration, reaction temperature, and reaction time for the LAMP-AuNP assay. This is followed by a presentation of the results regarding the assay's specificity and sensitivity

4.2.8.1 LAMP-AuNP assay optimization

The results of the salt concentration optimization are depicted in Figure 42. When 1, 5, or 10 μL of MgCl_2 with varying molarities (2 mM, 20 mM, and 2M) were introduced into the AuNP solutions, color change of the solution (as a consequence of agglomeration of gold nanoparticles) was observed across all tested concentrations obtained with 20 mM MgCl_2 stock solution (Figure 42A).

Subsequent testing, using 2 μL of LAMP products (32 ng/ μL in final concentration), revealed that 2.5 μL of 20 mM MgCl_2 (i.e., 0.4 mM in final concentration) is the critical salt concentration that induces AuNP agglomeration (Figure 42B). This concentration was subsequently employed in additional tests with LAMP products.

Figure 42. Steps in optimization of salt concentration for colorimetric detection of LAMP products. A) impact of salt concentration on the aggregation of AuNPs; B) impact of salt concentration on the aggregation of AuNPs hybridized with LAMP amplifications.

The results of testing temperatures and time conditions for the LAMP-AuNP assay are presented in Figure 43. The findings suggest that incubation at 65 °C for 10 min proved to be the most optimal for the adsorption of LAMP products with AuNPs and was consequently employed in subsequent experiments.

Figure 43. Results of testing of incubation time and temperature of AuNP-LAMP assay. The numbers stand for concentrations of LAMP amplicons in ng/μL. Circled in red are chosen conditions.

The results of testing assay specificity are shown at Figure 44. The color of solutions and spectrophotometric measurements indicated that only AuNPs incubated with positive LAMP were not aggregated upon MgCl₂ addition (red box). These results indicate that the color remained red as a result of the binding between LAMP amplicons and AuNPs.

Figure 44. The difference in A_{630} in the positive LAMP reaction and all tested negative controls. A) Differences between each tested control and positive LAMP reaction and B) absorbance measurements in the range 450-700 nm for positive reaction and each control.

The results for determining the LOD of the LAMP-AuNP assay are presented in Figure 45. It can be observed from the picture that in the case of a positive LAMP reaction, a limit of detection of 24 ng/μL was evident to the naked eye (Figure 45A). At this amplicon dilution, a distinct difference in absorption intensity at 630 nm was observed between the positive LAMP reaction and the negative control (Figure 45B). The comparison of signal intensities at A₆₃₀ revealed that distinguishing between positive and negative LAMP reactions is not possible directly but requires a ten-time dilution of amplification product. Furthermore, Figure 45C illustrates that the LAMP-AuNPs assay exhibited sensitivity in a solution containing amplicons at concentrations ranging from 240 ng/μL to 2.4 ng/μL. However, additional dilution of samples led to a significant decrease in the number of amplicons, making it impossible to suppress AuNP aggregation at the given salt concentration.

Figure 45. Differences between positive and negative detection using LAMP-AuNP assays. A) Color changes in positive (above) and negative (below) reactions observed with the naked eye; B) The difference in absorbance values for the 100 x dilutions of positive (red) and negative (blue) detection at wavelengths 450-700 nm; C) The difference in A₆₃₀ values was assessed by testing various dilutions of positive (red) and negative (blue) LAMP reaction using LAMP-AuNP assay.

4.3 LAMP-based assay for *E. coli* detection in highly polluted water samples

The results presented in this section pertain to all experiments described in *Section 3.3*. The first part of *Section 4.3* presents the results of eDNA extraction from river water samples using the modified Kesberg and Schleheck (2013) syringe-based extraction method. This was done to show whether the modified protocol would yield concentrations and quality of eDNA that could be further used in Real Time LAMP detection of *E. coli* (as a representative of FIB bacteria). The same eDNA extracts were also used to compare their potency for use in Real Time PCR.

4.3.1 Concentration and purity of DNA

Concentration and purity of *E. coli* gDNA and eDNA isolated from highly polluted water samples are presented in Tables 27-28.

4.3.1.1 Bacterial cultures

Table 27 presents the concentration and purity of gDNA obtained from *E. coli* culture. This isolation was carried out in accordance with the instructions outlined in *Section 3.3.1.1*, aiming to utilize *E. coli* gDNA as a positive control in all subsequent analyses.

Table 27. Concentration and purity of gDNA isolated from *E. coli* culture.

Sample	gDNA concentration [ng/μL]	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	50.00	1.62	1.92

4.3.1.2 Water samples

Table 28 presents concentration and purity of eDNA from highly polluted water samples. This isolation was conducted following the instructions described in *Section 3.3.1.2*.

Table 28. Concentration and purity of eDNA from highly polluted water samples.

Sample	eDNA concentration [ng/ μ L]	A_{260}/A_{280}	A_{260}/A_{230}
S1 sample(upstream of S2)	17.36	1.28	1.23
S2 sample (city sewage outfall)	17.67	1.19	1.83
S3 sample (upstream of S1)	22.12	1.29	0.28

The concentration values of highly polluted water samples isolated using a modified syringe filter-based methodology, ranged from 17.36 to 22.12 ng/ μ L. The absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} for all tested eDNA isolates from water samples was consistently lower than the lower reference value, i.e., below 1.7. This indicates the presence of a significant amount of protein, phenolic compounds, and other contaminants, which have absorption maximum around 280 nm. Furthermore, for all tested samples, the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{230} consistently fell below the lower reference value, i.e., below 2.0. The values for these samples ranged from 0.28 to 1.83.

4.3.2 Microbiological confirmation of *E. coli* presence in water samples

The results presented in the following section pertain to the microbiological enumeration of *E. coli* presence in the tested river water samples - S1, S2, and S3 (Figure 46).

Figure 46 illustrates the confirmation and enumeration of *E. coli* on selective media.

Figure 46. The results of the microbiological confirmation of *E. coli* in water samples. A) *E. coli* colonies on selective media: *E. coli* species (blue colonies), other coliform bacterial species (pink colonies), other non-coliform bacterial species (yellow colonies); B) Enumeration of *E. coli* on selective media: Upper left – *E. coli* pure culture (positive control); upper right – S1 sample that contains 33800 CFU of *E. coli* per 100 mL of water sample; lower left – S2 sample that contains 55000 CFU of *E. coli* per 100 mL of water sample; lower right – S3 sample that contains 4300 CFU of *E. coli* per 100 mL of water sample.

4.3.3 LAMP assay

The results of the LAMP assay for the detection of *E. coli* in highly polluted water samples are depicted in Graphs 92–93 and Figure 47.

Real Time LAMP resulted in successful amplification of *E. coli* in S1 (black curve) and S2 (green curve) samples. Sample S3 did not give a positive reaction, which was consistent with the low abundance of *E. coli* obtained during microbiological determination (Figure 46).

Graph 92. Amplification graph for the results of Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from highly polluted water samples using following templates: gDNA *E. coli* 50 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from S1 sample (black curve), eDNA form S2 sample (green curve), eDNA from S3 sample (blue curve) and NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

Graph 93. Melting curve graph for Real Time LAMP analysis of eDNA from highly polluted water samples using following templates: gDNA *E. coli* 50 ng/μL as a positive control (red curve), eDNA from S1 sample (black curve), eDNA form S2 sample (green curve), eDNA from S3 sample (blue curve) and NTC – non-template control (pink curve).

The assessment of *E. coli* presence in tested highly polluted water samples was additionally conducted through the Colorimetric LAMP method. Colorimetric LAMP successfully detected *E. coli* in control sample, S1 and S2 samples (Figure 47). Sample S3 did not give a positive reaction.

Figure 47. Confirmation of *E. coli* presence in highly polluted water samples using the Colorimetric LAMP method and following templates: gDNA *E. coli* 50 ng/ μ L (yellow solution), eDNA from S1 sample (yellow solution), eDNA form S2 (yellow-to-orange solution), eDNA from S3 (pink solution), and NTC – non-template control (pink solution).

4.3.4 Real Time PCR assay

The Graph 94 presents the outcomes of the Real Time PCR analysis conducted on eDNA from highly polluted water samples. It indicates positive results in the Real Time PCR reaction solely for the positive control (curve A) at approximately the 27th minute. This duration is nearly twice as long as the time required for positive control results in the Real Time LAMP reaction. Additionally, there was no positive reaction observed in any of the tested water samples.

Graph 94. Real Time PCR analysis of eDNA from highly polluted water samples. The following templates were used: *E. coli* gDNA 50ng/μL (A), eDNA from S1 sample (B), eDNA form S2 sample (C), eDNA form S3 sample (D) and NTC. – non-template control (not amplified).

5. Discussion

5.1 Challenges posed by foodborne and waterborne pathogens

Contamination of food and water is a problem that is associated with increased mortality, human and animal diseases, and is also a significant economic burden (Vidic et al., 2019). According to the United States Centers for Disease Control (CDC), it is reported that illnesses caused by food contamination affect 48 million people each year, with 9.4 million infections caused by known pathogens (Fung et al., 2018). Furthermore, the European Food Safety Agency and the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) recorded approximately 359,000 hospitalizations due to zoonoses (diseases transmitted from animals to humans) and almost 500 deaths in the European Union in 2016, as reported in “The European Union summary report on trends and sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and foodborne outbreaks in 2016” (“The European Union summary report on trends and sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and food-borne outbreaks in 2016 | EFSA,” 2017). Such controversial incidents at the global level have led to a growing need for products that prioritize consumer safety. On the other hand, water is an essential input for many food system activities, including agriculture, food processing, and consumption. It serves both as a food ingredient and as a medium for exposing people to microbiological hazards through drinking. Therefore, the characterization of hazards from microbiological pathogens in both food and water must be considered together (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation and World Health Organization, 2019; Linderhof et al., 2021). An example where water was the direct source of food contamination is the romaine lettuce outbreak of 2018. The CDC identified an *E. coli* O157 outbreak linked to romaine lettuce grown in the Yuma, Arizona region. Contaminated irrigation canal water was found to be the source of the bacteria, resulting in 210 reported illnesses, 96 hospitalizations, and five cases of hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) in 36 states (CDC, 2024). Another case occurred in 2019 with the Ground Beef Recall (Food Safety and Inspection Service US Department of Agriculture, 2019). A multi-state outbreak of *E. coli* O103 was linked to ground beef products, with 209 reported cases. The CDC traced the contamination back to the water used in processing facilities, which was found to be contaminated with *E. coli*, leading to a massive recall of the affected beef products.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have a central role in developing and standardizing tools for microbiological risk assessment at the international level. The importance of developing tools for detection of food- and waterborne- pathogens are discussed in the FAO and WHO document describing guidelines for characterizing the hazards of pathogens in food and water

(World Health Organization and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2003).

Reducing the negative impact of pathogens on public health requires an understanding of all primary routes of exposure. Using a common approach to characterize microbiological hazards in food and water will foster this understanding, aid in effective risk analysis, and improve public health protection. Such approach to the detection of pathogens in food of animal and plant origin and in the environment (water, soil) corresponds to the “One health” paradigm, recommended by the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023).

On the other hand, when it comes to agricultural production, the importance of early detection of pathogens in crops is in preventing loss of yield which further enables providing enough food to meet the needs of a growing population, as well as in timely action in preventing later use of chemical treatments of the crops which negatively affects environment and human health. This is especially important when it comes to organic food production.

5.2 Advancement of diagnostic tools for pathogen detection

Traditional microbiological method employed for detecting food and water contamination rely on pathogen cultivation. However, a challenge with this detection method arises from pathogens that are viable but non-culturable (VBNC), whose detection can lead to false negative results and detection failures (Schottroff et al., 2018; Vidic et al., 2019; Nnachi et al., 2022). In this context, application of PCR changed the way microbiological analyses are performed in the direction of detecting specific microbial DNA as a target. PCR-based methods that detect pathogen-derived nucleic acids are fast (last up to several hours), very reliable and allow the analysis of pathogens that do not form visible colonies (Vidic et al., 2019). However, molecular techniques which are commonly applied, such as Endpoint PCR and Real Time PCR depend on precise instruments, clean working conditions and cannot be used in the field. Consequently, the growing demand for infrastructure-independent technologies arises from the lack of food pathogen screening methods that are especially suitable for resource-poor settings. Specifically, efforts have shifted toward developing point-of-need (PoN) food- and waterborne pathogen detection techniques that meet the World Health Organization’s ASSURED criteria. These criteria emphasize that the methods should be Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User-friendly, Rapid and robust, Equipment-free or simple, and Deliverable to end-users (Land et al., 2019; Campbell et al., 2021).

One of the current PoN approaches for detecting pathogens in food and water matrices relies on the integration of molecular methods, biosensors, microfluidics, and nanomaterials (Campbell et al., 2021). Emerging methods often include isothermal amplification, lateral flow immunoassay (LFA), functional nucleic acids, immunosensors, or metabolic assays, utilizing various detection readouts in paper-based and microfluidic devices. These hybrid techniques are designed to simplify food screening processes and enhance the feasibility of *in situ* detection (Campbell et al., 2021).

Among the methods identified in the literature as suitable for the PoN approach, isothermal methods, especially LAMP method, stand out prominently (Atceken et al., 2023). The advantages it offers, including high specificity, sensitivity, and low reaction time, have made significant contributions to its ongoing development. An additional benefit of the LAMP method is its ability to detect pathogens in samples without the need for prior NA purification, thanks to its high specificity achieved through the use of a set of 4 to 6 primers and its resistance to inhibitors presence in different sample types (Zhao et al., 2015; Tsai et. al., 2016). Furthermore, the LAMP technique has gained prominence as an analytical method for real time analysis of food- and waterborne pathogens owing to its advantageous features, including fluorescence, turbidity, and electrochemical sensing capabilities (Lakshmi and Kim, 2021). Nevertheless, further scientific advancements are necessary for LAMP to fully achieve the standards of point-of-need (PoN) diagnostics. Such improvements have the potential to significantly reduce the risk of food- and waterborne contamination, thereby alleviating the associated global health and economic burdens.

Based on these findings, this doctoral dissertation focuses on food and water safety by developing innovative methods for the rapid detection of pathogens in food and water, utilizing the isothermal method of nucleic acid amplification, LAMP, for fast and easy detection in the field. Regarding the development of the LAMP method for research and potential practical applications in detecting pathogens in various complex matrices, the following significant results were achieved: 1) *de novo* LAMP assay for detecting bacterial pathogens in diverse food matrices (both of plant and animal origin) was developed using *K. aerogenes* as a model system; 2) *de novo* LAMP assay for the early detection of pathogenic fungi in a soil-like matrix was developed using *Trichoderma* spp. as the model for pathogenic fungi and employing mushroom-growing substrates as the soil-like matrix. Furthermore, 3) the applicability of the LAMP method for assessing river water quality is confirmed by experimental validation of its use in detecting fecal indicator bacteria (FIB), such as *E. coli*, in highly polluted river water

samples. This approach to pathogen detection in food of animal and plant origin, as well as in environmental contexts, aligns with the "One Health" paradigm recommended by the FAO, which emphasizes methods for optimizing the health and well-being of people, animals, plants, and the environment. In addition, the results of this thesis include enhanced extraction protocols, such as a modified Chelex 100 method for food and soil-like samples, and an improved syringe-based DNA isolation method for water samples, as well as their evaluation for application in the field conditions. The dissertation also resulted in a comprehensive comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the developed LAMP protocols against conventional cultivation methods and the PCR method, which serves as the "gold standard" for nucleic acid amplification. Based on this analysis, conclusions can be drawn regarding the applicability of the developed LAMP protocols for the early detection of bacterial and fungal pathogens under field conditions.

It is important to note that clear and easily applicable protocols for the LAMP method do not currently exist for *K. aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp. This underscores the significance of the research and its potential impact in advancing pathogen detection and analysis that can be applicable in the field.

5.3 Development of a LAMP-based assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in food matrices

In this doctoral dissertation, a LAMP method was successfully developed, validated, and optimized for the rapid, efficient, and highly specific detection of the pathogenic bacterium *K. aerogenes*, in food samples of plant (vegetable) and animal (meat and meat products) origin. This bacterium was chosen as a model foodborne pathogen for the continued development of the LAMP assay due to its prevalence in various types of food and water. Currently, there is no literature documenting LAMP detection methods for this pathogenic bacterium (Cooney et al., 2014).

The LAMP primer design for the detection of *K. aerogenes* resulted in three sets of highly promising primer candidates (PCs) that specifically target the *HDC* gene of *K. aerogenes* (Section 4.1.2, Table 14). Further, the results of primer candidate testing revealed that the PC2 primer set exhibited the most favourable characteristics for the specific detection of *K. aerogenes* gDNA as a template (Graph 1, Section 5.1.3.1). Although primer set PC1 displayed a shorter Time to Threshold value (Tt) value (12 min) compared to PC2 (15 min), its negative control indicated the presence of false positives (Graph 2, Section 5.1.3.1) which occur often

in the case of LAMP (Moehling et al., 2021). Given that the same result was obtained in all tested replicates while following good laboratory practices, it is considered that this result is not due to cross-contamination during the experimental work. Conversely, PC2 showed no amplification in the negative controls. In comparison to the PC3 primer candidate set, PC2 demonstrated a shorter Tt value, suggesting more efficient amplification, hence it was used in further optimization experiments.

When tested with non-specific bacterial species, PC2 candidate demonstrated high efficacy and specificity (Graphs 4-5, *Section 4.1.3.2*). This specificity was confirmed through a naked-eye approach using the Colorimetric LAMP method (Figure 31, *Section 4.1.3.2*) and the results of the specificity test were further confirmed by electrophoresis on agarose gel (Figures 32 and 33, *Section 4.1.3.2*).

It has been determined that, when employing the primer set PC2, limit of detection (LOD) of the Real Time LAMP method for the species *K. aerogenes* was 240 fg/μL (Graphs 68, *Section 4.1.3.3*). Additionally, it has been determined that the Real Time LAMP method is more sensitive than the Colorimetric LAMP method, as the Colorimetric approach resulted in a higher detection limit of 24 pg/μL (Figure 34, *Section 4.1.3.3*). Such result could be attributed to the fact that the fluorescent intercalary dyes used in Real Time LAMP assays (Seyrig et al., 2015; Quyen et al., 2019a) are often more sensitive than the pH-sensitive dyes employed in the Colorimetric approach (Tanner et al., 2015; Poole et al., 2017). This increased sensitivity may enable the detection of lower concentrations of target DNA. Additionally, Real Time LAMP utilizes a specialized instrument to measure changes in fluorescence in Real Time (Genie® III), allowing for more precise quantification of the amplification signal. In contrast, the Colorimetric LAMP assay described in this dissertation relied on simple naked-eye inspection, which may have limitations in both sensitivity and quantification.

Since there are no existing works in the literature describing the LOD for *K. aerogenes* using LAMP, this LOD can be compared with the one obtained for the LAMP assay for a related species *K. pneumoniae* published by Dong et al., which is 115 fg/μL for Real Time turbidity monitoring and fluorescence detection (Dong et al., 2015). Another research group, Poirier et al. in 2021, developed a LAMP assay for the detection of *K. pneumoniae* and reported an LOD of 100 fg/μL for fluorometric detection and 10 pg/μL for colorimetric detection (Poirier et al., 2021). Based on this research, it can be concluded that the LAMP LOD of *K. aerogenes*

achieved in this doctoral dissertation is within the same order of magnitude as the LODs reported in the scientific literature for detecting *Klebsiella* species using LAMP.

5.3.4 *K. aerogenes* detection in spiked food samples

Based on the results obtained during the optimization of the LAMP reaction, the experimental work was extended to assess the sensitivity of detecting the *K. aerogenes* bacterium in food samples (vegetables and meat).

Considering that bacterial contaminants of any food type are generally not visible to the naked eye because individual bacterial cells are microscopic in size, this initiative aims to develop a Real Time LAMP method for the detection of *K. aerogenes* that can be applicable for in-field use, to prevent its further spreading to the consumers.

When selecting samples for testing, vegetable crops such as carrots (grown in the ground), lettuce (grown on the ground), and cucumber (grown slightly above the ground) were chosen to encompass the spectrum where cross-contamination can occur. Contamination of vegetable crops grown underground and, on the ground, typically arises from contact with soil containing pathogenic bacteria. Conversely, crops slightly above ground may encounter contamination during growth when young plants penetrate the soil, as well as through aerosols (Alegbeleye et al., 2018; Pavlíková et al., 2023). Given the variations in chemical composition and anatomical characteristics of the sampled vegetable parts, differing extraction efficiencies are expected (Tamari and Hinkley, 2016).

Fresh meat (chicken breast) and meat products (chicken salami) were selected to investigate the applicability of LAMP assay for *K. aerogenes* detection in both sample types. These two different types of meat samples were chosen due to the possibility of contamination by pathogenic bacteria at various stages of food production. Contamination can happen during and after slaughter where bacteria from the animal's microbiota, the slaughterhouse environment and equipment can get onto the carcasses, cuts, and meat products (Rouger et al., 2017).

The classic Chelex 100 method, commonly utilized as a fast and robust DNA extraction method (Gautam, 2022), inspired the use of a modified version described in *Section 3.1.2.2* of this doctoral dissertation for extracting DNA from food samples, particularly with potential field applications in focus. On the other hand, for the isolation of the same samples in laboratory conditions, DNA extraction was performed using commercial kits with spin column-based nucleic acid extraction, as a standard DNA extraction technique (Shin, 2012). Kits adapted for

special sample types were used, specifically the Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit (Norgen Biotek, Canada) for vegetable samples and the DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit (Qiagen, Germany) for meat samples.

Two experiments were conducted: in the first, vegetable and meat DNA extracts were spiked with 1 ng/ μ L of *K. aerogenes* gDNA, while in the second experiment, vegetable and meat samples were inoculated (artificially contaminated) with a bacterial suspension at a concentration of 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL. This approach allowed for the examination of the Real Time LAMP method's effectiveness in detecting *K. aerogenes* gDNA present in vegetable and meat extracts. Additionally, it enabled an assessment of the suitability of the selected methods for DNA isolation and sample preparation for PoN analysis using the Real Time LAMP method employing the Genie® III instrument (OptiGene, United Kingdom) a hand-held device known to be specifically developed for outdoor use with weatherproofing and portability as the primary design objectives.

The mechanical homogenization process varies between the two methods used for all tested food samples. Specifically, the Chelex 100 method achieves better tissue breakdown compared to used commercial kits. Consequently, samples isolated using this method are expected to exhibit a higher concentration of total DNA, which was confirmed by measuring the concentration of gDNA on BioSpec-nano spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) (Table 11, *Section 4.1.1.2* and Table 13, *Section 4.1.1.3*).

Both, the field and laboratory dependent isolation methods for all types of food samples yielded positive results in the Real Time LAMP reaction (Graphs 13-35 and Tables 15–17, *Section 4.1.4.2*). This confirms that detecting the presence of *K. aerogenes* gDNA in vegetable and meat DNA extracts is feasible by using the LAMP assay developed within this doctoral dissertation.

After demonstrating the feasibility of detecting the presence of *K. aerogenes*, the LOD of the LAMP assay for detecting this bacterium in food environments (vegetables and meat) was determined. Interestingly, the Chelex 100 method yielded significantly better results for vegetable samples, with a detection limit of 0.4 pg/ μ L across all three samples (Graphs 13, 15 and 17 in *Section 4.1.4.2*), compared to the commercial kit, detection limit of 40 pg/ μ L (Graphs 24, 26 and 28, *Section 4.1.4.2*). The LOD achieved for the LAMP assay, using both the field (Chelex 100) and laboratory (commercial kit) extraction methods, can be compared with the values reported by Sayad et al. (2016) These authors reported that LAMP assay LOD for

Salmonella enteritidis in spiked tomato samples was 5 pg/uL. However, in this study, the Boling method was employed for DNA extraction, involving centrifugation steps that make this approach reliant on laboratory conditions (Sayad et al., 2016). Thus, it can be concluded that the LAMP assay developed in this doctoral dissertation, integrated with an in-field DNA extraction approach from vegetable samples, exhibits superior effectiveness in terms of detection limit. Moreover, it shows great potential for point-of-need (PoN) applications.

On the contrary, for meat samples, both the Chelex 100 method and the commercial kit yielded the same detection limit for *K. aerogenes* extracts, which was 0.4 pg/ μ L (Graphs 19, 21, 31 and 33, Section 4.1.4.2).

When testing the effect of the mentioned DNA isolation methods on detection efficiency, the objective was to assess the success of the Real Time LAMP reaction depending on the method applied for sample preparation, with a focus on the Chelex 100 extraction method.

The Chelex 100 method is a fast and robust method, consisting of only a few steps, and as such, it is very suitable for field application (Gautam, 2022). However, this method is also known to be robust method for gDNA isolation since it leaves impurities in the DNA isolate (Singh et al., 2018). One of the papers that testifies to this claim was published by Auricchio et al. (2013), who showed that the Chelex 100 method had significantly lower purity compared to extracts obtained by other extraction methods. However, within the same study, it was demonstrated that the Chelex 100 method proved significantly more effective for gDNA isolation from the foodborne bacterium *C. botulinum* compared to other DNA isolation methods (Auricchio et al., 2013). The question was whether the gDNA from this rough isolation method could be detected in the Real Time LAMP reaction.

To enhance DNA extraction efficiency and its in-field usability, a modification of the classic Chelex 100 method was implemented by introducing an alkaline-PEG buffer (Tomlinson and Boonham, 2015) into the preparation process. This buffer, known as a widely used lysis reagent, enables the processing of a wide variety of biological samples (Chomczynski and Rymaszewski, 2006). Specifically, PEG 200 present in the alkaline-PEG buffer interacts with water by binding H^+ ions, leading to its dissociation and the release of a substantial amount of OH^- ions. Consequently, this enables the maintenance of a pH value above 13 (between 13.3-13.5) for an extended period. During this time, DNA released by the action of strong bases (NaOH or KOH) remains in suspension (Chomczynski and Rymaszewski, 2006). Additionally, Chelex 100 is responsible for binding heavy metal cations (such as Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Mg^{2+}),

which facilitates DNase inactivation and enhances the stability of the released DNA (National Institute of Justice, 2023).

Given that DNA extractions using commercial kits typically yield significantly purer DNA samples, the expectation in this experiment was that the results would favour them over the Chelex 100 method. However, all food samples inoculated with *K. aerogenes* suspension, including vegetables and meat, that were isolated using the Chelex 100 method, showed higher concentrations of gDNA (Table 11, *Section 4.1.1.2* and Table 13, *Section 4.1.1.3*). In the case of meat samples, both the field and laboratory extraction methods demonstrated similar efficacy, as confirmed by the Real Time LAMP reaction (Graph 38, *Section 4.1.5.1* and Graph 42, *Section 4.1.5.3*). On the other hand, concerning vegetable samples, the results of the Real Time LAMP reaction indicated that extraction with a commercial kit was more efficient in isolation of bacterial DNA. Additionally, a variation in the efficiency of these methods was observed when isolating gDNA from different types of vegetables. Considering the differences in the nature of the tissue components of the selected plant samples, the highest efficiency was expected during the extraction from lettuce, i.e., from the leafy sample (Tamari and Hinkley, 2016). Compared to the other two vegetable samples, lettuce contain less fibrous material what makes it easier to homogenize, and directly relates to the amount of destroyed cells from which DNA is released (Tomlinson and Boonham, 2015; Carrillo-López and Yahia, 2019). This hypothesis was also confirmed by the Real Time LAMP method, given that the inoculated lettuce sample showed the lowest Tt values for *K. aerogenes* detection in DNA extracts obtained by Chelex 100 extraction approach (Graph 36, *Section 4.1.5.1*).

Considering that contamination with the test bacterium *K. aerogenes* often remains on the surface of vegetables, cucumber samples were collected to include the pericarp. This part of the cucumber is harder than the inner part, the mesocarp. Given that the natural wax present on cucumber pericarp is washed away during cultivation in fields, artificial wax containing mineral oil, vegetable oil, or petroleum wax is typically applied to the cucumber pericarp before sale to enhance its attractiveness to buyers (Jung and Schaffner, 2021). Taking all the above into account, it is conceivable that homogenization of this sample requires a different approach and further optimization of isolation methods for in-field use.

5.3.5 Detection of *K. aerogenes* in inoculated food samples - comparative analysis: Real Time LAMP vs. Real Time PCR

When comparing Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR for the detection of *K. aerogenes* in inoculated food samples, it was evident that the results of the Real Time LAMP method demonstrate a clearer correlation with the differences in the anatomical nature of the samples. Specifically, in the case of vegetable extracts isolated by the Chelex 100 approach, the amplification curves for all three tested samples appear simultaneously but in a different order than observed in the Real Time PCR reaction (Graphs 44-45, *Section 4.1.6*). Moreover, it is noteworthy that amplification by Real Time PCR took twice as long for positive results (more than 1 hour) compared to Real Time LAMP (less than 30 minutes). In the case of vegetable DNA extracts isolated with a commercial kit (Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation Kit) the Real Time LAMP method proved to be successful, providing positive reactions within 30 minutes, while Real Time PCR did not detect *K. aerogenes* in any of the tested samples (Graphs 46-47, *Section 4.1.6*).

Moreover, in the case of meat samples, a positive Real Time PCR reaction occurred only in inoculated meat samples from which DNA was extracted using a commercial kit (DNeasy PowerFood Microbial Kit) (Graphs 48-49, *Section 4.1.6*). However, it took more than double the reaction time to obtain positive results (around 45 minutes) (Graph 49) compared to Real Time LAMP (less than 20 minutes) (Graph 42, *Section 4.1.5.3*).

The negative and less efficient results of Real Time PCR reactions may be related to the composition of the alkaline-PEG buffer used in the Chelex 100 method for cell lysis. Although it improves DNA yield during isolation, the PEG buffer does not favourably affect the purity of isolated DNA. Consequently, impurities present in the DNA isolate can act as inhibitors in the Real Time PCR reaction. Additionally, Chelex 100 has the ability to chelate divalent cations, including Mg^{2+} , which is an essential cofactor for *Taq* polymerase (Vashishtha and Konigsberg, 2016). However, it is evident that this buffer does not inhibit the reactions performed using the Real Time LAMP method, indicating the applicability of using the Chelex 100 method in the PoN approach, i.e., for the preparation of samples in field conditions that can be further analyzed using the Real Time LAMP method.

Finally, it is important to note that this doctoral dissertation describes the proposed methods of the pilot experiment, and the presented results indicate the great potential for further

optimization of both the DNA isolation method and the conditions of the Real Time LAMP and Real Time PCR reactions.

5.4 Development of a LAMP-based assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection in champignon production

Within this doctoral dissertation, a LAMP method has been successfully developed, validated, and optimized for the rapid, efficient, and highly specific detection of the pathogenic fungi *Trichoderma* spp. in soil-like substrates used for the organic cultivation of champignons. The selection of *Trichoderma* spp. as a model pathogenic fungus arises from its significant adverse effects on organic mushroom production, that become visible only after the formation of dark green spores. Once this occurs, it is impossible to prevent their further spread in the nursery, emphasizing the necessity to develop tools for their early detection (Šašić Zorić et al., 2023, Djisalov et al., 2024). Consequently, LAMP was considered as one potential solution for early detection of this type of pathogen directly in nurseries. Early detection would enable taking all necessary measures to prevent the spread of the infection, addressing a critical need in the industry.

This study explored the applicability of the LAMP method to soil-like samples, including compost and casing soil, and its coupling with a field-applicable eDNA extraction approach optimized within this doctoral dissertation. eDNA extraction is the key factor in determining the microbial diversity of soil (Wydro, 2022). However, it is important to emphasize that soil-like samples are often considered one of the most challenging environments, mainly due to the variety of species present and the numerous enzyme inhibitors (such as humic acids and heavy metals) that can be co-extracted with eDNA (Salonen et al., 2010; Zielińska et al., 2017). There are numerous reports in the literature that focus on comparing various eDNA extraction methods from soil (Gabor et al., 2003), with most relying on commercially available ready-made kits specifically designed for soil eDNA extraction that are either column-based or magnetic bead-based systems (Mazziotti et al., 2018). One such report is summarized in a review paper by Wydro (2022), where different approaches to eDNA extraction from soil-like samples and their applications for various downstream analyses are presented (Wydro, 2022). However, there are currently only a few publications that describe the detection of fungi in soil-like samples (Nazar et al., 1996; Filion et al., 2003; Reeleder et al., 2003; Park et al., 2020). Most of these works use commercial DNA extraction kits that require laboratory conditions.

To the best of my knowledge, there are currently no proposed solutions for PoN eDNA extraction of this type of sample, and there is presently a deficiency of literature documenting LAMP detection of these pathogenic fungi (*Trichoderma* spp.) Hence, it can be concluded that the adapted Chelex 100 method for eDNA extraction from soil-like samples coupled with the LAMP assay for *Trichoderma* spp. detection contribute significantly to advancement in the field of PoN analysis.

The LAMP primer design for the detection of *Trichoderma* spp. resulted in two sets of highly promising primer candidates (PCs) that specifically target the *tef1* gene of *Trichoderma* spp. (Section 4.2.2, Table 22). Further, the results of primer candidate testing revealed that the PC2 primer set exhibited the most advantageous characteristics for the specific detection of *T. harzianum* gDNA as a template (tested species from *Trichoderma* genus).

Specifically, primer set PC2 displayed a shorter time-to-result (Tt) value (17 min) compared to PC1 (30 min) (Graph 50, Section 4.2.3.2), suggesting more efficient amplification. Importantly, none of the tested primer sets showed amplification in the negative controls.

When testing the specificity of the PC2 primer set using the Real Time LAMP method with other non-*Trichoderma* fungal species known to be founded in soil-like samples (Perrone et al., 2007; Ghiaie Asl et al., 2017; Latgé and Chamilos, 2019; Park et al., 2020; Jindo et al., 2021), the results demonstrated a high degree of specificity to *T. harzianum* (tested species from *Trichoderma* genus) (Graph 53, Section 4.2.3.2). Furthermore, confirmation of specificity was achieved through the Colorimetric LAMP approach Figure 37, Section 4.2.3.2) and agarose gel electrophoresis (Figures 38-39, Section 4.2.3.2).

The multiple sequence alignment (Supplementary Figure 1) reveals homology among the developed LAMP PC2 set, the *tef1* gene of *Trichoderma harzianum* (as a model for highly aggressive *Trichoderma* spp.), and other tested *Trichoderma* species. This outcome was expected since the *tef1* gene, known for encoding the translation elongation factor 1 alpha and referred to as the secondary fungal DNA barcode in the literature (Meyer et. al., 2019) served as the basis for designing the LAMP primers. Consequently, the developed primers exhibit specificity for the genus level.

The Real Time LAMP method using the PC2 primer set has determined LOD for *T. harzianum* to be 917 fg/μL (0.92 pg/μL) (Graphs 55–57, Section 4.2.3.3). In the case of the colorimetric approach, a higher LOD value was obtained, amounting to 9.17 fg/μL (Figure 40, Section 4.2.3.2). As there are no existing references in the literature regarding the LOD for

Trichoderma using LAMP, this LOD can be compared with the LOD determined within the research published by Niessen and Vogel (2010) for the detection of *Fusarium*. In their study, using LAMP assay it was possible to detect less than 2 pg of purified DNA per reaction within 30 minutes. Likewise, Li et al. (2013) introduced an efficient LAMP assay specifically designed for detecting *Fusarium oxysporum*. Their method, completed in 60 minutes, offers rapid, sensitive, and highly specific detection. Utilizing a SCAR marker sequence, this assay is field-applicable and boasts a remarkable detection limit of 10 fg per 25 μ L reaction in pure culture (Li et al., 2013).

The LOD achieved within this doctoral dissertation for specific detection of *Trichoderma* species using the LAMP assay can also be compared to the LOD for PCR, as described in Lee et al. (2020), which was 500 fg/ μ L for the detection of *T. harzianum*. However, during the experimental testing of the primers described in the same publication, it was determined that the primers did not work; i.e., no reaction occurred in the positive controls due to unknown reasons. Therefore, we can emphasize the importance of developing the LAMP assay as a molecular tool for the detection of *Trichoderma spp.* Another study published by (Miyazaki et al., 2009) reported the detection of *T. harzianum* DNA using Nested PCR, with an LOD of 50 fg/ μ L. This confirms that the limit of detection (LOD) of the developed LAMP method for *Trichoderma* detection is within the range of the order of magnitude of other molecular methods present in the literature.

5.4.4 *Trichoderma spp.* detection in spiked compost and casing soil samples

Following the optimization of the LAMP reaction, the experimental work was extended to assess the sensitivity of detecting *T. harzianum* in the artificially contaminated samples of substrates for cultivation of organic champignons, including compost and casing soil. This initiative was directed towards creating a Real Time LAMP method suitable for detecting *Trichoderma spp.* in field settings.

Compost and casing soil samples were selected for testing and further optimization, considering that these two substrates for growing mushrooms are frequently contaminated with *Trichoderma* spores (Sharma et. al., 2007; Aydoğdu, 2024). Contamination can spread rapidly within the cultivation tunnel, underscoring the critical importance of early detection of these pathogenic fungi in the growing substrates enabling the mushroom growers to promptly remove contaminated cultivation bags and prevent further spread (Sharma et. al., 2007; Aydoğdu, 2024).

The methods chosen for DNA extraction were tailored to suit different settings: Chelex 100 was selected for potential field applications, while the use of the commercial kit (GenElute™ Soil DNA) was chosen for isolating the same samples under laboratory conditions.

Additionally, two experiments were conducted: in the first, compost and casing soil eDNA extracts were spiked with 1 ng/μL of *T. harzianum* gDNA, while in the second experiment, compost and casing soil samples were inoculated with pure *T. harzianum* culture in a 5:1 proportion. This approach allowed the examination of the effectiveness of the Real Time LAMP method in detecting *T. harzianum* gDNA present in compost and casing soil eDNA extracts. Additionally, it enabled an assessment of the suitability of the selected methods for eDNA isolation and samples preparation for analysis using the Real Time LAMP method, which could potentially be used in the field.

As expected, the mechanical homogenization process varies between the two methods. Specifically, for both compost and casing soil samples, eDNA extraction was more efficient when using a commercial kit adapted for this type of samples (Tables 20-21, *Section 4.2.1.2*). This can be attributed to the complex and soil-like composition of both tested sample types. Specifically, the casing soil samples are more homogeneous compared to compost, as they are composed of peat soil. Conversely, compost is an organic substrate produced through a thermophilic microbial process that incorporates various components such as crop residues, underutilized wood, nitrogen-containing additives (such as poultry- or horse manure), seed meal, or synthetic nitrogen sources like urea or ammonium nitrate, along with gypsum (Maeda et al., 2011). Due to its composition, compost is considerably more challenging for eDNA isolation (Šašić Zorić et al., 2023).

The Real Time LAMP reaction yielded positive results for both, in-field and laboratory dependent eDNA isolation methods applied to compost and casing soil samples (Graphs 62, 64, 67 and 69, *Section 4.2.4.2*). This verification underscores the feasibility of detecting the presence of *T. harzianum* gDNA in soil-like extracts using the LAMP assay developed within this doctoral dissertation.

The subsequent step involved determining LOD of the developed LAMP assay. Indeed, for eDNA from casing soil samples extracted using Chelex 100 method lower LOD value (0.4 pg/μL) was achieved (Graph 64, *Section 4.2.4.2*), compared to the eDNA extracted using commercial kit where recorded LOD was 4 pg/μL (Graph 69, *Section 4.2.4.2*). Conversely, the compost samples demonstrated a different trend - a lower LOD value was obtained when using

the commercial kit – 0.4 pg/ μ L (Graph 67, Section 4.2.4.2), while the LOD for Chelex 100 method was 4 pg/ μ L (Graph 62, Section 4.2.4.2). The reduced efficiency of the LAMP reaction when using eDNA from compost samples extracted using the Chelex 100 extraction method can be attributed to the fact that this material contains a large number of different substances known to inhibit enzyme-based DNA analyses, with humic acids being the most dominant (Reuter et al., 2009; Wnuk et al., 2020). On the other hand, the commercial kit used to compare the isolation efficiency (GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit) is adapted for difficult soil samples like compost and, as such, should remove all traces of humic acid using the provided Humic Acid Removal Column and the Organic Substance Removal (OSR) Solution.

The next objective was to examine and compare the efficiency of the mentioned eDNA isolation methods by assessing the success of the Real Time LAMP reaction, depending on the method applied for sample preparation after sample inoculation with pure *Trichoderma* culture. The particular focus was on the Chelex 100 extraction method, for which, according to my best knowledge, there are no published studies on application for soil-like samples such as compost and casing soil. Since the Chelex 100 method optimized within this doctoral dissertation has previously proven to be simple, fast, and efficient for various food matrices, we decided it to be our method of choice for testing the efficiency in this experimental part.

As mentioned before, commercial kits are adapted to the types of samples for which they are used, and it was expected that their efficiency would be higher compared to the robust Chelex 100 method. This was experimentally proven, taking into account that all eDNA extracts from soil-like samples obtained with the chosen commercial kit showed higher concentration values. Results of evaluation of the effect of eDNA extraction approach on Real Time LAMP reaction showed that in the case of casing soil samples, both extraction methods resulted in a positive LAMP reaction (Graphs 74 and 78, Section 4.2.5.1). On the other hand, in the case of compost samples, the results of the Real Time LAMP reaction showed that extraction with the commercial kit was more efficient (Graph 76, Section 4.2.5.1), which can be attributed to the high percentage of humic acid and other inhibitors present in this type of sample (Reuter et al., 2009; Wnuk et al., 2020).

As mentioned above, soil-like samples are generally considered challenging to manipulate for downstream DNA analyses, as the efficiency of DNA extraction depends on the type of soil and its properties (Wydro, 2022). Considering that, it can be said that the experimentally confirmed application of the optimized in-field extraction method for eDNA from casing soil

samples is indeed a significant scientific contribution. Although there were no positive LAMP results in the case of eDNA from compost samples inoculated with *Trichoderma* culture isolated using the Chelex 100 method (Graph 72, *Section 4.2.5.1*), this method is considered to have great potential for further optimization of protocol for in-field application. This consideration is supported by the positive results obtained in the case of spiking compost extracts obtained by the same method with *T. harzianum* gDNA. Further optimization could imply a different approach for sample homogenization and/or the inclusion of an additional step to remove humic acid, all aimed at adapting it for full field application.

5.4.5 *Trichoderma* detection in real samples

Currently, the most promising diagnostic tools for the early detection of various types of *Trichoderma* spp. in mushroom farming facilities are believed to be based on molecular methods (Šašić Zorić et al., 2023). DNA metabarcoding is known to be one of the most potent molecular methods for detection, as it enables the confirmation of the presence of all microorganisms even in complex samples (Reuter et al., 2009). However, this approach has some drawbacks, such as high time consumption (12–72 hours), the need for sophisticated equipment for its performance, and high costs of the analysis.

Within this doctoral dissertation, we tested the previously developed LAMP method for *Trichoderma* spp. detection using real compost and casing soil samples collected during one cycle of organic mushroom growth, which are represented in Table 6 (*Section 3.2.1*). The results of Real Time LAMP testing of eDNA extracted from these samples (eDNA isolation using GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation Kit) were then compared with the results obtained using the DNA metabarcoding approach, as well as with macro- and microscopic analysis (Table 25, *Section 4.2.7*).

Regardless of the type of sample and the cultivation phase in which the samples were collected, it was observed that the results of the tested molecular methods were in positive correlation in almost all samples, except in the case of P10. The observed pattern suggests that the negative Real Time LAMP reaction in P10 can be due to the insufficient amount of *Trichoderma*-derived DNA in this sample. This hypothesis can also be applied to samples K1, P3, and K7#, where a positive Real Time LAMP reaction was not achieved in all tested repetitions (Table 26, *Section 4.2.7*). On the other hand, the exceptional sensitivity of DNA metabarcoding enables the detection of extremely small amounts of DNA fragments (Kredics et al., 2018), so it is not surprising that the reaction was positive when this method was applied to the same

samples. Additionally, the differing results of the Real Time LAMP reaction in the K7 and K7# samples suggest that as the quantity of *Trichoderma* spores increases within the same cultivation bag during champignon cultivation, the likelihood of detecting this pathogenic fungus also rises. Finally, in the case of K10# sample where *Trichoderma* spp. presence was confirmed by macro- and microscopic analysis, molecular methods did not give positive results. This could be attributed to the fact that both tested molecular methods (DNA barcoding and Real Time LAMP) utilized the same eDNA samples for analysis, whereas a separate sub-sample was employed for microbiological cultivation, and to the assumption that *Trichoderma* spp. spores were not evenly distributed in the sample. Moreover, potential cross-contamination from handling during microbiological cultivation, along with the ease of spore spread, could also contribute to the observed patterns in the results for the K10# sample.

When it comes to the samples tested using the Chelex 100 extraction method, there was no positive amplification (Graphs 88 and 90, *Section 4.2.7*), despite positive results obtained with casing soil samples spiked with *Trichoderma* culture. The lack of amplification might be due to using a different sub-sample for eDNA extraction than the one used for extraction with the kit. This further confirms the suggested hypothesis that the reason for variation between replicates, as well as for negative Real Time LAMP reactions in samples where sequencing showed the presence of *Trichoderma*, is an insufficient amount of *Trichoderma*-derived DNA, likely caused by the uneven distribution of *Trichoderma* spores.

Despite the results obtained with real samples, we cannot reject the potency of the developed LAMP assay that is proven on spiked samples (*Section 4.2.4*). Additionally, results described in this doctoral dissertation represent only a proof of concept that requires further optimization. The next experimental steps would involve further work on sampling of compost and casing soil samples in nurseries to ensure a more representative analysis. Additionally, the Chelex 100 extraction method will be optimized, particularly for the more complex compost samples.

5.4.6 Comparative Analysis: Real Time LAMP vs. Real Time PCR

Unfortunately, a comparative analysis of Real Time LAMP with Real Time PCR was not possible due to the unavailability of specific primers for *Trichoderma* spp. in the literature. Namely, when testing the PCR primers (TDF/TDR) described in the Lee et al., 2020, there was no amplification in the positive controls. Additionally, the F3 and B3 primers from the PC1 and PC2 primer sets were tested as PCR primer candidates. However, none of the candidates

showed adequate specificity, as amplification also occurred when testing other non-*Trichoderma* fungal species (Graphs 80-83, *Section 4.2.6*).

5.4.7 LAMP assay coupled with Gold Nanoparticles for Colorimetric Detection of *Trichoderma* spp.

One of the goals of this doctoral dissertation was to explore innovative solutions for the detection of LAMP products. For these purposes, an assay based on the LAMP method in combination with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) was developed. The assay principle relies on the strong tendency of oligonucleotides to adsorb onto the surface of AuNPs through electrostatic interactions, as described by Marin et al.(2021). Precisely, the adsorption of amplicons on AuNPs protects nanoparticles from salt-induced aggregation. Therefore, it was expected that with the addition of $MgCl_2$, there would be no color change in the solution containing LAMP products (positive reactions). Conversely, AuNPs incubated with negative LAMP reaction (no amplicons) were expected to change color from red to violet, as a result of AuNP aggregation.

The results of the assay specificity showed that only AuNPs incubated with positive LAMP reactions were not aggregated upon $MgCl_2$ addition, in comparison with all tested negative controls (Figure 44, *Section 4.2.8.1*). This outcome was a result of the binding between LAMP amplicons and AuNPs.

Furthermore, the results of the determination of the minimum amount of LAMP products detectable by the developed assay indicated that in the case of a positive LAMP reaction, the limit of detection (LOD) was 24 ng/ μ L, which can be observed by the naked eye (Figure 45, *Section 4.2.8.1*). At this amplicon dilution, there was a clear difference in absorption intensity at 630 nm between the positive LAMP reaction and all tested negative controls. The comparison of signal intensities at A_{630} revealed that distinguishing between positive and negative LAMP reactions directly in crude samples is not feasible and requires a tenfold dilution. This phenomenon can be attributed to the high concentration of reactants and primers in the LAMP reaction and master mix, which prevent salt-induced AuNPs aggregation. In diluted samples, the concentration of reagents and primers decreases, and AuNPs aggregation is solely controlled by the presence of amplicons. The results also indicate that the LAMP-AuNPs assay was sensitive in solutions containing amplicons at concentrations ranging from 240 ng/ μ L to 24 ng/ μ L. However, additional dilution of samples significantly decreased the number of amplicons, making it impossible to suppress AuNP aggregation at the given salt concentration.

It is important to highlight that the suggested assay depends strongly on the size and shape of the AuNPs used, as it is based on salt-induced AuNPs aggregation (Marin et. al., 2021). Changing the type of AuNPs will require new optimization of salt concentration and reaction time to enable naked-eye detection.

All in all, the developed LAMP-AuNP assay, resulting in a colorimetric signal, provides a simple and rapid mean of acquiring results independent of the number of samples present on the plate. The portability and naked-eye visualization of results may aid in the future development of a high-throughput, sensitive *Trichoderma* spp. detection directly at the farm. The test can be easily adapted for smartphone-based colorimetric analysis, as many phone applications are available that can image and analyze 96-well plates (such as the free app MyLight).

5.5 LAMP-based assay for *E. coli* detection in highly polluted water samples

Contamination of water and food with fecal bacteria is a persistent problem with serious impacts on public health and the economy (Walker et al., 2019). *Escherichia coli*, a member of the fecal coliform subgroup, is commonly found in the intestines of both humans and animals, serving as a recognized indicator of fecal contamination. Early detection of such contamination remains a critical challenge in maintaining water quality globally. This is especially significant in countries like Serbia, which fall under the category of medium-developed countries in terms of sewage infrastructure. In such countries, where wastewater facilities are lacking, it is crucial to address the issue of untreated wastewater flowing directly into rivers. This untreated wastewater can further serve as a contamination source in the food production chain (Baklan Green Energz news, 2022; Čista Srbija, 2022).

The widely accepted standard for detecting fecal indicator bacteria (FIB) involves the use of conventional culture-based methods due to their cost-effectiveness and ease of use. However, these methods are time-consuming and can take several days for analysis. Molecular methods, primarily PCR and Real Time PCR techniques, have revolutionized microbiological analyses by reducing analysis time and increasing sensitivity and specificity. Furthermore, PCR methods have drawbacks including sensitivity to reaction contaminants common in water samples, which can interfere with the reaction, and their limited application for pathogen detection beyond laboratory settings. LAMP, on the other hand, has significantly decreased the reaction's

susceptibility to inhibitors commonly found in environmental samples and holds potential for further optimization for PoN applications (Moehling et al., 2021).

As timely assessment of water quality is imperative in waterborne pathogen control, the focus of this doctoral dissertation was to demonstrate the feasibility of detecting *E. coli* using the LAMP assay, even in highly polluted water samples.

5.5.1 Optimization of syringe filter-based DNA extraction method

The detection of pathogens using described molecular methods relies on eDNA extracted from environmental samples and is contingent upon the efficiency of the extraction process. Extracting eDNA from environmental water samples can pose significant challenges, primarily attributed to filter clogging during the filtration step (Takasaki et al., 2021). Moreover, the presence of various substances in environmental samples can lead to low purity and extremely low DNA yields, thereby impeding the molecular detection of pathogens in water samples. This is documented by numerous references in the scientific literature (Goldberg et al., 2016; Hunter et al., 2019; Tsuji et al., 2019; Bairoliya et al., 2022).

Multiple commercially available DNA extraction kits have been utilized for collecting eDNA from water samples, and according to available studies, the most commonly employed method involves a filtration-based approach, followed by extraction and purification using either the DNeasy Blood and Tissue DNA Extraction Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) or the PowerWater DNA Extraction Kit (Qiagen) (Tsuji et al., 2019). However, the use of these kits can be limited by their high cost and the need for sterile laboratory conditions. To achieve a cost-effective and rapid application, optimizing traditional syringe-based eDNA extraction methodologies is a viable option.

Acknowledging all the challenges encountered during extraction, and with the aim of developing a fast and simple methodology that could be further optimized for field application, the primary focus of this doctoral dissertation was the modification of the protocol outlined in Kesberg and Schleheck (2013) for sample preparation, purification, and DNA extraction taking a step forward towards its applicability in the field.

Results showed that introduction of the modification in the pre-filtration step prevented significant impurities in the final extract using 10 µm pore size filters, followed by filtration through 0.45 µm pore size filters to concentrate bacterial cells. Additionally, in comparison with the original protocol described by Kesberg and Schleheck (2013) and the modified one by

Lee et al., (2019) extraction flow described within this doctoral theses includes only one incubation step at 65°C after the addition of TPS buffer, significantly contributing to a shortened overall analysis time (Figure 27, *Section 3.3.3.2*). Specifically, the protocol developed in this research requires approximately 45 minutes for all DNA extraction steps, including pre-filtration. In the protocol delineated by Kesberg and Schleheck (2013), the DNA extraction process requires 4 hours for completion, with a hands-on time of approximately 2 hours. On the other hand, in the modified protocol described by Lee et al. (2019), reaction time was reduced by up to 30 minutes. However, this research group conducted LAMP detection of target bacteria using artificially contaminated water samples, which neglects any potential influence of bacteria already present in the water on the measured concentration of isolated eDNA. This makes it challenging to establish a direct correlation between colony-forming units (CFU) and the concentration of the targeted bacterial DNA.

Furthermore, to ensure the purity of the DNA samples, three additional washing steps were introduced into the extraction process. The DNA yield obtained in this study (ranging from 17.36 to 22.12 ng/μL) (Table 28, *Section 4.3.1.2*) falls within the range reported in Kesberg and Schleheck (2013) (10–80 ng/μL) and Lee et. al. (2019) (~20 ng/μL), while the purity, as measured by optical density ratios (OD_{260/280}), was only slightly lower. However, this minor variance may be attributed to the utilization of highly polluted water samples in our study.

5.5.2 *E. coli* detection in real samples

Numerous studies have explored the use of LAMP for detecting bacterial DNA in water samples (Martzy et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2019; Fu et al., 2021; Khodaparast et al., 2022). For instance, Lee et al. (2019) described their use of LAMP to detect target bacteria in artificially contaminated water samples. Nevertheless, using spiked samples disregards potential influences of bacteria already present in the water on the measured concentration of isolated DNA, thus complicating the establishment of a direct correlation between colony forming units (CFU) and the concentration of the targeted bacterial DNA. Conversely, various studies have described the application of LAMP with real, non-spiked water samples. However, the majority of these studies rely on expensive commercial DNA extraction kits, which are highly dependent on laboratory working conditions (Martzy et al., 2017; Fu et al., 2021).

In the research conducted within this doctoral dissertation, raw, highly polluted water samples directly collected from the Danube River were used for all types of analyses. The samples were collected from three sampling points at and upstream of the place where the wastewater

(sewage) is being discharged to the Danube River in Novi Sad, Serbia. While the number of samples utilized was adequate for evaluation at a proof-of-principle level, optimizing for a point-of-need (PoN) application would require conducting measurements on a larger number of samples and various sample/water types with differing levels of contamination.

Further, culture plating on selective media confirmed the presence of coliform bacteria, including *E. coli*, in the analyzed samples (Figure 46, Section 4.3.3). The results revealed that *E. coli* was present in samples from all three sites at concentrations high enough to be detected by conventional microbiological techniques. As predicted, the samples taken upstream of the S2 point exhibited a notably lower count of contaminating bacteria, providing an optimal setting for comparing the sensitivities of the three molecular techniques: Real Time LAMP, Colorimetric LAMP and Real Time PCR.

After microbiological confirmation of the *E. coli* presence in tested water samples, the next step included comparison of *E. coli* detection using Real Time PCR with two different LAMP approaches, Real Time and Colorimetric which yielded positive applications in S1 and S2 samples (Graphs 92–93 and Figure 47, Section 4.3.3). In the case of Real Time PCR, the results indicated that the only positive reaction originated from testing the control sample, which comprised purified DNA from the reference *E. coli* culture (Graph 94, Section 4.3.4). The lack of amplification in the tested environmental samples may potentially be attributed to the presence of common inhibitors such as fulvic acids, humic acids, humic material, metal ions, and polyphenols, which are prevalent in highly polluted environmental water samples (Ijzerman et al., 1997). Specifically, measurements of OD_{260/280} in all tested samples was around 1.25, which possibly can be related to high level of polyphenols present in environmental water samples (Schrader et al., 2012). As mentioned before, *E. coli* is the most frequently used indicator among fecal coliforms and is the dominant fecal coliform species isolated from water, accounting for over 95% of FIB in the samples (Bartram et al., 1996; Li et al., 2021). However, fecal coliforms are just part of a total bacterial diversity present in environmental water samples, therefore the proportion of extracted DNA that originated from *E. coli* in total eDNA isolate might be considerably lower than the overall eDNA amount detected. Such small amounts of DNA could be below the Real Time PCR detection limit.

On the other hand, numerous publications have demonstrated that the LAMP assay is resistant to PCR inhibitors commonly present in complex samples like blood and environmental samples (Lin et al., 2012; Mori et al., 2013b; Wang et al., 2013). The results obtained from testing both

LAMP approaches (Colorimetric and Real Time) provide additional evidence supporting this conclusion, since they clearly demonstrated the presence of *E. coli* in samples S1 and S2. However, no amplification was observed in sample S3. Although the eDNA concentration of all three samples used in this study was in the similar range (17.36 ng/ μ L for S1, 17.67 ng/ μ L for S2, and 22.12 ng/ μ L for S3), the previous microbiological analysis revealed a significant difference in *E. coli* CFU/mL in these samples. The S3 sample exhibited the highest concentration of DNA, however, microbiological analysis revealed a lower presence of *E. coli* in comparison to other coliforms. This implies that the DNA present in the S3 sample might have come from other bacterial species, which could account for the negative LAMP reactions. Nevertheless, LAMP successfully amplified the S1 and S2 samples, which Real Time PCR failed to amplify.

The importance of monitoring water quality to prevent the transmission of waterborne pathogens and identifying potential sources of contamination to protect public health is underscored by the findings from this doctoral dissertation. The dissertation also highlights the limitations of standard Real Time PCR-based protocols for FIB detection, which are highly sensitive to reaction inhibitors often present in eDNA from highly polluted water samples, indicating the need for alternative approaches. Given its effectiveness in overcoming PCR inhibitors in highly polluted water samples, and based on the results obtained, LAMP-based FIB detection should be considered the preferred method for samples where the presence of inhibitors could influence the results. The samples utilized in this study exemplify this situation well. The direct discharge of sewage water into the Danube leads to significant pollution of the river water and a high probability of PCR inhibitors, which are challenging to completely remove during DNA extraction. If FIB detection will be conducted using Real Time PCR, additional optimizations of eDNA extraction are advised. Alternatively, the application of the LAMP methodology and the design of LAMP primers for various bacterial targets should be taken into consideration.

6. Conclusions

Based on the proposed hypotheses, defined objectives, and obtained results, the following main conclusions can be drawn: 1) Detection based on the developed and validated LAMP protocols is adequate for identifying pathogenic bacteria in real food samples of plant and animal origin, as well as in highly polluted river water, as well as for detecting pathogenic fungi in real soil-like substrate samples. This demonstrates that the LAMP method is suitable for implementation within the “One health” approach recommended by FAO; 2) The LAMP method developed and validated in this dissertation for the specific detection of pathogenic bacteria and fungi has proven to be superior to PCR and traditional microbiological cultivation methods for the same pathogens.

Concretely:

- The LAMP method was successfully developed and optimized for the specific and sensitive detection of *Klebsiella aerogenes* (model system for pathogenic bacteria) in food of plant and animal origin;
- The obtained low detection limits for *K. aerogenes* using the Real Time LAMP method indicate the great potential of the LAMP method as a sensitive and reliable diagnostic tool;
- The application of the LAMP method for a PoN approach in detecting pathogens in food of plant and animal origin is possible in combination with in-field methods for DNA isolation, such as the Chelex 100 method optimized within this doctoral dissertation;
- Compared to the Real Time PCR method, the LAMP method proved to be more time-efficient in *K. aerogenes* detection in food of plant and animal origin;
- The results obtained in the analysis of samples of plant and animal origin (vegetables and meat) indicate the great potential of the LAMP method for the analysis of different types of food matrices (e.g. milk, eggs, fish and seafood), in order to detect the presence of foodborne pathogens;
- The LAMP method was successfully developed and optimized for the specific and sensitive detection of green mold, i.e., the pathogenic fungi *Trichoderma* spp., in substrates used for organic mushroom cultivation (compost and casing soil);
- The obtained low detection limits for *Trichoderma* spp. using the Real Time LAMP method indicate the great potential of the LAMP method as a sensitive and reliable diagnostic tool for laboratory and field conditions;

- The application of the LAMP method for a PoN approach in detecting *Trichoderma* spp. in casing soil is feasible when combined with field-appropriate DNA isolation methods, such as the Chelex 100 method optimized in this doctoral dissertation;
- The results obtained with real samples indicate that LAMP is a potent diagnostic tool for working with complex soil-like samples, such as compost and casing soil. With further adaptation and optimization, it can become the method of choice for early detection of pathogens that negatively affect food production;
- The LAMP method can also be used to detect *E. coli* from complex samples such as highly polluted river water;
- Further optimization and adaptation of the syringe-based DNA extraction method for (PoN) applications are needed to enable complete development of LAMP testing in the field.

To the best of my knowledge, this doctoral dissertation describes the first LAMP protocol for detecting *Klebsiella aerogenes* and *Trichoderma* spp., using newly designed LAMP primers for respective bacterial and fungal pathogens. It is important to emphasize that the Chelex 100 extraction method was adapted in this dissertation for use with meat samples and soil-like substrates, which is not found in the published scientific literature. Given these advancements and the overall results, this doctoral dissertation represents a significant contribution to the field of molecular diagnostics and its application within the “One Health” concept. This is especially true for the detection of bacterial pathogens in real food and water samples, as well as for identifying pathogenic molds in real soil-like substrate samples (compost and casing soil). Finally, the dissertation demonstrates substantial progress in increasing technology readiness level of the molecular diagnostic method for real-life application in field conditions.

7. Literature

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8. Supplementary materials

a)

T. harzianum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. auriculariae tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. endophyticum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. lentinulae tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. pollinicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. simmonsii tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. vermifimicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. xixiacum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
Trich-F3
Trich-B3 reverse

610 620 630 640 650 660 670 680 690 700
T. harzianum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCAATTAACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. auriculariae tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCAATTAACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. endophyticum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. lentinulae tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. pollinicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. simmonsii tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. vermifimicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. xixiacum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTCACACAGCGATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTACACAGCGTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
Trich-F3
Trich-B3 reverse

710 720 730 740 750 760 770 780 790 800
T. harzianum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. auriculariae tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. endophyticum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. lentinulae tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. pollinicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. simmonsii tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. vermifimicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
T. xixiacum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
Trich-F3
Trich-B3 reverse

810 820 830 840 850 860 870 880 890 900
T. harzianum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. auriculariae tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. endophyticum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. lentinulae tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. pollinicola tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. simmonsii tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. vermifimicola tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
T. xixiacum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA
Trich-F3
Trich-B3 reverse

910 920 930 940 950 960 970 980 990 1000
T. harzianum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. auriculariae tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. endophyticum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. lentinulae tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. pollinicola tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. simmonsii tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. vermifimicola tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
T. xixiacum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAACCTCATCAAGAAGGTGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTGCTTTCTGTCCTCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC
Trich-F3
Trich-B3 reverse

1010 1020 1030 1040 1050 1060 1070 1080 1090 1100
T. harzianum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
T. auriculariae tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. endophyticum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCCGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. lentinulae tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCCATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. pollinicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCCATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. simmonsii tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. xixiacum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGCAAGTTACCAGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1110 1120 1130 1140 1150 1160 1170 1180 1190 1200
 T. harzianum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. auriculariae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. endophyticum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. lentinulae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. pollinicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. simmonsii tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. xixiacum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTCCCCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1210 1220 1230 1240 1250 1260 1270 1280 1290 1300
 T. harzianum tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. auriculariae tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. endophyticum tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. lentinulae tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. pollinicola tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. simmonsii tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. vermifimicola tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. xixiacum tef1 TCAAGCCCGTATGGTGTGTCACCTTCGCCTCCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1310 1320 1330 1340 1350 1360 1370 1380 1390 1400
 T. harzianum tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. auriculariae tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. endophyticum tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. lentinulae tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. pollinicola tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. simmonsii tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 T. xixiacum tef1 GTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAAGCTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTGCC-GGTGACTCCAAGAACGACCCCCCATGGGTGCC
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1410 1420 1430 1440 1450 1460 1470 1480 1490 1500
 T. harzianum tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGATACGCCCC
 T. auriculariae tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTG
 T. endophyticum tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCG
 T. lentinulae tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACT
 T. pollinicola tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATGGCTGCA
 T. simmonsii tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATGGCTGCA
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGATAC
 T. xixiacum tef1 GCTTCTTTACCGCTCAGTTCATCGTATGAACACCCGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGATAC
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1510 1520 1530 1540 1550 1560 1570 1580 1590 1600
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1

T. pollinicola tef1 AGTTGCGCGAGCTCCAGGAGAAGATCGACCGCCGTACCGGTAAGGCTACCGAGACTGCCCAAGTTCATCAAGTCCGGTGACTCTGCCATCGTCAAGAT
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

1610 1620 1630 1640 1650 1660 1670 1680 1690 1700

T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1
 T. pollinicola tef1 GATTCCTCCAAGCCCATGTGCGTTGAGGCTT
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-F3
 Trich-B3 reverse

b)

10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1
 T. pollinicola tef1
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

110 120 130 140 150 160 170 180 190 200
 T. harzianum tef1 GCAACTCATTTCGGCCTCGA
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1 TAAGCTTCAACTCGTTTTGCCCCAAG
 T. lentinulae tef1 CCCAAC
 T. pollinicola tef1
 T. simmonsii tef1 TTCGAGAAGGTAAGCTTCAACTCATTTCGCCTCGAT
 T. vermifimicola tef1 A
 T. xixiacum tef1 CGA
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

210 220 230 240 250 260 270 280 290 300
 T. harzianum tef1 TTCTCCTTCAATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. auriculariae tef1 ATTC AATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. endophyticum tef1 TCTCCCTCCACATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. lentinulae tef1 TCTCCCTCCACATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. pollinicola tef1 TCTCCCTCCACATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. simmonsii tef1 TCTCCCTCCACATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 TTCTCCTTCAATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 T. xixiacum tef1 TTCTCCTTCAATTCAATTGTGCCCGACAATTCGAGAGAAATTTTCGTGTCAACAATTTTTCATCACCCCGCTTTGCATTACCCCTCCTTTGCAGCGAC
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

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          310      320      330      340      350      360      370      380      390      400
T. harzianum tef1  GCAAAATTTTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGTACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCATTTTT-CTGCTTCACTCTCACATCACAGCC
T. auriculariae tef1 GCAAAAAATTTTTT-GCTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGTACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCATTTTT-CTGCTTCACTCTCACATCACAGCC
T. endophyticum tef1 GCAAA-TTTTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGCACCCCACTAGCTCACTGCCTTTTTTTTCTGCTTCGCTCTCACTTCCAGCC
T. lentinulae tef1  GCAAA-TTTTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGCACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCTTTTTTTC-CTGCTTCGCTCTCACTTCCAGCC
T. pollinicola tef1 GCAAA-TTTTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGCACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCTTTTTTTC-CTGCTTCGCTCTCACTTCCAGCC
T. simmonsii tef1  GCAAA-AATTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTAAGTGGGGTTTCTTGTGCACCCC-CTAGCTCG-----TTTTTCTGCTTCGCTCTCACTTCCAGCC
T. vermifimicola tef1 GCAAAAAATTTTTT-GCTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGTACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCATTTTT-CTGCTTCACTCTCACATCACAGCC
T. xixiacum tef1   GCAAAAAATTTTTTGTGTGTTGGTTTTA GTGGGGTTTCTTGTGTACCCC-CTAGCTCACTGCATTTTT-CTGCTTCACTCTCACATCACAGCC
Trich-F2
Trich-Flc reverse
    
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          410      420      430      440      450      460      470      480      490      500
T. harzianum tef1  ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTTGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. auriculariae tef1 ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTTGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. endophyticum tef1 ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTTGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. lentinulae tef1  ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTC-GTCACTTTAGCAATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. pollinicola tef1 ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTC-GTCACTTTAGCAATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. simmonsii tef1  ATCATTCAACGTATTCTGTGCTCGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. vermifimicola tef1 ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTTGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
T. xixiacum tef1   ATCATTCAACGTGCTCTGTGCTTGTCACTTTAGCGATGCTAACCACATTTTCCATCAATAGGAAGCCGCCGAACCTGGCAAGGGTTCCTTCAAGTACGC
Trich-F2
Trich-Flc reverse
    
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T. harzianum tef1  TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. auriculariae tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. endophyticum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. lentinulae tef1  TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. pollinicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. simmonsii tef1  TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. vermifimicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
T. xixiacum tef1   TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
Trich-F2
Trich-Flc reverse
    
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          610      620      630      640      650      660      670      680      690      700
T. harzianum tef1  GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. auriculariae tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. endophyticum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. lentinulae tef1  GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. pollinicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. simmonsii tef1  GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. vermifimicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
T. xixiacum tef1   GGTATGTTCTTGCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTACAAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
Trich-F2
Trich-Flc reverse
    
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          710      720      730      740      750      760      770      780      790      800
T. harzianum tef1  CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. auriculariae tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. endophyticum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. lentinulae tef1  CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. pollinicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. simmonsii tef1  CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. vermifimicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
T. xixiacum tef1   CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGTTACTGGTGGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCAC
Trich-F2
Trich-Flc reverse
    
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810 820 830 840 850 860 870 880 890 900

T. harzianum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. auriculariae tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. endophyticum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. lentinulae tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. pollinicola tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. simmonsii tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. vermifimicola tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

T. xixiacum tef1 GCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCCCTGGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACTGCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCA

Trich-F2

Trich-Flc reverse

910 920 930 940 950 960 970 980 990 1000

T. harzianum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. auriculariae tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. endophyticum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. lentinulae tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. pollinicola tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. simmonsii tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. vermifimicola tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

T. xixiacum tef1 AGGAGACTTCCAATTCAATCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCGTCCTCCCATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTC

Trich-F2

Trich-Flc reverse

1010 1020 1030 1040 1050 1060 1070 1080 1090 1100

T. harzianum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. auriculariae tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. endophyticum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. lentinulae tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. pollinicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. simmonsii tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. vermifimicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

T. xixiacum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC

Trich-F2

Trich-Flc reverse

1110 1120 1130 1140 1150 1160 1170 1180 1190 1200

T. harzianum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. auriculariae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. endophyticum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. lentinulae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. pollinicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. simmonsii tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. vermifimicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

T. xixiacum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCGTGCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC

Trich-F2

Trich-Flc reverse

1210 1220 1230 1240 1250 1260 1270 1280 1290 1300

T. harzianum tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. auriculariae tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. endophyticum tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. lentinulae tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. pollinicola tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. simmonsii tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. vermifimicola tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

T. xixiacum tef1 TCAAGCCCGGTATGGTCTGTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAAGCTCACCCTGAGTCAAGTCCGTGAGATGCACCACG AGCAGCT CGT CGAGGGT GTT C

Trich-F2

Trich-Flc reverse

1310 1320 1330 1340 1350 1360 1370 1380 1390 1400
 T. harzianum tef1 GGTGACAACGTCGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. auriculariae tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. endophyticum tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. lentinulae tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. pollinicola tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. simmonsii tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 T. xixiacum tef1 GGTGACAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAAATTCGCCGTGGTAACGTTGCC - GGTGACTCCAAGAAGACACCCCCCATGGGTGC
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

1410 1420 1430 1440 1450 1460 1470 1480 1490 1500
 T. harzianum tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGATACGCCCCC
 T. auriculariae tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTG
 T. endophyticum tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCG
 T. lentinulae tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGCTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACT
 T. pollinicola tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGCTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCCGTC
 T. simmonsii tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGCTACGCCCCCGTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCCGTC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGATAC
 T. xixiacum tef1 CGCTTCTTTACCCGCTCAGGTCATCGTCATGAACCACCTGGCCAGGTCGGTGCCGGATAC
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

1510 1520 1530 1540 1550 1560 1570 1580 1590 1600
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1
 T. pollinicola tef1 AAGTTCGCCGAGCTCCAGGAGAAGATCGACCCGCTACCGGTAAGGCTACCGAGACTGCCCCCAAGTTCATCAAGTCCGGTGACTCTGCCATCGTCAAGA
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

1610 1620 1630 1640 1650 1660 1670 1680 1690 1700
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1
 T. pollinicola tef1 TGATTCCTCCAAGCCATGTGCGTTGAGGCTT
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-F2
 Trich-F1c reverse

T. harzianum tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. auriculariae tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. endophyticum tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. lentinulae tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. pollinicola tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. simmonsii tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. vermifimicola tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 T. xixiacum tef1 ACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGATCACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATATTGCCGCCGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGA
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

610 620 630 640 650 660 670 680 690 700
 T. harzianum tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. auriculariae tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. endophyticum tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. lentinulae tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. pollinicola tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. simmonsii tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 T. xixiacum tef1 GGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCTACACCCGTTGGTGTCAAGCAGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACT
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

710 720 730 740 750 760 770 780 790 800
 T. harzianum tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. auriculariae tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. endophyticum tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. lentinulae tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. pollinicola tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. simmonsii tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 T. xixiacum tef1 GCCAACTGGGCCGAGGCTCGTTACCAGGAAATCATCAAGGAGACTTCCAACCTTCAAGAAGGTCGGCTTCAACCCCAAGGCTGTTGCTTTCTGCCCA
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

810 820 830 840 850 860 870 880 890 900
 T. harzianum tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. auriculariae tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. endophyticum tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. lentinulae tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. pollinicola tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. simmonsii tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. vermifimicola tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 T. xixiacum tef1 TCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGCTCCAGCCCTCCACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCTGGCAAGTTCAACGGCAA
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

910 920 930 940 950 960 970 980 990 1000
 T. harzianum tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. auriculariae tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. endophyticum tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. lentinulae tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. pollinicola tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. simmonsii tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 T. xixiacum tef1 GACCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCCAAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATT
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

1010 1020 1030 1040 1050 1060 1070 1080 1090 1100
 T. harzianum tef1 GGAAACGGTTCTGTGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTGTGCTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCGTCG
 T. auriculariae tef1 GGAAACGGTTCTGTGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTGTGCTCACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCGTCG

T. endophyticum tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 T. lentinulae tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 T. pollinicola tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 T. simmonsii tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 T. xixiacum tef1 GGAACAGTTCCTCGGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCTCAAGCCCGGATGGTCGTACCTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCAACACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCCG
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

1110 1120 1130 1140 1150 1160 1170 1180 1190 1200
 T. harzianum tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. auriculariae tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. endophyticum tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. lentinulae tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. pollinicola tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. simmonsii tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 T. xixiacum tef1 AGATGCCACGACGAGCAGCTCGTGGGGTGTCCCGGTGACCAACGTTGGTTTCAACGTCAAGAACGTTCCGTTAAGGAATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c AATTCGCCGTGGTAACTGTTGC

1210 1220 1230 1240 1250 1260 1270 1280 1290 1300
 T. harzianum tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. auriculariae tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. endophyticum tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. lentinulae tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. pollinicola tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. simmonsii tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 T. xixiacum tef1 CGGTGACTCCAAGAAGACGACCCCGCATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATACGCCCGC
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c ATGGGTGCCGCTTCTTTCCCGCTCAGGTATCGTATGAACACCCCTGGCCAGGTGGTCCGGATAC

1310 1320 1330 1340 1350 1360 1370 1380 1390 1400
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1 GTTCTTGACTGCCACACT
 T. pollinicola tef1 GTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCCGCAAGTTCGCCGAGCTCCAGGAGAAGATCGACCGCGTACCGTAAGGCTACCGAGACTGCCCCCAAGT
 T. simmonsii tef1 GTTCTTGACTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

1410 1420 1430 1440 1450 1460 1470 1480 1490 1500
 T. harzianum tef1
 T. auriculariae tef1
 T. endophyticum tef1
 T. lentinulae tef1
 T. pollinicola tef1 TCATCAAGTCCGGTACTCTGCCATCGTCAAGATGATTCCTCCAAGCCCATGTGCGTTGAGGCTT
 T. simmonsii tef1
 T. vermifimicola tef1
 T. xixiacum tef1
 Trich-B2 reverse
 Trich-B1c

d)

T. harzianum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. auriculariae tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. endophyticum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. lentinulae tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. pollinicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. simmonsii tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. vermifimicola tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 T. xixiacum tef1 TTGGGTTCTTGACAAGCTCAAGGCCGAGCGTGAGCGTGGTATCACCATCGACATTGCTCTGTGGAAGTTCGAGACTCCCAAGTACTATGTCACCGTCATT
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

610 620 630 640 650 660 670 680 690 700

T. harzianum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. auriculariae tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. endophyticum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. lentinulae tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. pollinicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. simmonsii tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. vermifimicola tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 T. xixiacum tef1 GGTATGTTCTTCCATCAACTTACACAGCAATTAACAGCCAGTGTAAACAAGCAATTCACAGACGCTCCCGGCCACCGTGATTTTCATCAAGAACATGAT
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

710 720 730 740 750 760 770 780 790 800

T. harzianum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. auriculariae tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. endophyticum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. lentinulae tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. pollinicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. simmonsii tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 T. xixiacum tef1 CACTGGTACTTCCCAGGCCGATTGCGCTATCCTCATCATTGCCGCCGACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTATCTCCAAGGATGGCCAGACCCCGTGAGCAC
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

T. endophyticum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGCCGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. lentinulae tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. pollinicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. simmonsii tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 T. xixiacum tef1 CACCAACTGCCCTGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGGGCTGGCAAGTTCACCGGCAAGACCCCTCCTTGAGGCTATCGACTCCATCGAGCCCCC
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

1110 1120 1130 1140 1150 1160 1170 1180 1190 1200

T. harzianum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. auriculariae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. endophyticum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. lentinulae tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. pollinicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. simmonsii tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. vermifimicola tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 T. xixiacum tef1 AAGCGTCCCACGGACAAGCCCCCTCCGCTTCCCTCCAGGATGCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACGGTTCCTGTCCGCCGATCGAGACTGGTGTCC
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

1210 1220 1230 1240 1250 1260 1270 1280 1290 1300

T. harzianum tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. auriculariae tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. endophyticum tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. lentinulae tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. pollinicola tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. simmonsii tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. vermifimicola tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 T. xixiacum tef1 TCAAGCCCCGATGGTCGTCACTTCGCTCCCTCCAACGTCACCACTGAAGTCAAGTCCGTCGAGATGCACACG-AGCAGCTCGTCGAGGGTGTCCCG
 Trich-LB
 Trich-LF reverse

Trich-LF reverse

AAGTCCGTCGAGATGCAC

Supplementary Figure 1. Sequence alignment done in BioEdit v7.2.0 software (Informer Technologies, Inc.) to confirm genus level specificity based on complementarity of LAMP primer sequences with homolog target regions of *tef1* gene sequences of different *Trichoderma* species: *T. harzianum* - GenBank: OL435125, *T. auriculariae* - GenBank: OR548070, *T. endophyticum* - GenBank: KX689257, *T. lentinulae* - GenBank: OP832395, *T. pollinicola* - GenBank: MF939621, *T. simmonsii* - GenBank: OP562772, *T. vermifimicola* - GenBank: MN605882, *T. xixiacum* - GenBank: MN605885

- Alignment of *tef1* gene sequences of *Trichoderma* species with F3 and B3 (reverse complementary) primer sequences;
- Alignment of *tef1* gene sequences of *Trichoderma* species with the regions of FIP (F1c+F2) primer sequence (F1c reverse complementary sequence and F2 sequences separately aligned);
- Alignment of *tef1* gene sequences of *Trichoderma* species with the regions of BIP (B1c+ B2) primer sequence (B1c sequence and B2 reverse complementary sequence separately aligned);
- Alignment of *tef1* gene sequences of *Trichoderma* species with LF (revers complementary) and LB primer sequences.

Supplementary Table 1. The results of biochemical tests for microbial identification the bacteria originated from food samples used in this doctoral dissertation

SAMPLE NO.	SAMPLE SOURCE	GRAM STAINING	MORPHOLOGY	NITRATE REDUCTASE TEST	CATALASE TEST	OXSIDASE TEST	INDOLE TEST	VOGES-PROSCAUER TEST	METYL-RED TEST
1.	<i>E. coli</i> (control)	-	rod-shaped	+	+	-	+	-	+
2.	<i>K. aerogenes</i> (control)	-	rod-shaped	+	+	-	-	+	-
3.	Lettuce-1	+	cocci	-	+	+	-	-	-
4.	Lettuce-2 (<i>Bacillus</i>)	+	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested
5.	Carrot-1	+	rod-shaped	+	+	+	-	-	+
6.	Carrot-2	-	rod-shaped	+	+	+	-	-	+
7.	Cucumber-1 (<i>Bacillus</i>)	+	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested
8.	Cucumber-2 (<i>Bacillus</i>)	+	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested
9.	Chicken breasts-1	+	cocci	+	+	-	-	-	+
10.	Chicken breasts-2	+	cocci	-	+	-	-	-	+
11.	Chicken breasts-3 (<i>Bacillus</i>)	+	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested	Not tested
12.	Salami-1	+	cocci	+	+	-	-	-	+
13.	Salami-2	+	cocci	+	+	-	-	-	+

9. Extended abstract in Serbian

Uvod: Prema Organizaciji za hranu i poljoprivredu Ujedinjenih nacija - FAO (od *engl.* Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), procenjuje se da će do 2050. godine svetska populacija dostići skoro 10 milijardi ljudi, stvarajući povećanu potrebu za održivim snabdevanjem hranom i vodom (FAO, 2023). Mikrobiološki patogeni koji se prenose putem hrane i vode predstavljaju izazov za postizanje ovog cilja, s obzirom na stalni globalni porast slučajeva infekcija i time direktan uticaj na javno zdravlje i ekonomiju (Law i sar., 2015). Porast primera trovanja hranom na međunarodnom nivou dovodi do sve veće potražnje za bezbednijim prehrambenim proizvodima koji neće predstavljati opasnost za potrošače (Kvintela Baluja i sar., 2014; Baraketi i sar., 2018). Posebno je važno napomenuti da voda, ključna za mnoge aktivnosti u lancu ishrane, kao što su uzgoj i prerada hrane, može biti i medijum za prenos patogena. Stoga je neophodno zajedničko razmatranje rizika od patogena poreklom iz hrane i vode radi efikasnog očuvanja javnog zdravlja (FAO, 2023). Takođe, za održiv sistem proizvodnje hrane, neophodno je osigurati odsustvo patogena u svim fazama proizvodnje hrane, uključujući gajenje useva, budući da patogeni mogu značajno uticati na njihov prinos i kvalitet (Quintela Baluja i sar., 2014; Baraketi i sar., 2018). Ovo naglašava važnost primene rigoroznih kontrolnih mera tokom celog uzgojnog ciklusa radi zaštite potrošača i održavanja efikasnosti poljoprivredne proizvodnje. FAO i Svetska Zdravstvena Organizacija (*engl.* World Health Organization, WHO) ističu potrebu za standardizovanim alatima za procenu i upravljanje ovim rizicima na globalnom nivou, zagovarajući pristup „Jedno zdravlje“ (*engl.* One Health) koji integriše zdravlje ljudi, životinja, biljaka i životne sredine (WHO i FAO, 2003; FAO, 2023). Takođe, rano otkrivanje patogena u usevima od suštinskog je značaja za održivu poljoprivredu, smanjenje gubitaka prinosa i smanjenje upotrebe hemijskih tretmana, čime se čuva i bezbednost i sigurnost hrane i zdravlje životne sredine.

Poznato je da postoji preko 250 različitih bolesti koje se prenose hranom i koje godišnje imaju direktan uticaj na bar trećinu svetske populacije (Stein i Chirilă, 2017). Međutim, ove bolesti često nisu dovoljno prijavljivane i njihova učestalost se neretko potcenjuje. Globalizacija, transport hrane na veće udaljenosti od izvornih lokacija i različite faze u lancu snabdevanja predstavljaju izazove u istraživanju izbijanja bolesti prenosivih putem hrane i vode (Stein i Chirilă, 2017). Posebno je važno razumeti da patogeni koji se prenose putem hrane mogu ući, preneti se i potencijalno ugroziti bilo koju fazu lanca ishrane (Stein i Chirilă, 2017; Sahoo i sar., 2022;).

Još jedna značajna činjenica u vezi sa patogenima u hrani i vodi je njihova sve veća otpornost na antibiotike (White i sar., 2002; Taviani i sar., 2022). WHO je 2017. godine objavila „listu bakterija koje hitno zahtevaju nove antibiotike” kako bi se suzbila rastuća globalna antimikrobna rezistencija (Tacconelli i Magrini, 2017). Maja 2024, ova lista je ažurirana kako bi usmerila i podstakla istraživanje i razvoj novih antibiotika i alata za borbu protiv rastuće globalne otpornosti na antimikrobne lekove (WHO, 2024). Pomenuta lista uključuje bakterije koje se prenose putem hrane i vode, tako da se i *Klebsiella* spp. i *Escherichia coli*, čija je detekcija u hrani i vodi, respektivno, u fokusu ove doktorske disertacije, nalaze među ovim istaknutim vrstama. Dodatno, kroz razvoj alata za otkrivanje patogena štetnih za poljoprivredne useve, ova doktorska disertacija se bavi još jednim značajnim patogenom: gljivicom *Trichoderma* spp. za koju je poznato da ima negativan uticaj na prinos i kvalitet šampinjona, jedne od najčešće kultivisanih vrsta jestivih gljiva.

Osetljive i efikasne metode za otkrivanje patogena su od vitalnog značaja za bezbednu i održivu proizvodnju hrane. Idealne metode korišćene u ove svrhe bi trebalo da budu brze, pristupačne i jednostavne za korišćenje, uz minimalnu potrebu za obukom osoblja (Zhang, 2013). Standardni pristup detekciji mikrobioloških patogena obuhvata mikrobiološku kultivaciju na hranljivom medijumu, što podrazumeva pripremu uzorka, mikrobiološku kultivaciju u fazama (bujon za obogaćivanje, selektivni medijum, medijum za izolaciju) i biohemijsku identifikaciju kroz brojne testove za potvrdu specifičnih mikroorganizama (Cai i sar., 2007; Wang i Duncan, 2017; Vidic i sar., 2019). Međutim, ove klasične metode su zahtevne u pogledu vremena i resursa, obično traju 3–4 dana, nekad i duže (do sedam dana) kada je mala brojnost bakterija u uzorku koji se testira (Vidic i sar., 2019; Nehra i sar., 2022). Sem toga, ove metode ne mogu otkriti bakterije koje su vijabline, ali se ne mogu kultivisati (*engl.* viable but non-culturable, VBNC), jer one ne formiraju vidljive kolonije, što ograničava efikasnost i primenljivost mikrobioloških metoda kultivacije (Oliver, 2010; Gao i sar., 2021).

Molekularno-dijagnostičke tehnike, posebno PCR metode, revolucionalizovale su detekciju mikroorganizama omogućavajući njihovu bržu i precizniju identifikaciju uz visoku specifičnost. Ove metode se fokusiraju na detekciju genetičkog materijala (DNK ili RNK), što omogućava kako kvalitativnu, tako i kvantitativnu analizu (Moreno i sar., 2018). PCR metode su široko prihvaćene zbog sposobnosti da brzo umnože segmente DNK iz male količine uzorka, prevazilazeći ograničenja klasičnih mikrobioloških metoda (Law i sar., 2015; Nehra i sar., 2022). Ove karakteristike olakšavaju rano otkrivanje patogena, čak i pri niskim koncentracijama, uključujući i one iz VBNC grupe. Real Time PCR dodatno unapređuje ovaj

proces omogućavajući direktno kvantitativno praćenje umnoženog genetičkog materijala korišćenjem fluorescentnih boja (Kralik i Ricchi, 2017). Međutim, PCR metode zahtevaju specijalizovanu opremu i izuzetne higijenske uslove za rad, osetljive su na inhibitore prisutne u kompleksnim uzorcima i mogu proizvesti lažno pozitivne ili lažno negativne rezultate, najčešće zbog primene nespecifičnih početnica ili zbog nemogućnosti razlikovanja nukleinskih kiselina poreklom iz živih (aktivnih) i mrtvih (inaktivnih) ćelija patogena (Cangelosi i Meschke, 2014).

Petljom-posredovana metoda izotermalnog umnožavanja nukleinskih kiselina (*engl. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification, LAMP*), koju je 2000. godine razvila grupa japanskih naučnika (Notomi i sar., 2000), pruža značajne prednosti u detekciji patogena u odnosu i na PCR i na klasične mikrobiološke metode. LAMP se ističe zbog svoje brzine, jednostavnosti i pouzdanosti u umnožavanju nukleinskih kiselina, što ga čini veoma pogodnim za kompleksne uzorke poput kliničkih uzoraka, uzoraka hrane, vode i zemlje, gde PCR može biti otežan zbog prisustva inhibitora reakcije (Becherer i sar., 2020). Za razliku od PCR-a, koji zahteva kontrolisane ponavljajuće promene temperature (što se postiže posebnom aparaturom), LAMP radi na konstantnoj temperaturi koristeći *Bst DNA* polimerazu iz *Bacillus stearothermophilus*, osiguravajući visoku specifičnost uz minimalnu potrebnu opremu (Soroka i sar., 2021). Dodatno, LAMP, zajedno sa reverznom transkripcijom, omogućava umnožavanje RNK sekvenci direktno u jednom reakcionom sudu, što unapređuje njegovu efikasnost u detekciji RNK virusa (Li i sar., 2022). Sve ove karakteristike čine LAMP metodom od izbora za dijagnostiku na mestu potrebe (*engl. point of need, PoN*) tj. na terenu, omogućavajući praćenje u realnom vremenu, čime se pojednostavljuje i ubrzava proces detekcije u poređenju sa PCR-om i mikrobiološkim metodama.

Hipoteza i ciljevi istraživanja: Zagađenje hrane i vode patogenima predstavlja ozbiljan izazov za bezbednost hrane, što rezultira tegobama ljudi i životinja, povećanim brojem smrtnih slučajeva, kao i velikim ekonomskim opterećenjima za sistem javnog zdravlja. S obzirom na porast globalne populacije, postaje neophodno preduzeti korake kako bi se osiguralo snabdevanje bezbednom hranom u dovoljnim količinama za sve. Postizanje ovog cilja je moguće, između ostalog, i razvojem inovativnih dijagnostičkih alata za brzo i efikasno otkrivanje patogena duž celokupnog lanca vrednosti hrane (*engl. food value chain*), uključujući njihovo otkrivanje i u terenskim uslovima. U skladu sa svim navedenim aspektima, ova disertacija se koncentriše na razvoj, unapređivanje i primenu LAMP metode, koja omogućava

brzu, jednostavnu i pouzdanu detekciju na terenu. Hipoteze ove disertacije su da je **1)** detekcija zasnovana na LAMP-u je adekvatna za detekciju mikrobioloških patogena u hrani životinjskog i biljnog porekla, kao i u životnoj sredini, što odgovara paradigmi „Jedno zdravlje“ koju preporučuje FAO i **2)** LAMP pogodnija i efikasnija metoda u odnosu na najčešće korišćene metode za detekciju patogena poput mikrobioloških i PCR metoda.

Kako bi se evaluirale postavljene hipoteze, ova doktorska disertacija ima nekoliko ključnih ciljeva: **1)** unapređenje LAMP-a za detekciju patogena u kompleksnim matricama poput hrane (životinjskog i biljnog porekla), visokozagađene rečne vode i uzoraka nalik zemljištu, uz evaluaciju performansi LAMP-a u poređenju sa kultivacionim metodama i PCR-om kao zlatnim standardom za umnožavanje nukleinskih kiselina. U okviru cilja **1)** se nalaze **1.1.** koji obuhvata: uspostavljanje jasnih protokola za LAMP detekciju bakterijskih patogena u različitim matricama hrane koristeći bakteriju *K. aerogenes* kao model sistem i **1.2** uspostavljanje jasnih LAMP protokola za rano otkrivanje patogenih gljiva *Trichoderma* spp. u matriksu nalik zemljištu (MnZ), odnosno kompostu i pokrivci korišćenim za gajenje pečuraka. Važno je naglasiti da se u disertaciji koristi *de novo* dizajn specifičnih početnica i za *K. aerogenes*, i za *Trichoderma* spp. budući da ne postoje u literaturi. Finalni protokol obuhvata implementaciju kolorimetrijske detekcije LAMP proizvoda pomoću zlatnih nanočestica, čime se povećava nivo tehnološke spremnosti (*engl.* technology readiness level, TRL) za realnu primenu razvijenog protokola; **2)** evaluacija potencijalne primene LAMP-a u detekciji bakterija indikatora fekalnog zagađenja (*engl.* fecal indicator bacteria, FIB), poput *E. coli*, za procenu kvaliteta vode; i **3)** unapređenje protokola za brzu izolaciju nukleinskih kiselina iz uzoraka hrane i visokozagađene vode, sa mogućnošću primene u terenskim uslovima. Radi preglednosti, u okviru cilja **3)** se razmatraju **3.1.1** i **3.1.2** koji se bave protokolima izolacije DNK iz hrane i iz MnZ, respektivno, kao i **3.2** za izolaciju DNK iz visokozagađene rečne vode. Cilj **4)** se bavi izvođenjem konačnih zaključaka o primenljivosti razvijenih LAMP protokola u svrhe rane detekcije patogena bakterijskog i fungalnog porekla, u terenskim uslovima.

Materijal i metode¹: Za potrebe istraživanja u ovoj disertaciji izvedene su tri eksperimentalne postavke (**EP**) u okviru kojih je rađeno sledeće: **EP1)** razvoj i optimizacija LAMP protokola za detekciju *K. aerogenes* u uzorcima hrane; **EP2)** razvoj i optimizacija LAMP protokola za

¹ **Napomena:** za sve korišćene hemikalije i aparaturu detaljni podaci su navedeni u disertaciji, dok se u proširenom apstraktu, radi uštede prostora, navode samo nazivi npr. TSB medijum, bez navođenja proizvođača i zemlje porekla npr. TSB medijum (Oxoid, UK).

detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. u proizvodnji šampinjona; **EP3**) testiranje LAMP-a za detekciju *E. coli* u visokozagađenoj rečnoj vodi.

U okviru **EP1** korišćeni su uzorci različitog povrća: krastavac (*Cucumis sativus* L.), zelena salata (*Lactuca sativa* L.) i šargarepa (*Daucus carota* L.). Ovi uzorci su odabrani zbog njihovog direktnog kontakta sa zemljom tokom uzgoja, s obzirom da je zemljište jedan od glavnih izvora *K. aerogenes* u povrću. Svo povrće korišćeno u eksperimentalnom radu kupljeno je u lokalnom supermarketu u Novom Sadu, 10.03.2023. U EP1 korišćeni su i mesni uzorci – sveže pileće grudi i pileća salama lokalnog proizvođača, kupljena u lokalnom supermarketu u Novom Sadu 18.07.2023. Najpre je sprovedeno testiranje prisustva *K. aerogenes* u opisanim uzorcima. U slučaju uzoraka povrća, testiranje je podrazumevalo ispiranje komadića povrća sa 3 mL PCR vode, od čega je 1 mL potom prebačeno na TSA ploču i inkubirano u toku 24 h. Bakterijske kulture izrasle nakon inkubacije su potom korišćene za: 1) sub-kultivaciju pojedinačnih kolonija (morfološki različitih) na TSA podlogama, kako bi se dobile čiste kolonije, koje su potom podvrgnute biohemijskim testovima za identifikaciju mikroorganizama; 2) izolaciju DNK korišćenjem komercijalnog kompleta (KK) specijalizovanog za ovakav tip uzorka - GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification komplet [videti *Sekciju (S) 3.1.2.1, A*], praćenu Real Time LAMP reakcijom. U slučaju uzoraka mesa, testiranje je podrazumevalo inkubaciju 250 mg svakog tipa mesnog uzorka u TSB medijumu na 37 °C u toku 24 h. Nakon inkubacije, ovakvi uzorci su potom korišćeni za izolaciju DNK korišćenjem KK specijalizovanog za ovakav tip uzorka - DNeasy PowerFood Microbial komplet i Chelex 100 metode (C100m) (na način opisan u *S 3.1.2.3*).

Bakterijske kulture korišćene u EP1 (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Alcaligenes faecalis*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Salmonella enterica* i *Escherichia coli*) pripremane su 24 h inkubacijom (preko noći) na 37 °C na TSA podlogama.

Izolacija DNK iz različitih tipova uzoraka sprovedena je: 1) primenom KK specijalizovanih za svaki tip uzorka, prema uputstvima proizvođača i 2) primenom C100m za primenu u terenskim uslovima. Detaljnije, DNK izolacija iz bakterijskih kultura rađena je primenom GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification kompleta (videti *S 3.1.2.1*), za izolaciju iz uzoraka povrća korišćen je Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation komplet kao i C100m protokol prilagođen za ovaj tip uzorka (videti *S 3.1.2.2*), dok je za izolaciju DNK iz uzoraka mesa korišćen DNeasy PowerFood Microbial komplet, kao i C100m protokol prilagođen za ovaj tip uzorka (videti *S 3.2.1.3*).

Merenje koncentracije i čistoće dobijenih DNK određivano je spektrofotometrijski na BioSpec-nano spektrofotometru merenjem apsorbance uzoraka DNK od 2 µL na 260, 280 i 230 nm.

Ciljano, kontrolisano zagađenje uzoraka (tzv. „spajkovanje” od *engl.* spiking) hrane rađeno je na dva načina: 1) direktnim dodavanjem *K. aerogenes* gDNK ekstraktima povrća/mesa (videti *S 3.1.3.1 A* i *S 3.1.3.2 A*) i 2) inokulacijom povrća/mesa sa bakterijskom suspenzijom *K. aerogenes* (v. *S 3.1.3.1 B* i *S 3.1.3.2 B*).

Za dizajn LAMP početnica za detekciju *K. aerogenes* odabran je gen koji kodira histidin dekarboksilazu – *HDC* (Gene ID: 66602288). LAMP početnice za ovaj gen dizajnirane su primenom onlajn softvera Primer Explorer V5 software (<http://primerexplorer.jp>). Provera efikasnosti i specifičnosti novih LAMP početnica rađena je testiranjem tri seta početnica (PC, od *engl.* primer candidates) prvobitno odabranih na osnovu najboljih performansi) na 65 °C u toku 45 min. Nakon toga, testiranje specifičnosti odabranog PC seta rađeno je uz pomoć Real Time i Colorimetric LAMP-a na 65 °C u toku 30 min., čiji su produkti potom proveravani na 2% agaroznom gelu. Za Real Time i Colorimetric LAMP korišćeni su komercijalno dostupni kompleti proizvođača New England BioLabs, konkretno WarmStart® LAMP komplet (DNA & RNA) i Colorimetric LAMP 2x Master Mix (DNA & RNA). Osetljivost LAMP metode utvrđena je testiranjem serije razblaženja gDNK *K. aerogenes* (1:1, 1:10, 1:100, 1:1000 i 1:10000).

Dalja provera mogućnosti detekcije *K. aerogenes* gDNK korišćenjem LAMP-a sprovedena je testiranjem ekstrakata hrane spajkovanih sa gDNK i određivanjem granice detekcije (*engl.* Limit Of Detection, LOD) *K. aerogenes* gDNK u ovakvim uzorcima. Ovakvi DNK ekstrakti su dobijeni izolacijom DNK iz uzoraka pomoću KK i C100m, nakon čega su spajkovani sa *K. aerogenes* gDNK. Statistički značajne razlike u Tt vrednostima zabeleženim za sve testirane uzorke hrane utvrđena je jednosmernom analizom varijanse (*engl.* one-way analysis of variance, ANOVA) i *post-hoc* Tuckey-evim testom za nivo značajnosti $p < 0.05$, primenom softvera GraphPad Prism 8.

Uporedna analiza efikasnosti različitih metoda izolacije DNK, kao i njihovog uticaja na ishod Real Time LAMP-a, rađena je testiranjem uzoraka hrane inokulisanih sa *K. aerogenes* suspenzijom, koji su potom bili podvrgnuti izolaciji DNK korišćenjem KK i C100m. U cilju upoređivanja efikasnosti LAMP metode sa PCR-om, isti ovi uzorci su potom testirani Real Time PCR-om primenom Maxima SYBR Green/ROX qPCR Master Mix (2X) kompleta.

U okviru **EP2** rađeno je na razvoju i optimizaciji LAMP protokola za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. koji bi mogao da se koristi za kontrolu proizvodnje šampinjona. Ova faza podrazumevala je najpre prikupljanje uzoraka komposta i pokrivke sa gajilišta za organsku proizvodnju šampinjona kompanije EKOFUNGI DOO u Padinskoj Skeli, tokom juna i jula 2021. godine, u različitim fazama uzgoja *Agaricus bisporus* (šampinjona) (videti Tabelu 6). Prvo je izvršeno testiranje prisustva *Trichoderma* spp. u ovim uzorcima na tri različita načina: 1) posmatranjem „golim okom“ vreća za uzgoj iz kojih su prikupljeni uzorci, kako bi se ustanovilo da li je došlo do pojave zelene plesni koju uzrokuje *Trichoderma* spp.; 2) izolacijom čistih fungalnih kultura kroz proces kultivacije i ko-kultivacije iz prikupljenih uzoraka i 3) molekularnom identifikacijom – metabarkodiranjem. Nakon primene ovih različitih metoda za potvrdu prisustva *Trichoderma* spp., odabrano je nekoliko uzoraka (ukupno 9) za dalju analizu uz pomoć Real Time LAMP-a (Tabela 25).

Fungalne kulture korišćene u EP2 tj. *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Aspergillus carbonarius*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Penicillium halotolerans* i *Cladosporium allicinum* pripremane su kultivacijom na sladnom agaru (*engl.* malt agar, MA) i inkubacijom na 26 °C u toku 5–7 dana.

DNK izolacija iz uzoraka komposta i pokrivke rađena je: 1) primenom KK specijalizovanog za zemljišni tip uzoraka, konkretno GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kompleta prema uputstvu proizvođača (v. *S* 3.2.2.2 **B**) i 2) primenom C100m prilagođene za primenu u terenskim uslovima (v. *S* 3.1.2.2 **A**). DNK izolacija iz fungalnih kultura rađena je primenom Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kompleta (v. *S* 3.1.2.1). Merenje koncentracije i procena čistoće dobijenih izolata DNK urađena je spektrofotometrijski na isti način već opisan u delu o detekciji *K. aerogenes*. Ciljano, kontrolisano zagađenje tj. spajkovanje uzoraka komposta/pokrivke rađeno je na dva načina: 1) direktnim dodavanjem genomske DNK *T. harzianum* ekstraktima komposta/pokrivke (v. *Sekciju* 3.2.3 **A** i 2) inokulacijom uzoraka komposta/pokrivke fungalnom kulturom *T. harzianum* (v. *Sekciju* 3.2.3 **B**).

Za dizajn LAMP početnica za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. odabran je gen koji kodira translacioni elongacioni faktor 1 alfa – *tef1* (GenBank accession no.: OL435125), koji je dobro poznat kao sekundarni DNK barkod kod gljiva uključujući vrste roda *Trichoderma*. LAMP početnice za ovaj gen dizajnirane su primenom onlajn softvera Primer Explorer V5 software (<http://primerexplorer.jp>).

Provera efikasnosti i specifičnosti novih LAMP početnica rađena je testiranjem dva seta početnica (prvobitno odabranih na osnovu najboljih performansi) na 65 °C u toku 60 min. Nakon toga, testiranje specifičnosti odabranog PC seta rađeno je testiranjem uz pomoć Real Time i Colorimetric LAMP eseja na 65 °C u toku 30 min., čiji su produkti potom proveravani na 2% agaroznom gelu. Osetljivost LAMP metode utvrđena je testiranjem serije razblaženja gDNK *T. harzianum* (1:1, 1:10, 1:100, 1:1000 i 1:10000).

Dalja provera mogućnosti detekcije gDNK *Trichoderma* spp. korišćenjem LAMP-a sprovedena je testiranjem eDNA ekstrakata komposta/pokrivke spajkovanih sa gDNK i LOD-a *T. harzianum* gDNK (kao modela *Trichoderma* spp.) u ovim uzorcima. Ovi ekstrakti su dobijeni izolacijom DNK pomoću KK i C100m, nakon čega su spajkovani sa gDNK *T. harzianum*. Statistički značajne razlike u Tt vrednostima zabeležene za sve testirane uzorke hrane utvrđene su putem ANOVA analize i *post-hoc* Tuckey-evim testom, na način opisan za detekciju *K. aerogenes*.

Upporedna analiza efikasnosti različitih metoda izolacije DNK, kao i njihovog uticaja na ishod Real Time LAMP reakcije rađena je testiranjem uzoraka komposta/pokrivke inokulisanih sa *T. harzianum* kulturom, koji su potom bili podvrgnuti izolaciji DNK pomoću KK i C100m. U cilju upoređivanja efikasnosti LAMP-a sa PCR-om, isti ovi uzorci su potom testirani Real Time PCR-om primenom F3 i B3 LAMP početnica, kao i primenom PCR početnica iz literature.

U cilju razvoja LAMP eseja kuplovanog sa zlatnim nanočesticama za kolorimetrijsku detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. najpre je urađena sinteza i karakterizacija 20 nm zlatnih nanočestica (*engl.* gold nanoparticles, AuNPs) primenom protokola opisanog u Braiek i sar. (2016). Nakon toga je rađeno ispitivanje uticaja koncentracije soli koja dovodi do agregacije AuNPs – testiranjem koncentracija 1, 5 i 10 µL MgCl₂ različitih molariteta (2 mM, 20 mM i 2M). Potom su testirani različiti temperaturni i vremenski uslovi neophodni za vezivanje LAMP produkata za AuNPs: 1) bez inkubacije; 2) inkubacija na 55 °C u toku 20 min i 3) inkubacija na 60 °C u toku 10 min. Na kraju su odabrani sledeći uslovi za dalje testiranje LAMP-AuNP eseja: 2.5 µL LAMP produkata (koncentracija 32 ng/µL) inkubirano je sa 50 µL AuNP-a i 98 µL PCR vode na 65 °C tokom 10 minuta. Nakon toga, dodato je 2,5 µL 20 mM MgCl₂, a promena boje je posmatrana golim okom ili merenjem apsorbance rastvora, korišćenjem SPARK multimo čitača mikroploča.

U svrhe procene specifičnosti LAMP-AuNP eseja, AuNPs su inkubirane sa: 1) LAMP produktima tj. LAMP umnošcima dobijenim umnožavanjem *T. harzianum* gDNK (produkti

pozitivne LAMP reakcije); 2) mešavinom LAMP reakcije koja ne sadrži ciljnu DNK (negativna LAMP reakcija) i 3) LAMP produktima dobijenim dodavanjem nespecifične gDNK (izolovane iz *Bacillus subtilis*) u LAMP reakciju (nespecifična LAMP reakcija).

Da bi se odredila minimalna količina LAMP proizvoda koja se može detektovati pomoću AuNPs, sprovedeno je istraživanje koje je uključivalo testiranje serije razblaženja pozitivnih LAMP proizvoda u detekciji *T. harzianum* DNK. Paralelno, testirana su serijska razblaženja bez prisustva ciljne *T. harzianum* DNK. Korišćena su desetostruka razblaženja u opsegu od 2400 ng/mL do 2.4 fg/mL.

U okviru **EP3** rađeno je testiranje LAMP metode za detekciju prisustva *E. coli* u uzorcima visokozagađene rečne vode sakupljenim tokom maja 2022. godine. Uzorci su prikupljeni iz reke Dunav u Novom Sadu (Vojvodina, Srbija) sa tri različite lokacije za uzorkovanje u blizini ispusta za kanalizaciju (Slike 25-26).

Mikrobiološka potvrda prisustva *E. coli* u ispitivanim uzorcima rečne vode rađena je zasejavanjem uzoraka na selektivne ploče sa hromogenim koliformnim agarom (*engl.* Chromogenic Coliform Agar, CCA). Testirana su razblaženja uzoraka netretirane vode u rasponu od 1/2 do 10⁻² i ploče su kultivisane na 37 °C tokom 24 h. Kvantifikacija *E. coli* u uzorcima je postignuta brojanjem samo *E. coli* tj. kolonija koje su bile pozitivne na β-galaktozidazu i β-glukuronidazu, enzime sadržane u CCA.

DNK izolacija iz bakterijske kulture *E. coli* rađena je primenom GeneJET Genomic DNA Purification kompleta (v. S 3.1.2.1), dok je izolacija iz uzoraka vode rađena primenom prilagođenog protokola koji koristi špric filtere za ekstrakciju, opisanog od strane Kesberg i Schleheck (2013) (v. S 3.3.3.2., Slika 27). Merenje koncentracije i procena čistoće dobijenih izolata DNK urađena je spektrofotometrijski na BioSpec-nano spektrofotometru na isti način već opisan za *K. aerogenes*.

Procena mogućnosti detekcije *E. coli* gDNK u visokozagađenim uzorcima rečne vode primenom LAMP-a, rađena je testiranjem ekstrakata dobijenih na prethodno opisan način. U ove svrhe korišćene su početnice iz literature opisane u Song i sar. (2019), koje ciljaju *malB* gen, poznat kao prisutan u različitim sojevima *E. coli*. LAMP reakcije za sve testirane uzorke izvođene su na 65 °C u toku 30 min.

U cilju upoređivanja efikasnosti LAMP metode sa klasičnom Real Time PCR metodom, isti ovi uzorci su potom testirani Real Time PCR metodom primenom F3 i B3 LAMP početnica, kao i primenom PCR početnica iz literature.

Rezultati: Rezultati proizišli iz ove doktorske disertacije mogu se podeliti na sledeći način: 1) rezultati proizišli iz prve eksperimentalne postavke (EP1); 2) rezultati proizišli iz EP2 i 3) rezultati proizišli iz EP3.

Rezultati proizišli iz EP1- Merenje koncentracije i čistoće DNK izolata ukazalo je na to da su vrednosti koncentracije DNK svih uzoraka povrća (inokulisanih i neinokulisanih), izolovane Chelex 100 metodom (C100m), bile značajno više (od 70.20 do 273 ng/ μ L) u poređenju sa uzorcima izolovanim pomoću Plant/Fungi kompleta (od 5.31 do 28.35 ng/ μ L) (Tabela 11). U uzorcima dobijenim C100m, odnos apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{280} konzistentno je bio ispod 1.7, što ukazuje na vrednosti niže od donje referentne vrednosti (RV), osim u jednom uzorku neinokulisanih ekstrakta šargarepe koji je pokazao odnos iznad 1.9. Odnosi apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{230} za ove uzorke kretali su se od 0.29 do 0.75, čime su sve vrednosti bile ispod 2.0, tj. niži od donje RV. Nasuprot tome, uzorci dobijeni pomoću Plant/Fungi kompleta imali su značajnu varijabilnost u odnosima apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{280} , pri čemu su DNK uzorci ekstrakta salate, kako inokulisani tako i neinokulisani, konzistentno imali odnose ispod donje RV. Za sve ostale uzorke dobijene ovim kompletom, odnos A_{260}/A_{280} bio je iznad gornje RV. Odnosi apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{230} za uzorke dobijene pomoću kompleta kretali su se od 0.21 do 0.92 (ispod donje RV). S druge strane, kada su u pitanju uzorci mesa, merenje koncentracije i čistoće DNK ekstrakata ukazalo je na to da su vrednosti koncentracija DNK uzoraka (inokulisanih i neinokulisanih) izolovane putem C100m bile u rasponu od 10.08 do 59.42 ng/ μ L (Tabela 13). Slično tome, uzorci izolovani pomoću DNeasy PowerFood Microbial kompleta kretali su se u rasponu od 10.18 do 17.69 ng/ μ L, što je unutar koncentracionog opsega C100m. Uzorci dobijeni putem C100m imali su konzistentan odnos A_{260}/A_{280} ispod 1.7 za oba tipa DNK ekstrakata, sa izuzetkom spajkovanog uzorka pilećih grudi za koji je ovaj odnos iznosio 2.17. Odnos A_{260}/A_{230} za mesne uzorke kretao se od 0.36 do 0.54 (svi ispod RV od 2.0). Dalje, uzorci izolovani pomoću DNeasy PowerFood Microbial kompleta imali su konzistentne odnose A_{260}/A_{280} unutar referentnog opsega, kako za inokulisane, tako i za neinokulisane DNK ekstrakte mesa, osim za neinokulisani DNK ekstrakt pileće salame koji je imao odnos od 1.62. Odnosi A_{260}/A_{230} za ove uzorke kretali su se od 0.10 do 1.63, što je takođe ispod donje RV.

Prilikom dizajna LAMP početnica, rezultati *BLAST* analize su pokazali da sve sekvence *HDC* gena (76) različitih sojeva *K. aerogenes* pokazuju veliku sličnost. Na osnovu najboljih performansi (v. *S 1.3.1.1*), inicijalno su odabrana tri seta LAMP PC kandidata – PC1, PC2 i PC3 za dalje testiranje i odabir najboljeg seta početnica, koji će potom biti korišćen za dalju optimizaciju i istraživanje (Tabela 14, Slike 28–30). Rezultati testiranja početnica su pokazali da vreme reakcije od 30 min konzistentno dovodi do pozitivnih i stabilnih rezultata. Kao optimalan set LAMP početnica odabran je PC2, jer se pokazalo da omogućava brzu detekciju sa visokom pouzdanošću, bez rizika od pojave lažno pozitivnih rezultata (Grafici 1–3). Dodatno, i Real Time i Colorimetric LAMP su pokazali da PC2 set ima visoku specifičnost prilikom testiranja sa drugim bakterijskim vrstama (Grafici 4–5, Slike 31–33). Rezultati testiranja osetljivosti LAMP metode primenom Real Time LAMP pristupa dali su LOD od 240 fg/μL, dok je za Colorimetric LAMP iznosio 24 pg/μL.

Rezultati ispitivanja uzoraka hrane na kontaminaciju *K. aerogenes* potvrdili su odsustvo ove bakterijske vrste u svim ispitivanim uzorcima (Grafici 9–12, Dodatna Tabela 1). Rezultati Real Time LAMP-a pokazuju da je LOD za *K. aerogenes* gDNK u DNK ekstraktima hrane dobijenim korišćenjem putem C100m i spajkovanih sa *K. aerogenes* gDNK bio konzistentan u svim testiranim uzorcima hrane. Ovaj nalaz, ekvivalentan 0.4 pg/μL, ističe efikasnost metode (Grafici 13, 15, 17, 19 i 21). Pored toga, analizom Grafika 23 može se uočiti da su uzorci zelene salate, krastavca, šargarepe i salame imali slične *Tt* vrednosti pri svim testiranim koncentracijama. Najmanje koncentrovani uzorci su detektovani za otprilike 23–28 minuta. Nasuprot tome, uzorci pilećih grudi su imali duže *Tt* vrednosti, sa najrazblaženijim uzorkom koji je za detekciju zahtevao više od 29 minuta. Značajne statističke razlike primećene su između najrazblaženijih uzoraka zelene salate i pilećih grudi, kao i između najrazblaženijih uzoraka pilećih grudi i salame ($p < 0,05$) (Tabela 15). Uzorci dobijeni izolacijom korišćenjem Plant/Fungi kompleta imali su različite granice detekcije bakterijske gDNKu različitim DNK ekstraktima povrća. Za DNK ekstrakt šargarepe, detekcija je bila pouzdana do 0.04 ng/μL (što je ekvivalentno 40 pg/μL), kako pokazuju rezultati Real Time LAMP reakcije (Grafici 24 i 25). Uzorci krastavca su imali procenjenu granicu detekcije između 40–400 pg/μL, sa uspešnom detekcijom na razblaženju od 10^{-1} (Grafici 26 i 27). Slično tome, uzorak gDNK zelene salate imao je granicu detekcije od 0.04 ng/μL (Grafici 28 i 29). *Tt* vrednosti za DNK ekstrakte šargarepe i zelene salate spajkovanih sa *K. aerogenes* gDNK su bile slične, sa vrednostima koje su se kretale između 23 i 26 minuta, dok su za DNK ekstrakt krastavca primećene značajne razlike, posebno pri većim koncentracijama gde nije bilo pojavljivanja krive umnožavanja sve

do razblaženja od 10^{-1} (Grafik 30, Tabela 16). DNK ekstrakti mesa dobijeni korišćenjem DNeasy PowerFood Microbial kompleta imali su konzistentne granice detekcije za *K. aerogenes* gDNK. Rezultati Real Time LAMP reakcije ukazuju da je LOD za *K. aerogenes* gDNK u DNK ekstraktima dobijenim ovim kompletom bio $0.4 \text{ pg}/\mu\text{L}$ za uzorke pilećih grudi i salame (Grafici 31 i 33). Dodatno, rezultati prikazani na Grafiku 35 i u Tabeli 17 ukazuju na slične T_t vrednosti dobijene za oba tipa mesnih uzoraka, bez statistički značajnih razlika.

Prilikom ispitivanja uticaja načina izolacije DNK iz uzoraka hrane na uspešnost detekcije *K. aerogenes* primenom LAMP-a, pokazano je da su u eksperimentima u kojima je korišćen C100m za izolaciju DNK, pozitivne Real Time LAMP reakcije bile zabeležene u slučaju inokulisanih uzoraka šargarepe (oko 29 minuta) i zelene salate (oko 26 minuta), ali ne i kod krastavca (Grafik 36). Kontrolne LAMP reakcije, sa neinokulisanim uzorcima (bez prisustva ciljane gDNK) nisu imali detektovane krive umnožavanja, što znači da su reakcije bile negativne. Za mesne uzorke, i inokulisani uzorci pilećih prsa i pileće salame su kao rezultat imali pozitivne reakcije za oko 16 minuta. Kontrolni tj. neinokulisani mesni uzorci takođe nisu rezultovali pozitivnim reakcijama (Grafik 38). S druge strane, kada je korišćen Plant/Fungi kit, svi inokulisani uzorci povrća su rezultovali pozitivnim reakcijama, koje se javljaju između 22. i 27. minuta (Grafik 40). Nakon upotrebe DNeasy PowerFood Microbial kompleta dobijeni su slični rezultati za mesne uzorke kao nakon upotrebe C100m, sa pozitivnim reakcijama za pileću salamu i pileća prsa za oko 17. i 18. minuta (Grafik 42).

Prilikom testiranja istih ovih uzoraka pomoću Real Time PCR metode došlo je do pojave pozitivnih rezultata kod svih inokulisanih uzoraka povrća izolovanih putem C100m (Grafici 44 i 45) nakon oko sat vremena (nakon 25 ciklusa), što je dvostruko duže od vremena potrebnog za Real Time LAMP reakciju. Dalje, Grafici 46 i 47 pokazuju da je u slučaju primene Plant/Fungi kompleta do pojave pozitivne reakcije došlo samo u slučaju pozitivne kontrole. U slučaju mesnih uzoraka (Grafici 48 i 49), pozitivna LAMP reakcija se uočava samo kod inokulisanih uzoraka izolovanih pomoću KK, dok uzorci izolovani putem C100m nisu imali pozitivne rezultate.

Rezultati proizašli iz EP2 - Vrednosti koncentracije eDNK ekstrakata iz komposta i pokrivke, izolovanih putem C100m i uz pomoć GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kompleta, bile su sličnog opsega (Tabela 20). Koncentracije C100m-izolovane eDNK su se kretale od 4.44 do 71.87 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$, dok su koncentracije KK-izolovane eDNK bile od 4.20 do 53.79 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$. Odnos apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{280} za većinu testiranih eDNK ekstrakata komposta (K1, K10, K10* i K10#)

izolovanih putem C100m bio je ispod 1.7, što ukazuje na prisustvo proteina i drugih kontaminanata u ovoj vrsti uzorka. Kod eDNK uzoraka pokrivke (P9 i P10) ovaj odnos je bio iznad 2.0. Za ostale kompostne ekstrakte (K7 i K7#) i jedan uzorak pokrivke (P3), odnos je bio unutar referentnih vrednosti. Za sve uzorke izolovane putem C100m odnos apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{230} bio je ispod 2.0. Kod eDNK uzoraka izolovanih primenom GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kompleta, odnos apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{280} bio je oko 2.0, osim za uzorke P3 i K10# za koje je ovaj odnos iznosio 3.19 i 1.68, redom. Svi eDNK uzorci izolovani ovom metodom takođe su imali odnos A_{260}/A_{230} ispod 2.0.

Dodatni izolati eDNK iz komposta i pokrivke inokulisanih sa *T. harzianum* kulturom i izolovani putem C100m, imali su koncentracije od 7.03 do 50.63 ng/ μ L (Tabela 21). Izolati eDNK istih uzoraka izolovana GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation kompletom imali su slične koncentracije, u opsegu od 15.10 do 73.24 ng/ μ L. Kod svih uzoraka, odnos apsorpcije A_{260}/A_{280} i A_{260}/A_{230} bio je ispod referentnih vrednosti (Tabela 21).

Prilikom dizajna LAMP početnica, rezultati *BLAST*-a pokazali su da sekvence (ukupno 99) koje imaju značajnu sličnost sa sekvencom *tefl* gena, odabranom kao templet za dizajn početnica, vode poreklo od različitih vrsta roda *Trichoderma*. Na osnovu najboljih performansi, inicijalno su odabrana dva seta LAMP početnica, za dalja testiranja i odabir najboljeg seta početnica koji će se koristiti za sve dalje korake optimizacije i buduća istraživanja (Tabela 22, Slike 35–36). Rezultati testiranja početnica su pokazali da vreme reakcije od 30 min konzistentno dovodi do pozitivnih i stabilnih rezultata. Kao optimalan set LAMP početnica odabran je drugi set početnica (PC2), jer se pokazalo da LAMP reakcija sa njima omogućava brzu detekciju sa visokom pouzdanošću, bez rizika od pojave lažno pozitivnih rezultata (Grafici 50–52). Dodatno, i Real Time i Colorimetric LAMP su pokazali da odabrani set početnica ima visoku specifičnost prilikom testiranja sa drugim vrstama gljiva (Grafici 53–54, Slike 37–39). Rezultati testiranja osetljivosti LAMP metode primenom Real Time LAMP pristupa dali su LOD od 917 fg/ μ L (0.92 pg/ μ L), dok je za Colorimetric LAMP iznosio 9.17 fg/ μ L pg/ μ L.

Rezultati testiranja eDNK iz komposta i pokrivke dobijenih putem C100m (Grafici 58–59) i korišćenjem KK za izolaciju (Grafici 60–61) pokazali su odsustvo *Trichoderma* spp. u svim ispitivanim uzorcima koji su dalje bili korišćeni za inokulaciju sa *T. harzianum* kulturom (Grafici 9–12).

Rezultati Real Time LAMP reakcije pokazuju da je LOD za *T. harzianum* gDNK u eDNK ekstraktima komposta i pokrivke, dobijenim korišćenjem C100m i spajkovanih sa

T. harzianum gDNK, bila 4 pg/ μ L za uzorke komposta (Grafik 62) i 0.4 pg/ μ L za uzorke pokrivke (Grafik 64). Pored toga, Grafik 66 prikazuje da uzorci pokrivke imaju značajno niže Tt vrednosti i da kod njih postoji mogućnost detekcije većih razblaženja tokom 30 minuta reakcije. Nasuprot tome, izolati eDNK iz komposta imali su značajno više Tt vrednosti, sa dodatnih 6–7 minuta potrebnih za detekciju razblaženja od 1×10^{-1} *T. harzianum* gDNK u poređenju sa uzorcima pokrivke (Tabela 23). Uzorci dobijeni izolacijom korišćenjem kompleta GenElute™ Soil DNA Isolation pokazali su LOD za *Trichoderma* spp. od 0.4 pg/ μ L za uzorke komposta (Grafik 67) i 4 pg/ μ L za uzorke pokrivke (Grafik 69). Na Grafiku 71 može se uočiti da su Tt vrednosti kod oba ispitivana izolata DNK bile slične (Tabela 24), ali je statistički značajna razlika primećena za razblaženje 1×10^{-1} ($p < 0,05$) između ovih uzoraka.

Prilikom ispitivanja uticaja načina izolacije eDNK iz uzoraka komposta i pokrivke na uspešnost detekcije *Trichoderma* spp. primenom LAMP metode, pokazano je da je, u eksperimentima sa inokulisanim uzorcima pokrivke izolovanih putem C100m došlo do pojave pozitivnih LAMP reakcija posle oko 22 min (Grafik 74). Nasuprot tome, umnožavanje nije bilo primećeno u uzorcima inokulisano komposta (Grafik 72), kao ni kod kontrolnih, neinokulisanih eDNK uzoraka komposta i pokrivke. Međutim, kada je za izolaciju korišćen KK, pozitivna LAMP reakcija je zabeležena kod oba tipa inokulisanih uzoraka (komposta i pokrivke). Konkretno, u slučaju uzoraka komposta, uspešna detekcija LAMP-om dogodila se nakon otprilike 20 min (Grafik 76), dok detekcija nije bila moguća kod C100m eDNK izolata. Takođe, primena KK za izolaciju eDNK iz inokulisanih uzoraka pokrivke rezultirala je efikasnijom LAMP detekcijom, sa vremenom detekcije od oko 18 min (Grafik 78), što je kraće vreme u odnosu na uzorke pokrivke izolovane putem C100m. Nijedan od testiranih setova PCR početnica, bilo novodizajniranih ili preuzetih iz literature, nije pokazao specifičnu PCR reakciju (Grafici 80–83). Zbog toga nije bilo moguće upotrebiti iste ove uzorke za uporedno testiranje sa Real Time LAMP metodom.

U cilju testiranja razvijenog LAMP eseja za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. u realnim uzorcima komposta i pokrivke sa organskog gajilišta šampinjona, nakon sekvenciranja i makro- i mikroskopske analize, odabran je samo određeni broj uzoraka za dalju analizu (označeni zelenom bojom u Tabeli 25): K1, K7, K7#, P3, P9, K10, K10*, K10# i P10.

Rezultati Real Time LAMP analize ekstrakata dobijenih korišćenjem KK-a pokazali su da je pozitivna reakcija zabeležena u jednom od tri replikata uzoraka K1, P3 i P9, dok je za uzorak K7# pozitivan rezultat zabeležen u dva od tri replikata (Grafici 84 i 86). Pri testiranju istih

uzoraka eDNK izolovanih primenom C100m, nije detektovana pozitivna Real Time LAMP reakcija (Grafici 88 i 90).

Rezultati razvoja LAMP eseja kuplovanog sa zlatnim nanočesticama za kolorimetrijsku detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. pokazuju da optimalna koncentracija $MgCl_2$ koja treba da se koristi u konstrukciji ovog eseja iznosi 0.4 mM (Slika 42). Dalje, Slika 43 pokazuje da je inkubacija na 65°C tokom 10 minuta optimalna za adsorpciju LAMP proizvoda na AuNP. Testiranje specifičnosti (Slika 44) pokazalo je da samo pozitivne LAMP reakcije tj. prisustvo LAMP produkata sprečavaju aglomeraciju AuNP nakon dodavanja $MgCl_2$. LOD za LAMP-AuNP esej je 24 ng/μL (Slika 45), sa osetljivošću zabeleženom pri koncentracijama umnožaka od 240 ng/μL do 2.4 ng/μL, što je zahtevalo razblaživanje uzorka zbog prevelike koncentracije produkata.

U EP3 dobijeni rezultati su pokazali da su koncentracije DNK iz visokozagađenih uzoraka vode, izolovane primenom prilagođenog protokola sa špric filterima, bile u rasponu od 17.36 do 22.12 ng/μL. Apsorpcioni odnos $A_{260/A280}$ za sve testirane eDNK uzorke vode bio je konzistentno ispod 1.7, što ukazuje na značajno prisustvo proteina, fenolnih jedinjenja i drugih kontaminanata. Takođe, apsorpcioni odnos $A_{260/A230}$ za sve uzorke bio je ispod 2.0, sa vrednostima u rasponu od 0.28 do 1.83, što sugeriše prisustvo dodatnih kontaminanata.

Rezultati mikrobiološkog testiranja na prisustvo *E. coli* u uzorcima visokozagađene rečne vode pokazali su da je S1 uzorak imao 33.800 CFU *E. coli* na 100 mL vode, S2 uzorak 55.000 CFU na 100 mL vode, dok je S3 uzorak pokazao prisustvo od 4.300 CFU *E. coli* na 100 mL vode (Slika 46).

Prisustvo *E. coli* je uspešno detektovano pomoću Real Time LAMP metode u uzorcima S1 i S2. Nasuprot tome, kod uzorka S3 Real Tim LAMP reakcija je bila negativna, što je u skladu sa prethodno utvrđenim niskim prisustvom *E. coli* u ovom uzorku (Slika 46). Identični rezultati dobijeni su i primenom Colorimetric LAMP metode (Slika 47).

Grafik 94 prikazuje rezultate Real Time PCR analize na istim uzorcima visokozagađene vode. Pozitivni rezultati su uočeni samo u kontrolnom uzorku za oko 27 min., što je skoro dvostruko duže u poređenju sa vremenom potrebnim za pozitivne rezultate u Real Time LAMP reakciji. Međutim, važno je napomenuti da nije bilo pozitivnih reakcija ni u jednom od testiranih uzoraka vode (S1, S2 i S3).

Diskusija: Zagađenje hrane i vode je ozbiljan globalni izazov koji negativno utiče na javno zdravlje i ekonomiju, rezultujući povećanom stopom smrtnosti i opterećenjem zdravstvenog sistema. Tradicionalne mikrobiološke metode za detekciju kontaminacije hrane i vode oslanjaju se na uzgoj patogena, ali se, kao takve, suočavaju sa brojnim izazovima kao što su dugo vreme do dobijanja rezultata, ali i nemogućnost detekcije VBNC patogena, što može dovesti do pojave lažno negativnih rezultata (Schottroff i sar., 2018; Vidic i sar., 2019; Nnachi i sar., 2022). Metode bazirane na PCR-u su dovele do revolucije u polju mikrobioloških dijagnostičkih analiza, budući da detektuju specifičnu mikrobnu DNK brzo i pouzdano, prevazilazeći ograničenja metodologija baziranih na kultivaciji (Vidic i sar., 2019). Međutim, PCR zahteva precizne instrumente i čiste uslove za rad, što ograničava njegovu upotrebu u terenskim uslovima. Zbog toga postoji inicijativa za tehnologijama nezavisnim od infrastrukture, koje zadovoljavaju tzv. „ASSURED“ kriterijume² definisane od strane WHO za detekciju patogena na mestu potrebe u područjima sa ograničenim resursima (Campbell i sar., 2021). Trenutne tehnologije za detekciju patogena na terenu kombinuju molekularne metode, biosenzore, mikrofluidiku i nanomaterijale. Među njima se metoda izotermalnog umnožavanja nukleinskih kiselina, poput LAMP-a, izdvaja zbog svoje brzine, specifičnosti i jednostavnosti primene (Zhao i sar., 2015; Soroka i sar., 2021; Atceken i sar., 2023). Takođe, LAMP ima sposobnost da direktno detektuje patogene u uzorcima bez kompleksne pripreme, što ga čini idealnim za korišćenje u terenskim uslovima (Lakshmi i Kim, 2021). LAMP ne zahteva ni posebnu aparaturu za variranje temperature reakcije, kao što je slučaj kod PCR-a, jer je izotermalna tj. odvija se na istoj temperaturi.

U okviru ove doktorske disertacije urađen je razvoj, optimizacija i validacija LAMP metode za brzo, efikasno i visoko specifično otkrivanje patogene bakterije *K. aerogenes* u prehrambenim uzorcima biljnog (povrća) i životinjskog (mesa i mesnih proizvoda) porekla. Ova bakterijska vrsta je izabrana kao model za detekciju patogena primenom LAMP metode zbog svoje rasprostranjenosti u različitim vrstama namirnica i vodi. Osim toga, trenutno ne postoji literatura koja dokumentuje LAMP metode detekcije za ovu patogenu bakteriju (Cooney i sar., 2014). U literaturi nisu opisane ni sekvence LAMP početnica koje bi se mogle koristiti za detekciju *K. aerogenes*. Zbog toga je razvoj LAMP eseja opisan u disertaciji obuhvatio i *de*

² ASSURED je skraćenica za (A) *affordable*-pristupačno, (S) *sensitive* - osetljivo, (S) *specific*-specifično, (U) *user-friendly*-jednostavno za korišćenje, (R) *robust and rapid*- robusno i brzo, (E) *equipment-free* - sa minimalnom neophodnom opremom i (D) *deliverable to those who need them* - dostupno korisnicima kojima je najpotrebnije, kojom se označavaju osnovni kriterijumi koje WHO zahteva od eseja za primenu na mestu potrebe (PoN).

novo dizajniranje LAMP početnica. Set početnica boj 2 (PC2) je identifikovan kao najefikasniji za detekciju gDNK *K. aerogenes*, pokazujući odsustvo lažno pozitivnih rezultata i visok stepen specifičnosti i efikasnosti kada je testiran na druge nespecifične bakterijske vrste. Real Time LAMP je pokazao LOD od 240 fg/ μ L, što je osetljivije od Colorimetric LAMP metode sa LOD od 24 pg/ μ L. Ovakav rezultat može se pripisati činjenici da su fluorescentne interkalarne boje korišćene u Real Time LAMP testovima (Seyrig i sar., 2015; Quyen i sar., 2019a) često osetljivije od pH-osetljivih boja korišćenih u kolorimetrijskom pristupu (Tanner i sar., 2015; Poole i sar., 2017). Dodatno, za Real Time LAMP se koristi specijalizovani instrument za merenje promene fluorescencije u realnom vremenu (Genie® III), što omogućava detekciju krive umnožavanja koja predstavlja vid potvrde detekcije DNK u uzorku. Nasuprot tome, kolorimetrijska LAMP metoda opisana u ovoj disertaciji oslanjala se na jednostavnu vizuelnu detekciju „golim okom“, koja svakako može imati ograničenja u osetljivosti i kvantifikaciji.

Budući da ne postoje radovi u literaturi koji opisuju LOD za *K. aerogenes* primenom LAMP-a, ovaj LOD može se uporediti sa onim dobijenim za LAMP test za srodnu vrstu *K. pneumoniae* objavljenim od strane Dong i sar., koji iznosi 115 fg/ μ L (Dong i sar., 2015). Druga istraživačka grupa, Poirier i sar. u 2021. godini, razvila je LAMP test za detekciju *K. pneumoniae* i prijavila LOD od 100 fg/ μ L za fluorimetrijski pristup detekcije i 10 pg/ μ L za kolorimetrijski pristup (Poirier i sar., 202). Na osnovu ovih radova može se zaključiti da je LOD za LAMP detekciju razvijenu u ovoj doktorskoj disertaciji u istom redu veličina kao i LOD-ovi prijavljeni u naučnoj literaturi za detekciju drugih *Klebsiella* vrsta korišćenjem LAMP-a.

Na osnovu rezultata optimizacije LAMP reakcije, istraživanje je prošireno u pravcu procene osetljivosti detekcije bakterije *K. aerogenes* u uzorcima hrane, uključujući povrće (šargarepa, zelena salata, krastavac) i meso (pileće belo meso i pileća salama). Cilj je bio razviti Real Time LAMP metodu koja može biti korišćena izvan laboratorije (u terenskim uslovima) za sprečavanje širenja bakterije među potrošačima tj. konzumentima ovih namirnica. Metode izolacije DNK korišćene za pripremu uzoraka uključivale su modifikovanu Chelex 100 metodu (C100m) za izvođenje u terenskim uslovima i komercijalne komplete (KK) za izolaciju DNK specijalizovanih za određen tip uzorka – za izvođenje u laboratorijskim uslovima. Rezultati su pokazali da je C100m bila efikasnija za uzorke povrća sa LOD od 0.4 pg/ μ L, dok su KK rezultovali LOD-om od 40 pg/ μ L. Za mesne uzorke, obe metode rezultovale su istim LOD od 0.4 pg/ μ L.

Rezultati ove doktorske disertacije potvrđuju da je LAMP metoda razvijena za detekciju *K. aerogenes* efikasna i pogodna za primenu u nelaboratorijskim uslovima, dok su istovremeno ukazali na potrebu za daljom optimizacijom metoda izolacije DNK za određene vrste uzoraka, poput krastavca, koji zahtevaju specifičniji pristup, što je detaljnije objašnjeno u samoj disertaciji.

Poređenje Real Time LAMP i Real Time PCR metoda za detekciju *K. aerogenes* u inokulisanim uzorcima hrane pokazuje da su rezultati Real Time LAMP bili u skladu sa tipom biljnog materijala, dobro korelirajući sa razlikama u anatomiji delova biljaka koji su korišćeni za izolaciju DNK, kao i da je Real Time LAMP bio superiorniji u odnosu na Real Time PCR. Dalje, uzorci gDNK izolovanih iz povrća putem C100m, imali su drugačiji redosled amplifikacionih krivi u Real Time PCR reakciji u odnosu na Real Time LAMP (Grafici 44–45). Real Time LAMP je dao pozitivne rezultate za manje od 30 min, dok je istovremeno za dobijanje pozitivne reakcije pomoću Real Time PCR-a trebalo 2 puta, pa čak i više vremena. Za DNK ekstrakte povrća izolovane primenom KK, Real Time LAMP je uspešno detektovao *K. aerogenes* za manje od 30 min., dok je detekcija Real Time PCR-om bila neuspešna (Grafici 46–47). Kod uzoraka mesa, prisustvo *K. aerogenes* pokazano je samo u uzorcima gDNK izolovanih pomoću KK, za šta je bilo potrebno oko 45 minuta, dok je Real Time LAMP-u trebalo manje od 20 minuta za pojavu pozitivnih rezultata (Grafik 42; Grafik 49). Manja efikasnost Real Time PCR može se pripisati nečistoćama u izolovanoj DNK, koje potiču iz alkalnog-PEG pufera korišćenog u C100m za lizu ćelija. Ovaj reagens poboljšava prinos DNK, ali umanjuje njenu čistoću. S obzirom na to da je LAMP metoda otpornija na inhibitore i nečistoće, ove nepravilnosti nisu uticale na njen rad. Generalno posmatrano, ova studija ističe potrebu za daljom optimizacijom metoda izolacije DNK i uslova reakcije za obe tehnike, ukazujući na potencijal Real Time LAMP-a za terensku primenu (Vashishtha i Konigsberg, 2016).

U ovoj doktorskoj disertaciji uspešno je razvijena, optimizovana i validirana LAMP metoda za brzu, efikasnu i specifičnu detekciju patogenih gljiva *Trichoderma* spp. u uzorcima nalik zemljišnim (kompostu i pokrивci) koji se koriste za organsku proizvodnju šampinjona. *Trichoderma* spp. je odabrana zbog značajnih negativnih efekata na proizvodnju pečuraka, koji se manifestuju tek kada se formiraju tamnozeleno spore, čime se otežava kontrola njihove dalje propagacije u gajilištima (Šašić Zorić i sar., 2023). Takođe, LAMP metoda testirana je na

uzorcima komposta i pokrivke, uz optimizaciju izolacije eDNK primenljive na terenu. Izolacija eDNK je ključna za određivanje mikrobiološke raznovrsnosti zemljišnih uzoraka (Wydro, 2022), za koje je poznato da su jedni od od najizazovnijih okruženja zbog prisustva različitih vrsta i enzimskih inhibitora (Salonen i sar., 2010; Zielińska i sar., 2017). U literaturi je većina istraživanja fokusirana na upotrebu KK za izolaciju eDNK iz zemljišnih uzoraka, dok nedostaju rešenja za ekstrakciju i detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. u terenskim uslovima. (Nazar i sar., 1996; Filion i sar., 2003; Reeleder i sar., 2003; Park i sar., 2020).

U okviru ove disertacije je urađen i *de novo* dizajn LAMP početnica (PC) za *T. harzianum*, budući da u literaturi nisu pronađene odgovarajuće. Pokazano je da je set broj 2 (PC2) imao najpovoljnije karakteristike za specifičnu detekciju *T. harzianum* gDNK, sa kraćim vremenom neophodnim za pojavu pozitivnih rezultata (17 min) u poređenju sa PC1 (30 min) (Grafik 50). PC2 set je pokazao visoku specifičnost kada je testiran na drugim gljivama neretko prisutnim u sličnim uzorcima zemlje (Perrone i sar., 2007; Ghiaie Asl i sar., 2017; Latgé i Chamilos, 2019; Park i sar., 2020.; Jindo i sar., 2021).

Real Time LAMP metoda je omogućila detekciju *T. harzianum* sa LOD od 917 fg/ μ L (0.92 pg/ μ L) (Grafici 55–57), dok je Colorimetric LAMP pristup dao LOD od 91.7 ng/ μ L (Slika 40). Ove vrednosti LOD-a mogu se uporediti sa granicama detekcije za *Fusarium graminearum* i *F. oxysporum* iz literature, gde su korišćene LAMP metode (Niessen i Vogel, 2010; Li i sar., 2013). Upoređivanje sa PCR metodama pokazuje da je LAMP metoda za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. efikasna i nudi konkurentnu granicu detekcije, u opsegu drugih molekularnih metoda (Miyazaki i sar., 2009; Lee i sar., 2020). LOD postignuta u okviru ove doktorske disertacije za specifičnu detekciju roda *Trichoderma* pomoću LAMP metode može se uporediti sa LOD-om za PCR opisanom u radu Lee i sar. (2020), koji iznosi 500 fg/ μ L za detekciju *T. harzianum*. Međutim, tokom eksperimentalnog testiranja početnica iz pomenutog rada (sprovedenog u okviru ove doktorske disertacije) došlo je do izostanka reakcija u pozitivnim kontrolama. Ovakav rezultat dodatno naglašava značaj razvoja LAMP metode kao molekularnog alata za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. U još jednoj studiji koju su objavili Miyazaki i sar. (2009) prikazana je detekcija DNK *T. harzianum* pomoću Nested PCR-a sa LOD-om od 50 fg/ μ L. Ovo dodatno potvrđuje da je LOD LAMP metode za detekciju *Trichoderma* razvijene u ovoj disertaciji, u opsegu poređenja sa drugim molekularnim metodama prisutnim u naučnoj literaturi.

Na osnovu optimizacije LAMP reakcije, istraživanje je prošireno na procenu osetljivosti detekcije *Trichoderma* spp. u realnim uzorcima supstrata za organsku proizvodnju šampinjona, kao što su kompost i pokrивka. Ovi supstrati često sadrže spore *Trichoderma* koje se mogu brzo širiti unutar proizvodnih tunela. Stoga je rano otkrivanje ovih patogenih gljiva ključno za pravovremeno uklanjanje kontaminiranih vreća i sprečavanje daljeg širenja.

Za izolaciju DNK korišćene su dve metode: C100m za rad na terenu i KK- GenElute™ Soil DNA za rad u laboratorijskim uslovima. Rezultati su pokazali da je DNK izolacija bila efikasnija primenom KK, posebno za uzorke komposta, koji su kompleksniji za manipulaciju u poređenju sa uzorcima pokrивke. Uprkos tome, utvrđeno je da je LAMP reakcija dala pozitivne rezultate za obe metode izolacije u slučaju oba tipa uzorka (komposta i pokrивke), što potvrđuje efikasnost razvijenog LAMP protokola. Naime, LOD za *T. harzianum* je 0.4 pg/μL za eDNK uzorke pokrивke dobijene korišćenjem C100m, dok je za eDNK komposta LOD bio 4 pg/μL. Nasuprot tome, u uzorcima kod kojih je eDNK izolovana pomoću KK dobijene su vrednosti LOD od 0.4 pg/μL za kompost i 4 pg/μL za pokrивku. Niža efikasnost LAMP reakcije u kombinaciji sa C100m ekstrakcijom za kompost može se pripisati prisustvu huminskih kiselina koje inhibiraju analize DNK (Reuter i sar., 2009; Wnuk i sar., 2020). Istraživanje je pokazalo da su KK efikasniji za kompost, dok C100m pokazuje veliki potencijal za dalju optimizaciju u terenskim uslovima, posebno za uzorke pokrивke. Dalja optimizacija mogla bi uključivati promene u procesu homogenizacije uzoraka i dodatne korake za uklanjanje huminskih kiselina kako bi se metoda bolje prilagodila za terenske uslove (Wydro, 2022).

Ova doktorska disertacija bavila se i proučavanjem efikasnosti Real Time LAMP metode za detekciju *Trichoderma* spp. u realnim uzorcima supstrata za uzgoj pečuraka. Studija je pokazala da, iako je Real Time LAMP metoda generalno dobro korelirala sa rezultatima DNK metabarkodinga, imala je poteškoća sa uzorcima koji su sadržali nedovoljne količine DNK poreklom od *Trichoderma* spp. (npr. uzorak P10). S druge strane, DNK metabarkoding se, očekivano, pokazao kao osetljiviji, detektujući i vrlo male količine DNK koje su ispod granice detektibilnosti putem LAMP-a (Kredics i sar., 2018). Ovakav rezultat može biti posledica neravnomerne raspoređenosti spora poreklom od *Trichoderma* spp. u testiranim uzorcima. Ova hipoteza se takođe može primeniti na uzorke K1, P3 i K7#, gde pozitivna Real Time LAMP reakcija nije postignuta u svim testiranim ponavljanjima. Ovi nalazi naglašavaju izuzetan

potencijal LAMP metode, ali takođe ukazuju na potrebu za daljom optimizacijom i sveobuhvatnijim uzorkovanjem kako bi se poboljšala njena praktična primena.

Uporedna analiza između Real Time LAMP i Real Time PCR metoda nije sprovedena zbog nepostojanja specifičnih PCR početnica za *Trichoderma* spp. u literaturi. Naime, kao što je prethodno rečeno, PCR početnice opisane u radu Lee i sar. (2020) nisu dale pozitivne reakcije u kontrolnim uzorcima. Takođe, testirane su F3 i B3 početnice iz PC1 i PC2 setova kao potencijalne PCR početnice, ali nijedna od njih nije pokazala dovoljnu specifičnost, budući da su umnožavale gDNK i druge, ne-*Trichoderma* vrste gljiva (Grafici 80–83).

U okviru ove doktorske disertacije razvijen je novi esej koji kombinuje LAMP metodu sa zlatnim nanočesticama (AuNPs) za kolorimetrijsku detekciju LAMP proizvoda (Đisalov i sar., 2024). Esej koristi sposobnost oligonukleotida (LAMP produkata tj. umnožaka) da se adsorbuju na površinu AuNPs, sprečavajući njihovu agregaciju izazvanu $MgCl_2$ u pozitivnim LAMP reakcijama (Marin i sar., 2021). Kao rezultat, kod pozitivnih reakcija nije došlo do promene boje, dok su negativne reakcije izazvale promenu boje iz crvene u ljubičastu.

Rezultati specifičnosti ovog eseja su pokazali da su samo AuNPs u prisustvu pozitivnih LAMP reakcija zadržali stabilnost nakon dodavanja $MgCl_2$, dok su svi negativni kontrolni uzorci rezultovali agregacijom (Slika 44). Test je postigao LOD od 24 ng/ μ L za pozitivne LAMP proizvode, što je bilo vidljivo golim okom (Slika 45). Međutim, zbog visoke koncentracije reagenasa i početnica koja sprečava agregaciju AuNPs, bilo je potrebno razblažiti uzorke deset puta da bi se mogli razlikovati pozitivni od negativnih rezultata (Reuter i sar., 2009). Test je bio osetljiv na koncentracije umnožaka u rasponu od 240 ng/ μ L do 2.4 ng/ μ L. U razblaženim uzorcima, smanjeni nivo umnožaka doveo je do agregacije AuNPs, koju nije bilo moguće efikasno suprimirati (Kredics i sar., 2018). Efikasnost testa zavisi od veličine i oblika AuNPs, što znači da bi promene u vrsti AuNPs zahtevale ponovnu optimizaciju koncentracije soli i vremena reakcije. Ukratko, razvijeni LAMP-AuNP test je jednostavan, brz i prenosiv metod za detekciju LAMP proizvoda, što može značajno pojednostaviti trenutno važeće procedure za detekciju *Trichoderma* na farmama. Osim toga, ovaj test se može prilagoditi za analizu boje putem pametnih telefona, koristeći aplikacije poput besplatne MyLight aplikacije, koja omogućava slikanje i analizu rezultata (Reuter i sar., 2009; Kredics i sar., 2018; Marin i sar., 2021).

Zagađenje vode i hrane fekalnim bakterijama predstavlja značajan problem za javno zdravlje i ekonomiju, pri čemu *Escherichia coli* služi kao ključna fekalna indikatorska bakterija (FIB) (Walker i sar., 2019). Ovaj problem je posebno izražen u zemljama poput Srbije, gde nedostatak infrastrukture za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda dovodi do toga da se neprečišćene otpadne vode ulivaju direktno u reke, čime se dalje kontaminira lanac proizvodnje hrane (Baklan Green Energz news, 2022; Čista Srbija, 2022). Tradicionalne metode zasnovane na kultivaciji u cilju detekcije FIB su ekonomične i široko korišćene, ali su vremenski zahtevne i često zahtevaju nekoliko dana za potvrdne rezultate. Molekularne metode kao što su PCR i Real Time PCR nude prednosti u pogledu brzine, osetljivosti i specifičnosti (u odnosu na mikrobiološke metode), ali su izuzetno osetljive na kontaminante i nepraktične za terensku upotrebu (Moehling i sar., 2021). LAMP metoda predstavlja obećavajuću alternativu. LAMP je značajno manje osetljiva metoda na uticaj inhibitora prisutnih u sredinskim uzorcima, čineći je jednostavnom i robusnom metodom za detekciju patogena u zagađenoj vodi. Ova doktorska disertacija ističe izvodljivost primene LAMP-a za brzu i efikasnu detekciju *E. coli* u visokozagađenim uzorcima vode, odgovarajući na ključnu potrebu za pravovremenom procenom kvaliteta vode i kontrolom patogena, a u skladu sa konceptom „Jedno zdravlje“.

Detekcija patogena korišćenjem molekularnih metoda u velikoj meri zavisi od efikasnosti izolacije eDNK iz realnih, sredinskih uzoraka. Izolacija eDNK iz vodenih uzoraka je posebno izazovna, prvenstveno zbog začepjenja filtera do kojeg dolazi tokom filtracije uzoraka (Takasaki i sar., 2021). Pored toga, prisustvo različitih supstanci u sredinskim uzorcima može rezultirati niskom stopom čistoće i izuzetno malim prinosom ukupn eDNK, što dalje otežava molekularnu detekciju patogena (Goldberg i sar., 2016; Hunter i sar., 2019; Tsuji i sar., 2019; Bairoliya i sar., 2022).

Komercijalno dostupni kompleti za izolaciju DNK, kao što su DNeasy Blood and Tissue DNA Extraction komplet i PowerWater DNA Extraction komplet, obično koriste pristup zasnovan na filtraciji. Međutim, visoka cena ovih kompleta i potreba za visokohigijenskim laboratorijskim uslovima za rad mogu biti ograničavajući faktori za terensku primenu. Stoga optimizacija tradicionalnih metoda izolacije eDNK pomoću šprica predstavlja isplativiju i bržu alternativu i način za postizanje ASSURED kriterijuma.

Deo istraživanja sprovedenog u ovoj doktorskoj disertaciji bio je posvećen prilagođavanju protokola za pripremu uzoraka i izolaciju eDNK prethodno opisanog u radu Kesberg i Schleheck (2013) kako bi se unapredila njegova primena na terenu. Izmene su uključivale

promene u koraku prefiltracije, korišćenjem 10 µm filtera, a zatim filtraciju kroz 0.45 µm filtere za koncentrovanje bakterijskih ćelija. Novi protokol takođe je uključivao jednu inkubaciju na 65°C nakon dodavanja TPS pufera, čime je značajno smanjeno ukupno vreme analize na otprilike 45 minuta, u poređenju sa Kesberg i Schleheck protokolom koji je trajao oko 4 sata (Kesberg i Schleheck, 2013). S druge strane, u prilagođenom protokolu koji su opisali Lee et al. (2019), vreme reakcije je smanjeno do 30 minuta. Međutim, ova istraživačka grupa je sprovela LAMP detekciju ciljnih bakterija koristeći veštački kontaminirane uzorke vode, čime se zanemaruje svaki potencijalni uticaj bakterija koje su već prisutne u vodi na izmerenu koncentraciju ukupne izolovane eDNK. U protokolu razvijenom u ovoj disertaciji su uvedena tri dodatna koraka ispiranja kako bi se poboljšala čistoća eDNK. Prinos eDNK po tom protokolu kretao se od 17.36 do 22.12 ng/µL, što je u skladu sa rasponom prijavljenim od strane Kesberg i Schleheck (2013) i Lee i sar. (2019) (~20 ng/µL), ali sa nešto nižom čistoćom, verovatno zbog korišćenja veoma zagađenih vodenih uzoraka u ovoj studiji.

Postoje brojne studije u literaturi koje su istraživale upotrebu LAMP metode za detekciju bakterijske DNK u uzorcima vode (Martzy i sar., 2017; Lee i sar., 2019; Fu i sar., 2021; Khodaparast i sar., 2022;), ali većina koristi skupe KK za izolaciju DNK koji zahtevaju laboratorijske uslove (Martzy i sar., 2017; Fu i sar., 2021), dok neke koriste spajkovane uzorke vode (Lee i sar. 2019), što ne daje realnu sliku o koncentracijama ukupne eDNK koja bi se mogla očekivati u netretiranim uzorcima. U okviru ove doktorske disertacije analizirani su realni, netretirani, visokozagađeni uzorci vode iz reke Dunav kod Novog Sada (uzorci S1–S3). Kultivacija na selektivnoj podlozi potvrdila je prisustvo koliformnih bakterija (uključujući *E. coli*) u svim uzorcima.

Zatim je izvedeno poređenje rezultata analize putem Real Time PCR-a i dva LAMP metodološka pristupa (Real Time i Colorimetric). Do pozitivne LAMP reakcije došlo je samo u slučaju testiranja S1 i S2 uzoraka, dok je Real Time PCR detektovao samo kontrolni uzorak sa prečišćenom DNK (Grafici 92-93 i Slika 47). Izostanak pozitivne reakcije tj. krive umnožavanja u PCR reakciji u sredinskim uzorcima može biti posledica inhibitora poput fulvičnih i huminskih kiselina, metalnih jona i polifenola, koji su uobičajeni u visokozagađenoj vodi (Ijzerman i sar., 1997). Takođe, s obzirom da je *E. coli* samo jedna od mnogih koliformnih bakterijskih vrsta u ovakvim uzorcima, *E. coli* DNK može činiti mali deo ukupne eDNK, usled čega se može naći ispod granice detekcije Real Time PCR-a (Bartram i sar., 1996; Li i sar., 2021). Nasuprot tome, LAMP, poznat po svojoj otpornosti na PCR inhibitore, uspešno je

detektovao *E. coli* u uzorcima S1 i S2, ali ne i u uzorku S3, verovatno zbog manjeg prisustva *E. coli* u ovom uzorku (Lin i sar., 2012; Mori i sar., 2013b; Wang i sar., 2013). Ovi rezultati pokazuju ograničenja Real Time PCR-a za detekciju FIB-a u visokozagađenim uzorcima i takođe prikazuju LAMP kao alternativu koja bi se mogla koristiti za efikasniji monitoring bakteriološkog kvaliteta vode.

Zaključci: Na osnovu predložene hipoteze, definisanih ciljeva i dobijenih rezultata, mogu se izvesti sledeći glavni zaključci: **1)** LAMP metoda razvijena i validirana u okviru disertacije, primenjena za specifičnu detekciju patogenih bakterija i gljivica, pokazala se optimalnijom u odnosu na PCR i tradicionalne mikrobiološke metode kultivacije za iste patogene i **2)** detekcija bazirana na LAMP protokolima iz disertacije je adekvatna za detekciju patogenih bakterija u realnim uzorcima hrane biljnog i životinjskog porekla, i visokozagađene rečne vode, kao i za detekciju patogenih gljivica u realnim uzorcima matriksa nalik zemljištu, čime je pokazano da je LAMP kompatibilan sa pristupom „Jedno zdravlje”. Konkretno za LAMP detekciju patogene bakterije *Klebsiella aerogenes* u hrani biljnog i životinjskog porekla dobijeni su niski detekcioni limiti (LOD) primenom Real Time LAMP-a, što potvrđuje veliki potencijal ove tehnike kao dijagnostičkog alata. U disertaciji je takođe pokazano da je terenska detekcija patogena u hrani biljnog i životinjskog porekla primenom LAMP-a moguća u kombinaciji sa terenskim metodama za izolaciju DNA, kao što je metoda Chelex 100 (C100m) optimizovana u okviru ove doktorske disertacije. Dalje, LAMP je uspešno optimizovan za specifično otkrivanje zelene plesni tj. patogene gljivice *Trichoderma* spp. u supstratima koji se koriste za organski uzgoj šampinjona. Dobijen je nizak LOD za *Trichoderma* spp. primenom Real Time LAMP-a što još jednom potvrđuje veliki potencijal LAMP-a kao alata za dijagnostiku. Dodatno, LAMP se pokazao kao pogodan dijagnostički alat kako u laboratoriji, tako i na terenu budući da je pokazano i da je terenska detekcija *Trichoderma* spp. u pokrivci primenom LAMP-a moguća u kombinaciji sa terenskim metodama za izolaciju DNK, kao što je C100m optimizovana u okviru ove doktorske disertacije. Daljom adaptacijom i optimizacijom, LAMP metoda može postati prvi izbor za ranu i osetljivu detekciju patogena koji negativno utiču na proizvodnju hrane. Sličan zaključak se može izvesti i za primenu LAMP metode za detekciju bakterijskog zagađenja u vodi, na osnovu rezultata detekcije *E. coli* u visokozagađenoj dunavskoj vodi, s tim da je neophodna i dodatna optimizacija metode izolacije eDNK pomoću šprica koja se koristi za ove uzorke.

Prema saznanjima autora disertacije, ova doktorska disertacija prvi put opisuje LAMP protokol za detekciju *K. aerogenes* i *Trichoderma* spp. patogena, uz korišćenje novodizajniranih početnica i za bakterijski i za gljivični patogen. Važno je naglasiti i da je u disertaciji adaptirana Chelex 100 metoda za terensku izolaciju DNK iz uzoraka mesa i uzoraka nalik zemljištu, što se takođe ne može naći u dostupnoj publikovanoj naučnoj literaturi. Uzimajući u obzir ove činjenice, kao i sveukupne rezultate, može se reći da ova doktorska disertacija daje značajan doprinos polju molekularne dijagnostike i njene primene u okviru koncepta „Jedno zdravlje”, pre svega za detekciju bakterijskih patogena u realnim uzorcima hrane i vode, kao i za detekciju patogenih plesni u realnim uzorcima zemljišnog supstrata (komposta i pokrivke). Disertacija takođe jasno prikazuje i napredne korake ka optimizaciji LAMP metode za krajnju primenu u terenskim uslovima.

Author biography

Mila Đisalov was born on August 13th, 1993, in Zrenjanin. She completed her Bachelor academic studies in Biochemistry at the Faculty of Sciences in Novi Sad, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection. She completed her graduation work under the mentorship of Prof. Jelena Purać, Ph.D and graduated in 2017 by defending her final thesis titled "*In Vitro* Cultivation of Honey bee Midgut and the Effect of Acute Paraquat Exposure". Immediately after attaining her B.Sc., she enrolled in Master's academic studies in Molecular Biology at the Department of Biology and Ecology, where she worked in the Laboratory for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology under the supervision of Prof. Jelena Purać, Ph.D. Under her supervision, Mila wrote her Master's thesis entitled "Effects of Dietary Cadmium and Zinc on Catalase Activity and Protein Thiol Content in *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hbn.) Larvae", which she defended in 2018. She enrolled in Doctoral academic studies in Biochemistry in 2018 at the Faculty of Science in Novi Sad under the mentorship of Prof. Marija Lesjak, Ph.D and Ivana Gađanski, Ph.D, Senior Research Associate at the BioSense Institute. She completed her Ph.D. research in the Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Laboratory at the BioSense Institute, where she has been employed as a young researcher since April 2019.

During her doctoral studies, Mila was involved in preparing proposals for several provincial, national and international project grants. At the BioSense, she was also involved in the implementation of 7 national and 8 international scientific research projects, where she worked in the field of biosensor development, molecular tools for pathogen detection, cellular agriculture, and the development of lab-on-a-chip platforms.

During her career, she expressed affinity for working in the field of the promotion and popularization of science. Concretely, she was one of the co-founders of the student group "The BioSense Alt. Protein Project" established in 2020 at the BioSense, which was supported by The Good Food Institute (USA). Additionally, in 2021, she received the KOMUNALT project grant (full name: Improvement of Knowledge and Communication Skills of Scientists in the Field of Alternative Proteins), funded by the Center for the Promotion of Science. Within this

project, the first multidisciplinary conference dedicated to alternative proteins in Serbia was held.

She has co-authored 2 papers published in international journals of exceptional value (M21a category), one of which was as one of the first authors with equal contribution; 5 papers in top international journals (M21 category), two of which were as the first author; 2 papers in prominent international journals (M22 category); 16 papers presented at international conferences (M34 category); and 5 papers presented at national conferences (M64 category). She also published work in a thematic collection of national importance (M45) as the first author and launched one new technical solution (method) applied at the national level (M82).

In May 2024, she received, with other co-authors, the Tanner Award for the most cited paper in 2021, published in the journal *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*.

План третмана података

Назив пројекта/истраживања
<p>„ Optimization of the method for Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) of nucleic acids for field detection of food- and waterborne pathogens“</p> <p>„Оптимизација петљом-посредоване методе изотермалног умножавања нуклеинских киселина (LAMP) за примену у теренској детекцији патогена из хране и воде“</p>
Назив институције/институција у оквиру којих се спроводи истраживање
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Природно-математички факултет, Универзитет у Новом Саду • Институт БиоСенс, Истраживачко – развојни институт за информационе технологије биосистема, Универзитет у Новом Саду • Национални институт за пољопривредна, прехранбена и еколошка истраживања (ИНРАЕ), Париз, Француска
Назив програма у оквиру ког се реализује истраживање
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • „IPANEMA – Integration of PAper-based Nucleic acid testing mEthods into Microfluidic devices for improved biosensing Applications“, пројекат који је добио средства од програма за истраживање и иновације Европске уније Хоризонт 2020 у оквиру споразума о гранту бр. 872662 • Програм научноистраживачког рада Министарства науке, технолошког развоја и иновација Републике Србије (Уговор о гранту број 451-03-66/2024-03/200358) • ANTARES – пројекат по уговору о гранту бр. 739570
1. Опис података

1.1 Врста студије

У оквиру студије коришћени су *in vivo* тестови који су подразумевали микробиолошко узгајање бактеријских и фунгалних култура. Даље, спроведене су *in vitro* студије које су подразумевале: вештачку контаминацију тј. спајковање узорака, амплификацију нуклеинских киселина применом *LAMP* и *PCR* метода, раздвајање продуката амплификације на агарозном гелу и спровођење биохемијских тестова за идентификацију микроорганизама. На крају, у оквиру студије коришћени су и *in silico* тестови, у циљу дизајна *de novo LAMP* почетница за специфичну детекцију бактеријских и гљивичних патогена од интереса.

1.2 Врсте података: **квалитативни и квантитативни**

1.3. Начин прикупљања података

- секвенце гена и нуклеотида доступне у НЦБИ бази података;
- визуелизација продуката амплификације нуклеинских киселина на агарозном гелу;
- записи са спектрофотометарских одређивања концентрације и чистоће нуклеинских киселина;
- Excel и Word фајлови са подацима након *in silico* анализа;

- записи након амплификације нуклеинских киселина применом *LAMP*-а и *PCR*-а на одговарајућем уређају;
- фотографије резултата визуелне детекције *LAMP* реакције;
- преглед доступне литературе.

1.3.1 Употребљени софтвер и формат датотеке:

Ехсел фајл, датотека .xlsx

PDF фајл, датотека .pdf

Текст фајл, датотека .docx

JPG фајл, датотека .jpg

1.3.2. Број записа (код квантитативних података)

број варијабли: од 3 до 5, у зависности од методе

број мерења: мерење сваког параметра је извршено у

два или три репликата, у зависности од методе и

доступности узорка

1.3.3. Поновљена мерења

не

Да ли формати и софтвер омогућавају дељење и дугорочну валидност података?

да

2. Прикупљање података

2.1 Методологија за прикупљање/генерисање података

2.1.1. У оквиру ког истраживачког нацрта су подаци прикупљени?

Експерименти, спектрофотометарских мерења концентрације нуклеинских киселина након различитих примењених метода екстракције *DNA* из различитих типова узорака; амплификација нуклеинских киселина применом *LAMP* и *PCR* метода у циљу детекције патогена од интереса; визуелна детекција *LAMP* реакције; визуелизација продуката амплификације нуклеинских киселина на агарозном гелу.

Остало, *in silico* предвиђања специфичности *LAMP* почетница за детекцију бактеријских и гљивичних патогена од интереса; дизајн *de novo LAMP* почетница применом онлајн софтвера.

2.1.2 Навести врсте мерних инструмената или стандарде података специфичних за одређену научну дисциплину (ако постоје).

спектрофотометар, апаратура за електрофорезу на агарозном гелу, уређај за *Real Time PCR*, уређај за *LAMP*, уређај за визуелизацију нуклеинских киселина на агарозном гелу, програмски пакети за *in silico* анализе

2.2 Квалитет података и стандарди

2.2.1. Третман недостајућих података

Да ли матрица садржи недостајуће податке? Не.

2.2.2. На који начин је контролисан квалитет података? Описати

статистичким анализама, коришћењем контролних експеримената и поређењем добијених резултата са доступним литературним подацима из релевантних извора

<p>2.2.3. На који начин је извршена контрола уноса података у матрицу? Поређењем добијених података са доступним литературним подацима</p>
<p>3. Третман података и пратећа документација</p>
<p>3.1. Третман и чување података</p> <p>3.1.1. Подаци ће бити депоновани у у Репозиторијуму докторских дисертација у Универзитету у Новом Саду (CRIS) и Заједничком порталу свих докторских дисертација и извештаја комисија о њиховој оцени на универзитетима у Србији (NARDUS).</p> <p>3.1.2. URL: https://www.cris.uns.ac.rs/index.jsf и https://nardus.mpn.gov.rs/</p> <p>3.1.3. DOI није додељен</p> <p>3.1.4. Да ли ће подаци бити у отвореном приступу? Да.</p> <p>3.1.5. Подаци неће бити депоновани у репозиторијум, али ће бити чувани.</p> <p>Образложење</p> <p>Докторска дисертација са прилогом ће бити депонована у Репозиторијуму докторских дисертација у Универзитету у Новом Саду (CRIS) и Заједничком порталу свих докторских дисертација и извештаја комисија о њиховој оцени на универзитетима у Србији (NARDUS).</p> <p>3.2 Метаподаци и документација података нема метаподатака</p> <p>3.3 Стратегија и стандарди за чување података</p> <p>3.3.1. До ког периода ће подаци бити чувани у репозиторијуму? неограничено</p> <p>3.3.2. Да ли ће подаци бити депоновани под шифром? Не.</p> <p>3.3.3. Да ли ће шифра бити доступна одређеном кругу истраживача? /</p> <p>3.3.4. Да ли се подаци морају уклонити из отвореног приступа после извесног времена? Не.</p>
<p>4. Безбедност података и заштита поверљивих информација</p>
<p>4.1 Формални стандарди за сигурност информација/података</p> <p>4.1.2. Да ли је истраживање одобрено од стране етичке комисије? Не.</p> <p>4.1.2. Да ли подаци укључују личне податке учесника у истраживању? Не.</p>
<p>5. Доступност података</p>
<p>5.1. Подаци ће бити јавно доступни</p> <p>5.4. Навести лиценцу под којом ће прикупљени подаци бити архивирани. ауторство – некомерцијално – делити под истим условима</p>
<p>6. Улоге и одговорност</p>

6.1. Навести име и презиме и мејл адресу власника (аутора) података

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6.2. Навести име и презиме и мејл адресу особе која одржава матрицу с подацима

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6.3. Навести име и презиме и мејл адресу особе која омогућује приступ подацима другим истраживачима

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